

Closed $SU(N)$ Flux Tubes as Bosonic Strings

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We study, by means of numerical simulations using lattice techniques, the spectra of the fundamental ($k = 1$) and $k = 2$ closed flux tubes in $2+1$ -dimensional $SU(N)$ gauge theories. Our motivation is the elucidation of the low-lying excitation spectrum of the fundamental and $k = 2$ closed flux tubes - which can be thought of as bound states of two fundamental ones - and of how these compare to known effective string theoretical descriptions. This contributes towards the quest for the flux tube's effective string theoretical description.

We provide clear evidence that the effective string theoretical description, which provides a very good approximation for the fundamental closed flux tube spectrum, is the Nambu-Goto free string theory. Astonishingly, the spectrum of the fundamental closed flux tube can be very well-approximated by Nambu-Goto, even for short lengths that are comparable to its width. The correction terms, however, appear to be unnaturally small of order $\mathcal{O}(1/10)$ in appropriate units.

For $k = 2$, we find that, to a very good approximation, the eigenstates fall into sectors that belong to nearly pure antisymmetric and symmetric representations, showing that k -strings know about the full group theoretical structure of the $SU(N)$ gauge group rather than just about its center, Z_N .

We obtain convincing evidence that in the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation of colour, the ground states for $q = 0, 1, 2$, for flux tube lengths not too small, have energies that are very close to those predicted by Nambu-Goto free string theory. The correction terms appear to be typically of $\mathcal{O}(1-10)$ in appropriate units. This is in striking contrast to what we observe for the fundamental representation. In addition we obtain that the low-lying excited states, although stringy, appear to exhibit high deviations from Nambu-Goto. In general we find that the corrections appear to be particularly small when the "phonons" along the string have the same momentum and large when their momentum is opposite.

The ground states for $q = 0, 1, 2$ in the much heavier $k = 2$ symmetric representation are recognisably string like, although less convincing due to high systematic errors, which limit our ability to obtain any useful conclusion.

Even though non-stringy states have not been observed, we have been able to identify $k = 2$ eigenstates that correspond to doubly wound ($w = 2$) in addition to the bound $k = 2$ singly wound flux tube.

Publications The results presented in this thesis are partially based on the publications [1, 2] and proceedings [3, 4, 5]. Many of the results presented in Chapter 5 are still awaiting publication. More results that will eventually lead to a better understanding of the closed flux-tube in $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories are under way. These in addition with the previous results will hopefully soon lead to a longer publication. A publication on the spectrum of the closed fundamental flux-tube in $D = 3 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories is being prepared and will appear in the archive (arXiv) shortly.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Prolegomena

One of the most interesting and still unresolved problems of high energy physics, is the elucidation of the effective string theory which describes the confining flux tube forming a meson. Two color sources (quark-antiquark) in the confining $SU(3)$ gauge theory are joined together by a thin long open flux tube. The latter can fluctuate like a width-less string. This is the hypothesis which constitutes the basic idea of the effective string description of confinement. During the last three decades a lot of effort has been invested in the investigation of the open flux tube and its stringy behaviour. However, apart from the open flux tube formation, another formation can also be investigated in a pure theoretical background, aiming for delivering answers to similar questions as in the open case; namely whether this can also be described by an effective string theory model and if so how this string model looks like. This construction only appears in a special formulation of Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) with imposed periodic boundary conditions in the direction of the flux. This form is called the closed flux tube or torelon, referring to its solitonic nature. To visualise this object (see Figure 1.1) we can simply think of the length of the open flux tube with the color sources attached at its ends being equal to the longitudinal extent of the lattice; if we then impose periodic boundary conditions, it closes upon itself, the two colour sources “annihilate”, in the sense that colour indices get contracted, and what is left is a closed tube of flux. The closed string setup provides a theoretically cleaner framework for studying the effective string theory, since we avoid the contribution of the sources in the spectrum.

Figure 1.1: Visualisation of the “formation” of the closed flux tube on a Euclidean $D = 1 + 1$ space-time. Left Panel: A pictorialisation of an open flux tube. Right Panel: A pictorialisation of a closed flux tube running along a compactified spatial direction.

If the flux emanates from a source that transforms in the fundamental representation

of colour then the flux tube is called fundamental or $k = 1$ flux tube. If it transforms in a representation higher than the fundamental, then the emanating flux tube is called k -flux tube or k -string, with k being the \mathcal{N} -ality of the representation; this is explained in detail in Section 1.3.1. Whatever the representation of colour is, the flux tube is expected to be described by an effective string theory model.

All the effective string theoretical approaches that have been proposed so far treat the flux tube as a free string with possible self and boundary interactions and in no way do they incorporate any $SU(3)$ gauge processes, such as flux tube - glueball mixings that might occur in the “real world” of $SU(3)$. It, therefore, makes a lot more sense to use these approaches in order to describe the flux tube in the large- N limit (assuming that confinement occurs in $N = \infty$); at this limit such processes are suppressed by powers of $1/N^2$ and thus the flux tube behaves freely. A quick review on the large- N limit is provided in Section 1.4. Hence, the right effective string theory description for the confining flux tube is more likely to be tracked in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit of $SU(N)$ gauge theories. This is also consistent with the belief that it is only in the large- N limit where QCD is expected to become a string theory. Nevertheless, as it has been pointed out in several works, $SU(3)$ is not far at all from $SU(\infty)$ and, therefore, an effective string may provide a good description for the flux tube even at $N = 3$.

Confinement is one of the important properties of $SU(N)$ gauge theories and still an open problem of high energy physics. The difficulty of probing this property results from the fact that this is a non-perturbative effect. A well-known tool for studying arithmetically non-perturbative phenomena is the framework of lattice gauge theories. From the early 1980s lattice gauge theorists have been pursuing projects towards the identification of the closed confining flux tube spectrum in both $D = 3 + 1$ and $D = 2 + 1$ and have already achieved much in their effort of visualising this spectrum. The most important recent findings on the vacuum structure of the closed flux tube spectrum are presented in the Section 1.2.3. Among these the most recent [39, 40, 41, 42] indicated that in $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(N)$ the ground state energy of the closed flux tube for $k = 1$ and $k \geq 2$ can be well-approximated by the Nambu-Goto string rather than by any other known effective string theory prediction.

This astonishing finding, suggests that the ground state of the fundamental and $k \geq 2$ closed flux tube behaves at a very good approximation as a Nambu-Goto free bosonic string; this has been constructed in such a way so that it is only consistent in $D = 26$. This contributes significantly towards the quest for the right effective string theory. In practice, however, the ground state provides only a limited insight into the nature of the string spectrum and it is, therefore, important to perform accurate calculations of at least a few excited states in order to learn more about the right effective string theoretical description for the closed flux tube. So far in the literature there has never been a report of a comprehensive extraction of the closed flux tube spectrum in $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(N \rightarrow \infty)$, neither in the fundamental nor in $k \geq 2$. This is a hard task in a lattice calculation, since one can only hope to obtain accurate energies for those states which have a very high overlap onto the basis of operators that one is using.

Accepting this challenge, we decided to attempt an attack on this problem and try to reveal the spectra of the fundamental and the slightly different $k = 2$ closed flux tube in $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories. The extraction of the excitation spectrum with high accuracy can only be achieved using the variational calculation in combination with a large basis of operators. To overcome the problem we, therefore, constructed a large basis of operators so that we could maximise the overlaps onto those states with energy that need to be extracted. Lattice gauge theory treatment wants us to quantify the problem, in the

sense that we have to perform a number of calculations for particular values of N and lattice spacing a . We, therefore chose a number of configurations of N and a so that our final results lead us to specific conclusions. These numbers are inserted as parameters in a Monte-Carlo simulation (see Section 3.4) which calculates the arithmetical value of matrices as a function of time, the entries of which are correlators between two operators from our basis. These matrices are then inserted in a variational calculation (see Section 3.5.3) which eventually leads to the spectrum.

The plan of the thesis is as follows. In this chapter we present a brief historical overview and the basic theoretical background necessary in understanding the problem. In Chapter 2 we discuss the effective string theories and their results to which our data for $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ spectra are to be compared. Then we move to Chapter 3 in order to present the lattice gauge theories formulation and all the technicalities used for the extraction of the spectrum. Subsequently, after the lattice formulation has been explained we dedicate Chapter 4 for discussing how our closed flux tube operators were built. Having set the theoretical and technical part of the calculation we proceed to the presentation of the results. The $k = 1$ spectrum is presented in Chapter 5 and $k = 2$ in Chapter 6. Finally, in Chapter 7, we close the thesis by concluding and suggesting some future work. In the Appendix A we provide the explicit expressions of the operators we used in Appendix B the calculation and we briefly present our findings on the spectrum of the closed fundamental flux tube in $D = 3 + 1$.

Concerning the current chapter, in the next section a brief historic overview is presented, discussing the flux tube model and the important results obtained both in lattice calculations and in analytical approaches. We then discuss k -strings commenting on what they are, on what the expectations for the k -string tension are and on the type of lattice operators one can build in order to project onto such states. Then we provide a brief presentation on the large- N limit, where we try to address what is so special about it. Finally, we are presenting the general expectations that one would hope to obtain by probing the spectrum of the closed flux-tube. Let us now begin the discussion.

1.2 Historical Overview

1.2.1 Flux Tube Model

The flux tube model has been proposed as an attempt to reveal the physics of QCD in the confining regime. The first applications of the model were the understanding of the excitation spectrum of colour singlet states such as mesons, baryons and pure glue states (for example glueballs) and the study of their decays.

The model was proposed by Kogut and Susskind [6] in 1975. This first flux tube model was based on a Lattice Hamiltonian formulation for a gauge theory, more precisely for the $SU(2)$ gauge group. The basic idea that constitutes the formulation is that we can use the euclidean space-time lattice to develop the strong coupling expansion, in other words, a perturbative expansion in powers of g^{-1} rather than g . The degrees of freedom in the strong-coupling approach are the colour sources and the chromoelectric flux links (what we call links on the lattice). The colour sources in the strong coupling are exactly the same objects as the ones considered in the weak coupling. The only difference appears in the gauge fields, where in contrast to the weak coupling they are described by the position and the degrees of excitation of the flux links. We could say that by imposing the flux tube model, the field theory $SU(N)$ at low spatial resolution (for example at a lattice formulation with lattice spacing a), can be reformulated by the quantum mechanics of objects called

flux tubes that carry mechanical degrees of freedom only. The dependence on mechanical degrees of freedom reflects to the string interpretation of the flux tube. A flux tube is a real physical object that carries a finite energy per unit of length and provides the storage medium to the linearly rising quark-antiquark potential:

$$V(r) \simeq \sigma_f r, \quad \text{for } r \gg 1/\sqrt{\sigma_f}, \quad (1.1)$$

with σ_f being the string tension in the fundamental representation of colour. The different objects that can be studied using the flux tube formulation can be specified by the topology of the flux tube. For example, a meson could be visualised as a quark connected to an antiquark through a string formed by a flux tube; a baryon could be pictorialised as three quarks in a completely antisymmetric colour configuration, such as $\epsilon^{ijk} q^i q^j q^k$ joint together by a “Y-shaped” or “ Δ -shaped” combination of flux tubes; and finally a non-quark state can be thought of as a closed flux tube - according to the geometry this could model either a glueball or a torelon. For more information on the flux tube I refer the reader to the works [6, 7, 8].

1.2.2 String-like approach

This overview would not have been complete if we had not given credit to the effort invested in the analytical quantitative string-like description of the flux tube. Here we briefly present the most important developments in the quest of deriving an effective string theory model able to describe the dynamical properties of the confining flux tube. Parts of this discussion are also presented in Chapter 2 in much more detail. This subsection is, therefore, provided solely for historical purposes.

The first connection between a soliton formation in a field theoretical framework and string theory has been reported by Nielsen and Olesen in 1973 at [9], where the authors showed that the vortex line formation in the Abelian Higgs model can approximately be identified with the Nambu-Goto string.

The first attempt to derive an effective string theory model able to describe a fluctuating open flux tube was reported at [10, 11] by Lüscher, Symanzik, and Weisz in 1980. The action has been manifestly constructed in such a way so as to take into account the small string transverse fluctuations at large distances. This consists of the linearly rising potential term and a free Gaussian part, which can be found in Equation (2.74). This can be derived by imposing the static gauge in the Nambu-Goto action (Equation (2.4)) in the non-relativistic limit. In addition, they showed that in D dimensions the quantum fluctuations of the string give rise to a correction on the linearly rising behaviour of the static quark-antiquark potential by a universal Coulomb-like term of strength¹ $\pi(D - 2)/24$ such as:

$$V(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l - \frac{\pi}{24l} (D - 2) + \mathcal{O}(l^{-2}), \quad (1.2)$$

with $\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$ the string tension in a representation \mathcal{R} of the colour. The next important development appeared in 1983 by Arvis in [12]. Arvis worked out the Nambu-Goto string spectrum with fixed ends in an attempt to provide a formula for the quark-antiquark potential for the whole range of the string lengths l . As it turned out, rotational invariance indicates that this model is consistent only in the critical dimension of $D = 26$. The resulting potential

¹This is the well known Lüscher term.

for the ground state according to Arvis is equal to:

$$V(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l \sqrt{1 - \frac{\pi}{12\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l^2} (D - 2)}. \quad (1.3)$$

This has been named the ‘‘Arvis Potential’’ and can be used as an effective string theoretical description for an open flux tube at large quark-antiquark separations l for $D < 26$. Expanding the square root of the above formula in terms of $\pi(D - 2)/12\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l^2$ we see that the first two terms match the result of Lüscher, Symanzik and Weisz presented in Equation (1.2), thus reflecting the universality.

Adopting the approach of Lüscher, Symanzik, and Weisz in [10], De Forcrand, Schierholtz, Schneider and Teper in 1985 [13] showed that the energy of the closed flux tube exhibits a universal Coulomb term of strength $\pi/3$:

$$E(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l - \frac{\pi}{3l} + \mathcal{O}(l^{-2}). \quad (1.4)$$

The same result had also been conjectured by Rakow in 1984 using duality arguments [10].

The interesting result of Arvis derived in a pure string theoretical framework has been followed by an also important result proposed by Olesen in 1985 and presented in [14]. Olesen showed that at large flux tube lengths such problems as the appearance of tachyonic modes in the critical dimension and as the Lorentz invariance that breaks at dimension D other than the critical $D = 26$ are asymptotically disappearing. In other words, a string model which is strictly inconsistent in either three or four dimensions, such as Nambu-Goto, turns out that at large separations it is effectively consistent and can be, therefore, used as a description for the confining flux tube. In fact it is the result of Olesen that makes the application of the Arvis potential an adequate approximation for the ground state of the open flux tube plausible.

Although an effective string theoretical approach had already been suggested, a need for a Poincaré invariant action was still an open question. The first to propose a consistent string theoretical description were Polchinski and Strominger in 1991 in their work [15]. The authors proposed a string action with a manifest D -dimensional Poincaré invariance and conformal symmetry. This is an effective theory only because one may have to consider additional terms when expanding the action in derivative powers of the long-string soliton. Using this they calculated the spectrum for the torelon up to order $1/l$:

$$E(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l + \frac{4\pi}{l} \left(n - \frac{D - 2}{24} \right) + \mathcal{O}(l^{-3}). \quad (1.5)$$

For $D = 4$ the above equation matches the result of De Forcrand, Schierholtz, Schneider and Teper presented in Equation (1.4). Using the same approach, the energy levels of the torelon up to order $1/l^3$ had been calculated in two independent works, in [16, 17] by Drummond in 2004 and by Dass and Matlock in [18, 19] in 2006. The energy formula is given by:

$$E(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l + \frac{4\pi}{l} \left(n - \frac{D - 2}{24} \right) - \frac{8\pi^2}{\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l^3} \left(n - \frac{D - 2}{24} \right)^2 + \mathcal{O}(l^{-5}). \quad (1.6)$$

Unfortunately the approach of Polchinski and Strominger appears to be difficult and hard to manipulate, making the ‘‘right’’ effective action approach barely inaccessible. Hence, so

far this particular approach has not led to the revealing of higher $1/l$ order terms. Recently in [20], Aharony and Karzbrun adopted the approach of Lüscher and Weisz [10, 11] and improved this result to one order further.

Recovering their old ideas materialised in [10, 11] Lüscher and Weisz returned in 2004 with a new development towards the revealing of subleading terms in the confining flux tube energy formula of Equation (1.2). Improving the action proposed in [10, 11], they included boundary and higher derivative operators with some coupling, designed to describe end distortions of the open Dirichlet string [21]. The resulting action can be found in Section 2.5. Using an open-closed dual interpretation of the partition function they managed to constrain these couplings in $D = 2 + 1$. This led to an energy expression given by Equation (1.6) at $D = 2 + 1$. For the case of $D = 3 + 1$, they showed that the prefactor of the $1/l$ term is given by Equation (1.6), while the prefactor of $1/l^3$ depends on a single adjustable coupling only.

Aharony and Karzbrun [20] adopted an approach similar to that of Lüscher and Weisz in [21] so as to reveal the higher $1/l$ order terms of the spectrum of the closed flux tube. In this action the authors included additional higher-derivative operators with some coupling. The resulting action can be found in Section 2.6. Using an additional closed-closed dual interpretation of the partition function they constrained these couplings and improved the energy expression up to $\mathcal{O}(1/l^5)$. For more details see Chapter 2.6.

1.2.3 Lattice Overview for the closed flux tube

In the following three subsections an attempt to present some of the most important contributions to the investigation of the closed flux tube is made. Due to space limitations we mainly restrict this presentation to the closed flux tube. However, much effort has also been invested to deliver answers on issues associated with the open flux tube and k -open strings in general. In an attempt to seek important contributions in the direction of the open flux tube investigation names such as G. Bali [22], M. Caselle [23], S. Deldar [24], F. Gliozzi [25], J. Kuti [26], P. Majumdar [27], C Michael [28] and R. Sommer [29] could be possible entries in the search engine of the online archive. The presentation is divided in three parts in chronological order. In the first part we briefly discuss some of the oldest work aiming to reveal the ground state of the closed flux tube. In the second part, we discuss some important contributions reported in the last decade. Finally, in the third part, we present some of the very recent results.

1.2.3.1 First Steps

This thesis deals with the calculation of correlation functions of Polyakov loops the asymptotic behaviour of which leads to the closed flux tube ground state; we, therefore, start the lattice overview by discussing the first such calculations. The first attempts were reported in 1983; a typical example is the work of Parisi, Petronzio and Rapuano presented in [30]. Restricted by significant CPU time limitations they only performed a calculation of the correlation function for two unblocked² Polyakov loops on a single lattice volume in $D = 3 + 1$ $SU(3)$ gauge theories. This led to the derivation of the string tension. This has proven to be the first adequate extraction of the QCD string tension using lattice techniques with an estimation of $\sigma_f = (400 \pm 20\text{MeV})^2$. However, this result has been extracted by fitting the

²For information on the blocking procedure see Section 4.2 in Chapter 4.

linearly rising expression for the torelon ground state energy, overlooking any $1/l$ subleading terms.

The first attempt to observe such a term for the closed flux tube ground state was reported two years later by De Forcrand, Schierholtz, Schneider and Teper [13], in a calculation which provided an accurate asymptotic exponential decay of a torelon correlation function in $D = 3 + 1$ $SU(3)$ for the first time. More specifically, using the “source” method [13, 31] the authors showed that the ground state energy exhibits a Coulomb-like contribution which was shown to be remarkably consistent with the $\pi/3l$ term presented in Equation (1.4).

1.2.3.2 Important Contributions

Significant effort in the investigation of the spectrum of the confining closed k -flux tube has been invested by Teper in collaboration with other researchers who have contributed greatly in the field of lattice gauge theory, such as B. Lucini [32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37], U. Wenger [37], H. Meyer [38] and B. Bringoltz [39, 40, 41, 42]. Starting this presentation, we mention for historical purposes that the first comprehensive review on the $SU(N)$ gauge theories in $D = 2 + 1$ was released in 1998 by Teper [43]. However, most of the qualitative results on the torelon presented there had been replaced and improved by more recent works. From the beginning of this decade, Teper with Lucini on his side had been pursuing studies towards the revealing of the spectrum of the closed k -flux tubes. The first such study was reported in 2000 [32], when Teper and Lucini attempted to extract the $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ string tensions in $SU(4)$ and $SU(5)$ gauge theories in $D = 3 + 1$. The authors indeed obtained stable flux tubes of \mathcal{N} -ality $k = 2$ with ratios of k -string tension to fundamental being consistent, within errors, with the “Casimir scaling” (Equation (1.10)) and “MQCD” (Equation (1.12)) predictions; the average of these ratios (without taking in account the error bars) appeared to be in between the “Casimir scaling” and “MQCD” predictions. However, the low accuracy prohibited the authors to discriminate which prediction the flux tube prefers.

In 2001 Del Debbio, Panagopoulos, Rossi and Vicari [44, 45, 46] performed a calculation on the spectrum of the confining closed k -flux tubes in $D = 3 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theory for $k = 1, 2, 3$ and $N = 4, 6$. More precisely, they extracted the ground state of the fundamental representation of colour and, assuming that for a given \mathcal{N} -ality k the stable string is associated with the antisymmetric representation of colour, they projected onto this using the right Polyakov operators which project onto the $k = 2$ antisymmetric and $k = 3$ fully antisymmetric representations. Using the linearly rising energy expression with the Lüscher $\mathcal{O}(1/l)$ energy correction, as this is presented in Equation (1.5), they extracted the string tension for each irreducible representation mentioned in the previous line for several values of lattice spacings. Aiming for continuum physics, they adopted as a final result the string tensions corresponding to the smallest lattice spacing. By comparing the continuum ratios of the closed k -flux tube tension to the fundamental ($k = 1$) string tension σ_k/σ_f they obtained results consistent with “MQCD” (Equation (1.12)) within an accuracy of approximately 1%. On the other hand by comparing the results to the “Casimir Scaling” prediction (Equation (1.10)), they obtained significant deviations of approximately 10%; this was in accordance to the then recent results of Teper and Lucini [32]. They also attempted to extract the ground state of the $k = 2$ symmetric representation, with no clear evidence for a stable string.

In 2001 Teper and Lucini published the first comprehensive review [34] on the string

tensions of closed k -flux tubes with $k = 1, 2, 3$ in both $D = 2 + 1$ and $D = 3 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories. More precisely, they did so for $SU(4)$ and $SU(5)$ in $D = 3 + 1$ and for $SU(4)$ and $SU(6)$ in $D = 2 + 1$. Concerning the k -string tensions, they obtained that, while in $D = 3 + 1$ the ratio of the $k = 2$ string tension to the fundamental falls somewhere between the “MQCD” and the “Casimir Scaling” predictions, in $D = 2 + 1$ the results were much more accurate and the ratios closer to the “Casimir Scaling” prediction. In addition to the investigation of k -flux tubes, they also attempted to extract unstable k -flux tubes such as the one that emanates in the symmetric representation of colour and is expected to appear as a nearly stable state. They found that although in $D = 3 + 1$ dimensions the accuracy did not lead to any important clues, in $D = 2 + 1$ they obtain a flux tube whose ratio of string tension to the fundamental is close to the associated “Casimir Scaling” prediction (Equation (1.11)) for the symmetric representation. In addition, by performing a calculation on the fundamental flux tube in both $D = 2 + 1$ and $D = 3 + 1$ $SU(2)$ gauge theories, the authors showed that the ground state at large string lengths exhibits string formation appearing to be consistent with the bosonic effective string theory prediction of Polchinski and Strominger presented in Equation (1.5). Complementarily, the Appendix of [34] provides all the details one needs in order to construct operators projecting onto states of flux tubes at a particular representation of colour within \mathcal{N} -ality k . This has proven to be a useful guide for the construction of our operators (see Sections 1.3.3 and 4.4).

In 2002 Lucini and Teper released a paper [36] in which by performing a calculation in $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories at $N = 4, 6$ they derived that at first approximation the fundamental string tension of the confining closed flux tube is given by the result of Karabali, Kim and Nair presented in Equation (1.9).

Investing effort in delivering answers related to closed k -flux tubes, in 2002 Del Debio, Panagopoulos and Vicari [47] studied the spectrum of confining closed k -flux tubes in $D = 3 + 1$ $SU(3)$ gauge theory for $k = 0, 1, 2$. Using the same methodology as in their previous work with Rossi [44, 45, 46], they obtained highly accurate results for two string lengths at a single value of lattice spacing a . The authors calculated the ground states and the associated string tensions of the $k = 1$ fundamental representation, the $k = 2$ symmetric representation and additionally of the $k = 0$ adjoint representation. What they observed was that the closed flux tube correlators for the $k = 2$ symmetric representation could be well approximated by a sum of two exponentials in which the lowest state is given by the ground state of the fundamental representation with a tiny overlap (exponential prefactor) and the heavier state, which dominates the sum with a much larger overlap compared to the latter, is given by string tension whose ratio with the fundamental is approximately given by the “Casimir Scaling” in Equation (1.11). This picture is in good agreement with predictions based on \mathcal{N} -ality arguments according to which the unstable symmetric flux tube is expected to decay to the antisymmetric (for $N = 3$ this is the fundamental) with a decay amplitude suppressed at least by a power of $1/N^2$. Considering the adjoint representation, the authors argued that the ratio of its string tension with the fundamental can also be approximated by the “Casimir Scaling” conjecture.

It would have been a serious omission not to discuss the work of Kuti and his collaborators. Their work, mostly presented in conferences and workshops deals with the spectrum of the QCD string mainly for the open and partially for the closed flux tube. Although, we focus on the closed flux tube spectrum, it would be proper to mention that by probing several field theories [48, 49, 50, 51] such as $D = 3 + 1$ $SU(3)$, $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(2)$ and $D = 2 + 1$ $Z(2)$ the authors found that the open flux tube spectrum in both $D = 3 + 1$ and $D = 2 + 1$ exhibits the following behaviour. For very small quark-antiquark separations,

string formation does not appear and the approximate degeneracies disagree with effective string theory expectations. Additionally from some flux tube length upwards all the energy levels pose behaviour approximately consistent with Nambu-Goto.

The first attempt to reveal the full low-lying spectrum of the closed flux tube in $D = 3+1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories was reported by Juge, Kuti, Maresca, Morningstar and Peardon in 2003 [52]. Their work provides results for the $D = 3 + 1$ torelon spectrum in $SU(3)$. More precisely they have used an anisotropic lattice with a temporal lattice spacing much smaller than the spatial, in order to extract the excitation spectrum of a closed QCD flux tube for one value of the lattice spacing, three different string lengths and for several irreducible representations of the lattice symmetry of rotations³ about the flux tube axis (see Appendix B). In order to project onto these diverse irreducible representations, they constructed a basis of operators consisting of several Polyakov paths in two blocking levels. Although susceptible to systematic errors, their results demonstrate that the energy gap and degeneracies of all the excited levels for the largest flux tube length are approximately in agreement with the effective string theory of Polchinski and Strominger, while for the shortest lengths the results exhibit a significant structure which disagrees with the latter effective string description.

In 2004 Lucini, Teper and Wenger, released a paper in which they proposed and tuned a variety of new blocking and smearing algorithms (see Section 4.2) for constructing torelon and glueball operators able to project onto the physical lightest states with large overlaps. One of these proposed procedures has been adopted by us in order to construct torelon operators for the extraction of the low-lying spectrum in $D = 3 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories, briefly presented in Section B. Using these improved algorithms they calculated the k -string tensions for $N = 4, 6, 8$ and $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$. They obtained significant improvement on the calculated values of these tensions compared to older results, thus indicating the significance of using the new blocking and smearing procedures. The authors demonstrated that the continuum limits of the more accurate ratios of the k -string tensions to the fundamental fall between the “Casimir Scaling” and “MQCD” predictions. In addition they also obtained states associated with quasi-stable irreducible representations of colour, such as the $k = 2$, $k = 3$ symmetric and $k = 3$ mixed, with string tensions close to the “Casimir Scaling” prediction. Finally, it would be interesting to mention that a puzzling and interesting behaviour also showed up related to the pattern of degeneracies: it appeared that states within diverse irreducible representations of colour are, within errors, degenerate. For example the first excited state of the $k = 2$ antisymmetric flux tube is degenerate with the ground state of the $k = 2$ symmetric representation. This was unexpected surprising, since one would expect that spectra within different irreducible representations of colour would not “communicate”. In addition, they demonstrated that the power in the leading correction in $1/N$ of the k -string to fundamental string tension ratio lays between 1 and 2.

In 2004 Meyer and Teper investigated the spectrum of the closed k -flux tube in $D = 3+1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories for $N = 4, 6$ and $k = 1, 2, 3$ and the trivial irreducible representation of the lattice symmetry of rotations about the tube axis. Their results demonstrated that linear confinement occurs in $D = 3 + 1$ for $N \rightarrow \infty$ (assuming that $N = 6$ is close enough to infinity). They also demonstrated that the ground state of the fundamental closed flux

³Untill now all the works presented above were considering the trivial irreducible representation of the lattice symmetry of rotations about the tube axis. According to Appendix B in $D = 3 + 1$ this is the representation with quantum numbers $\{J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = +, q = 0\}$ and according to Section 4.4 in $D = 2 + 1$ this is the representation with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$. Both can be extracted using the simple line Polyakov operator in several blocking levels.

tube is in a good agreement with Nambu-Goto with a correction term $\mathcal{O}(1/l)$ having a coefficient that one expects for an effective string theory belonging to the universality class of Nambu-Goto. They also showed that the first excited state of the fundamental closed flux tube is very close to Nambu-Goto. In addition they found that the ground states of the $k = 2$ and $k = 3$ closed flux tubes are very near Nambu-Goto. In addition it was shown that the ratio of the $k = 2$ and $k = 1$ string tensions is more or less between the ‘‘Casimir Scaling’’ (Equation (1.10)) and the ‘‘MQCD’’ (Equation (1.12)) predictions.

In the international symposium on Lattice Field Theory in 2005, Kuti presented an exceptional seminar on the QCD string [26]. Through this he reviewed the most important theoretical developments in the effort of physicists to connect the flux tube to effective string theories; part of what he presented is included in Section 1.2.2 and Chapter 2. Among the lattice results he presented for several flux tube formations, he also showed results on the closed fundamental flux tube spectrum for the $D = 2 + 1$ $Z(2)$ gauge model. These results demonstrate firstly that they can be described well by Nambu-Goto even at short flux tubes and secondly that Nambu-Goto provides a much better description than the result of Lüscher and Weisz, Drummond and Dass and Matlock presented in Equation (1.6).

1.2.3.3 Latest Findings

A precise calculation of the continuum fundamental string tension in $D = 2+1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories was presented by Bringoltz and Teper in 2006 [39, 40]. The authors calculated the fundamental string tension for $N = 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8$ attempting to control all the systematic errors in order to enable a precise comparison to the analytic prediction of Karabali, Kim and Nair [53]. The comparison showed that the predicted values of the string tension are at most 3% away for all values of N and the associated discrepancies reduce as N increases, but they do not vanish. By extrapolating to $N \rightarrow \infty$ they obtain that the prediction of Karabali, Kim and Nair is exceptionally close to their results. However, the agreement is unlikely to be exact since the discrepancy is ~ 6 standard deviations away. In addition they found that the Nambu-Goto prediction is a very good approximation for the closed flux tube ground state down to relatively short lengths, while the Polchinski and Strominger prediction is insufficient.

A development on k -strings has recently been reported by Bringoltz and Teper in [41, 42]. The authors performed a calculation on the ground state energies of closed k -strings in $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theory for $N = 4, 5, 6, 8$ and $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$. By the dependence of the ground state on the string length they provided strong evidence that the ground state can be described by an effective string theory model that belongs to the same bosonic universality class as Nambu-Goto. In addition, by calculating the continuum values of k -string to fundamental string tensions ratios they obtained that these are remarkably close to those predicted by the ‘‘Casimir Scaling’’ with a discrepancy of 1 – 2% and much further from the predictions of ‘‘MQCD’’. By probing the N dependence of the ratio $\sigma_{k=2}/\sigma_f$ they demonstrated that it favours an expansion in $1/N$ rather than $1/N^2$ as this is suggested by a naive colour counting. Finally, they demonstrated that it is likely that the $k = 2$ spectrum knows about the full $SU(N)$ gauge group rather than just the centre of the group by means of the $k = 2$ states falling into sectors of the antisymmetric and symmetric irreducible representations; this is a question that will be further investigated in this thesis.

1.3 k -strings

1.3.1 What is a k -string?

Let us think of a flux tube as a hose of gluoelectric flux emanating from sources in the fundamental representation of colour. These sources are called quarks and they are objects that transform in the fundamental representation of $SU(N)$. We denote as antiquarks the colour sources that transform under the conjugate representation of $SU(N)$. If $N \geq 4$ there exist stable flux tubes emanating from colour sources that transform in colour representations higher than the fundamental. If these sources transform as $\psi \rightarrow z^k \psi; z \in Z_N$ under a global gauge transformation belonging to the centre of the $SU(N)$ gauge group then the flux tube is named a k -string. The integer k indicates nothing else but the \mathcal{N} -ality of the representation; the fundamental representation has \mathcal{N} -ality of $k = 1$.

Following the standard notation, we denote by q^i and q_i objects that transform under the fundamental and conjugate representations of $SU(N)$, respectively. We can construct objects transforming in higher representations of colour from tensor products of quarks q^i and antiquarks q_i . The \mathcal{N} -ality of a representation is defined as the number of upper minus the number of lower indices modulo N ; in other words it can be expressed as the number of quarks minus the number of antiquarks modulo N . A flux tube initiating from a colour source with \mathcal{N} -ality k , can be thought of as a bound state of k fundamental flux tubes. For the case of our interest $k = 2$, an open $k = 2$ flux tube can be pictured as in Figure 1.2. \mathcal{N} -ality is related to the symmetry under the centre of the group Z_N in a straightforward

Figure 1.2: Left Panel: Two separated open fundamental flux tubes. Right Panel: An open $k = 2$ flux tube as a bound state of two open fundamental flux tubes.

manner. Under the action of this symmetry, an object ψ with \mathcal{N} -ality k is multiplied by a phase $z^k = e^{(2\pi i k n)/N} : n = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$ such as $\psi \rightarrow z^k \psi$. The fact that the centre of the group is a symmetry of the theory can be shown easily, using the definition of the Wilson action which does not change under such transformations; by multiplying all the parallel links lying on a particular spatial slice by an element z of the group Z_N . In fact if we try to calculate a quantity which is not invariant under transformations of the group, we will find that the result would be null. Due to the charge conjugation symmetry, the string tension of states with \mathcal{N} -ality k and $N - k$ is the same. Thus, for a given value of N the independent number of strings with different \mathcal{N} -alities is given by $\text{Int}\{N/2\}$.

It should be mentioned that the term k -string refers to the most energetically favorable and thus stable flux tube, which according to the “Casimir Scaling” conjecture is the one that emanates from a colour source transforming in the fully antisymmetric representation of colour. A bound state will be energetically favorable only if this has the smallest possible string tension. In addition, states emanating in higher irreducible representations are also possible to exist. However, these states would be unstable since gluons will screen the sources down to the states with lower energy. Nevertheless, such screening is expected to get suppressed as N increases and, therefore, at large values of N one would expect that the unstable string states will actually show up as quasi-stable.

1.3.2 k -string tension

In this section we discuss the expectations for the k -string tension.

Unbound k -strings: This is the simplest case one can imagine, according to which the total flux is carried by k independent unbound fundamental flux tubes, leading to a string tension of:

$$\sigma_k = k\sigma_f \quad \text{with} \quad k = \min\{k, N - k\}. \quad (1.7)$$

However, we know that this scenario only occurs when the interaction between the k fundamental flux tubes is too weak. In fact that is what we expect if we take $N = \infty$, at which the interaction between colour singlets vanishes. This is, therefore, impossible to be observed for finite values of N , and we should think of the string tension as a "measure" of the k -flux tube binding.

Bound k -strings: Hence the string tension of the stable representation flux tube will have a value within the range of the fundamental to k times the fundamental. This range will also depend on the value of N .

$$\sigma_k = k_{\text{eff}}(N)\sigma_f \quad \text{with} \quad 1 < k_{\text{eff}}(N) < k. \quad (1.8)$$

Karabali, Kim and Nair Prediction for the fundamental flux tube: Concerning the fundamental ($k = 1$) flux tube, a prediction for the string tension was derived by Karabali, Kim and Nair in [53]. Although in $2 + 1$ dimensions $SU(N)$ gauge theory cannot be solved analytically, the authors have obtained a good approximation for the string tension based on studying the continuum Hamiltonian. They obtained that the tension of the fundamental flux tube in $D = 2 + 1$ should be approximately given by:

$$\frac{\sqrt{\sigma}}{g^2 N} = \sqrt{\frac{1 - 1/N^2}{8\pi}}. \quad (1.9)$$

This prediction is in a remarkable agreement with lattice results [39].

Casimir Scaling: According to the same prediction [53], the string tensions in $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories should be proportional to the quadratic Casimir of the representation of the flux. Although this is an exact result in $D = 1 + 1$, based on the idea of effective dimensional reduction driven by a highly disordered vacuum, Ambjørn, Olesen and Peterson [54], conjectured that this might also hold in $D = 2 + 1$ and $D = 3 + 1$. This hypothesis is also supported by calculations of the potential between charges in various representations. According to this hypothesis, the stable k -string arises for the antisymmetric representation quadratic Casimir which has the smallest value for a given k . Therefore, the ratio of σ_k with σ_f is given by:

$$\frac{\sigma_k}{\sigma_f} = \frac{k(N - k)}{N - 1}. \quad (1.10)$$

In addition, Casimir Scaling predicts the string tension of unstable k -strings, which emanate in representations with higher quadratic Casimirs. For the case of our interest, $k = 2$, we also obtain k -flux tubes in the symmetric representation with σ_{kS}/σ_f ratio given by the

formula:

$$\frac{\sigma_{kS}}{\sigma_f} = \frac{k(N+k)}{N+1}. \quad (1.11)$$

MQCD Prediction: Another prediction for the k -string tension arises in a number of calculations in MQCD [55, 56, 57]. According to this, the string tension of the stable k -string is given by:

$$\frac{\sigma_k}{\sigma_f} = \frac{\sin \frac{k\pi}{N}}{\sin \frac{\pi}{N}}. \quad (1.12)$$

This result holds, strictly speaking, for 3+1 dimensional $SU(N)$ gauge theories. However, it is also believed to work in $D = 2 + 1$ [55, 56, 57].

1.3.3 k -strings Lattice Operators

Let us first consider a loop of fundamental flux that winds once around the compactified spatial direction with length $l = aL_{\parallel}$, as the one in Figure 1.1, where a the lattice spacing and L_{\parallel} the longitudinal size of the lattice in lattice spacing units. On the Lattice, a generic operator $l_{\mathcal{C}}$ that is expected to couple to such a closed flux tube can be obtained by tracing the path ordered product of link matrices that live along a curve \mathcal{C} located onto a time slice and winding once around the compact dimension with matrices in the fundamental representation; this is nothing else but a Polyakov loop. A relevant $k = 1$ operator would, therefore, be denoted as $\Phi_{k=1} = \text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}\}$. If we now act with a center Z_N transformation by means of multiplying all the links $U_{x_{\parallel}}$ of a given x_{\parallel} -slice of the D -dimensional spatial lattice by the element $z \in Z_N$, then we see that this operator transforms as $l_{\mathcal{C}} \rightarrow z l_{\mathcal{C}} = z^{k=1} l_{\mathcal{C}}$. A k -flux tube operator will, thus, transform as $l_{\mathcal{C},k} \rightarrow z^k l_{\mathcal{C},k}$. In the next paragraph we focus on the structure of the $k = 2$ flux tube operators.

Generally a $k = 2$ operator can be constructed by a sum of operators that involve traces of powers and/or powers of traces of $l_{\mathcal{C}}$ and $l_{\mathcal{C}}^{\dagger}$, in such a way that the total power of $l_{\mathcal{C}}$'s minus the total power of $l_{\mathcal{C}}^{\dagger}$'s is equal to $k = 2$. An example of such an operator would be the $\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}^2\}\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}\}\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}^{\dagger}\}$. However, operators that involve $l_{\mathcal{C}}^{\dagger}$ are associated with massive spectra, and the projection onto such states is not one of our main objectives. Neglecting the possibility of using operators $l_{\mathcal{C}}^{\dagger}$, our operators will consist of a product of two traced $l_{\mathcal{C}}$ and a trace of the product of two $l_{\mathcal{C}}$. Both constructions transform the same under the center of the group: $l_{\mathcal{C},2} \rightarrow z^2 l_{\mathcal{C},2}$. Heuristically, this can also be obtained by the ‘‘compactification’’ of the the $k = 2$ open flux tube that emanates from the product of two fundamental colour sources as this is presented in the right panel of Figure 1.2. Closing this flux tube, the colour indices of the sources can get contracted in two possible ways, leading to either a ‘‘coupling’’ between two fundamental flux tubes which can be represented as $\Phi_{k=2} = \{\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}\}\}^2$ or a single tube of fundamental flux that winds twice around the torus and can be modelled as $\Phi_{k=2} = \text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}^2\}$.

Using the decomposition of two fundamental colour sources according to the relevant Young-tableau notation (Equation (4.19)), it can be obtained that linear combinations of $\{\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}\}\}^2$ and $\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}^2\}$ correspond to the totally antisymmetric $k = 2A$ and totally symmetric $k = 2S$ irreducible representations. More precisely, these operators are written as: $\Phi_{k=2A} = [\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}^2\} - \{\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}\}\}^2] / 2$ and $\Phi_{k=2S} = [\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}^2\} + \{\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}\}\}^2] / 2$.

Another type of $k = 2$ operator has also been considered. These are the operators that

carry fundamental flux and wind twice ($w = 2$) around the torus, by means of exhibiting a periodicity of two longitudinal lattice extents. Even though we mentioned that $\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}^2\}$ can be thought of as a doubly-wound loop of fundamental flux, this is constructed using the Polyakov loop $l_{\mathcal{C}}$ as a main component. This Polyakov loop initiates and ends at the same lattice site within one longitudinal lattice extent L_{\parallel} and, therefore, has a periodicity of only one L_{\parallel} . Due to the strong $k = 2$ binding, and the fact that the two components are close to each other, it is more likely that the operator would be mostly bound into a singly-wound $k = 2$ flux tube. Hence, it is proper to construct $k = 2$ operators with periodicity of two L_{\parallel} . A typical operator for such a flux tube will be given by $\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}l_{\mathcal{C}'}\}$, where the two single-winding paths \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' are in general not the same but the joint path $\tilde{\mathcal{C}} = \mathcal{C}\mathcal{C}'$ is continuous and periodic with period of $2L_{\parallel}$.

It should be clear that using just operators of this kind we cannot project onto the non-trivial quantum numbers, hence the construction of the relevant operators has to change slightly in order to encode the quantum number of Parity P within the Lattice operators -this can be achieved by building operators that transform irreducibly under parity transformations. Thus, since a detailed presentation of the construction of the operators is of great importance, we dedicate a chapter on a discussion on the particulars of this procedure.

1.4 Large- N limit

1.4.1 General

As pointed out by 't Hooft [58, 59], many features of QCD can be understood by studying the gauge theory $SU(N)$ in the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$. Moreover, he also proposed the idea that large- N QCD might be exactly reformulated as a string theory. Although this relation has never been made precise, the results obtained in lattice gauge theory and in addition in this thesis leave little doubt that there is a connection between these two theories. Furthermore, it appears that the large- N diagrammatic analysis leads to counting rules for the $1/N$ suppression terms which are the same as those for the string coupling constant in a string loop expansion [60]; this enhances the suspicion that there is a, still uncovered, relation between large- N and string theory. Most importantly, this belief became more convincing through Maldacena's conjecture [61] according to which the large- N Yang-Mills theory is dual with some string theory in the low-energy limit. Finally, the good agreement of results obtained in the large- N expansion with experiment tells us that this theory should be analysed in detail. Having all these facts in mind let us now move on to a brief discussion on large- N QCD, in order to see what is so special about large- N and how this affects our calculation.

One might think that letting $N \rightarrow \infty$ and consequently increasing the number of variables means higher complexity. That is what usually happens, but not in the case of QCD⁴ and several other field theories. The reason is simple; namely if a theory can be expressed as an expansion in powers of $1/N$ then it becomes simpler as N grows. This is basically due to the fact that the non-planar Feynman diagrams are suppressed by powers of $1/N$ in this limit.

Quantum chromodynamics is the theory of the strong interactions based on the gauge

⁴In fact, although the analytical approach becomes easier by increasing the number of colour, on the Lattice we face tremendous difficulties since the computational time increases as $\sim N^3$.

group $SU(3)$ with associated Lagrangian density:

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{2}\text{Tr}F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_F} \bar{\psi}_i(i\gamma^\mu D_\mu + m_i)\psi_i. \quad (1.13)$$

At very high energies, the running coupling g is small, so QCD can be studied perturbatively. This provides a way of obtaining analytic results in the study of the high-energy properties of the theory. However, the knowledge of the theory cannot be restricted in the high-energy regime, but it shall be extended in the low-energy regime where perturbation theory about g not longer occurs and some of the most interesting, and still unresolved, high energy problems, such as confinement, are located. That is where the confining flux tube “lives”. Here comes the Lattice with which we formulate QCD on a discretised space-time and use numerical simulations to calculate the average value of colour singlet operators that reflect to some observable. This leads to a numerical result and in no way can this replace the importance of a definite approximation able to give concrete understanding of the phenomenon. Since its proposal, large- N QCD has been the most concrete possibility for approaching an analytical intuition on the strongly coupled regime of QCD.

1.4.2 Diagrammatic Expansion.

The basic idea of the large- N limit is to introduce the inverse number of colours N as a new expansion parameter, rather than keep using $N = 3$ and expanding about g . Results for QCD can be obtained from the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit by setting $N = 3$ and are in good agreement with experiment. In order to develop a diagrammatical formulation of large- N QCD, it is necessary to take proper account of $1/N$ factors. To this purpose we should study the field propagators in order to demonstrate how colour flows. The gauge field propagator reads as:

$$\langle 0|TA_{\mu b}^a(x)A_{\nu d}^c(y)|0\rangle = (\delta_d^a\delta_b^c - \frac{1}{N}\delta_b^a\delta_d^c)D_{\mu\nu}(x-y) \approx \delta_d^a\delta_b^c D_{\mu\nu}(x-y), \quad (1.14)$$

where $D_{\mu\nu}$ is the propagator for a single gauge field. The term proportional to $1/N$ appears because the $SU(N)$ gauge field is traceless. As $N \rightarrow \infty$ this term can be dropped since we are only interested in the leading order in $1/N$. The removal of the $1/N$ term simplifies the colour flow in the gluon operator. According to the 't Hooft simplifying double-line representation the gluon propagator can be represented by a double colour index line, such as in Figure 1.3. In the same context, one can show that the fermion propagator can be

$$\langle 0|TA_{\mu b}^a(x)A_{\nu d}^c(y)|0\rangle \approx \overset{a}{\underset{b}{\parallel}} \overset{d}{\underset{c}{\parallel}}$$

Figure 1.3: 't Hooft double line notation for the propagator of the gauge field.

represented by a single line carrying one colour index.

According to this representation, one can slightly modify the Feynman diagrammatic analysis in such a way that each line would correspond to a color index rather than a virtual particle. Using this let us see two simple examples of a planar and a non-planar Feynman diagram. The Feynman diagram on the left panel of Figure 1.4, which corresponds to the one loop gluon vacuum polarisation, has two vertices which contribute a factor of g^2 in the analytic expression and a circulating colour loop that contributes a factor of N . This suggests that the expression will be proportional to $\sim N \cdot g^2$. In order to have a well-defined large- N limit for this diagram, Ng^2 must be kept fixed to a constant value as N grows.

Figure 1.4: Left Panel: Example of a planar diagram, Right Panel: Example of a non-planar diagram

This limit is the well known 't Hooft limit, defined by the quantity $\lambda = Ng^2$, which is called the 't Hooft coupling. On the right panel of Figure 1.4 the non-planar Feynman diagram has six vertices and just one circulating loop, which means that the expression will be proportional to $\sim N \cdot g^6 = \lambda/N^2 \xrightarrow{N \rightarrow \infty} 0$. This is a naive way to demonstrate that the non-planar Feynman diagrams vanish in the large- N limit. It is also straightforward to show that a Feynman diagram that contains virtual quark loops will get suppressed in the large- N limit. Therefore, at the 't Hooft limit only planar Feynman diagrams without quark loops survive.

An even more interesting diagrammatic structure of large- N QCD arises when we consider vacuum-to-vacuum Feynman diagrams. Applying the 't Hooft double line notation, the vacuum-to-vacuum Feynman diagrams correspond to polygons glued together to form 2-dimensional surfaces. In this picture, each closed colour loop corresponds to a polygon. So, we can imagine a surface made of glued-together polygons, where each propagator corresponds to an edge E of a polygon and each polygon to a face F . We thus derive the following formula for the N -dependence of a vacuum-to-vacuum graph:

$$N^{\{\text{Number of vertices}\} - \{\text{Number of propagators}\} + \{\text{Number of closed loops}\}} = N^{V-E+F} = N^\chi, \quad (1.15)$$

where χ is the Euler characteristic, a famous topological invariant. This can be computed using the fact that a two-dimensional oriented surface is equivalent to a sphere with some number of holes and handles. If h is the number of handles and b the number of holes, then the Euler characteristic⁵ for a connected orientable surface is given by:

$$\chi = 2 - 2h - b. \quad (1.16)$$

A quark can be represented by a single line with an arrow pointing the colour flow direction. Consequently the appearance of a quark loop corresponds to a boundary, while a non-planar gluon loop corresponds to a handle. From the Euler characteristic in Equation (1.16) it turns out that the maximum N power of a diagram is two, for the case of a pure gluonic planar graph with $h = 0$ and $b = 0$ which corresponds to a topology of a sphere. The leading connected vacuum-to-vacuum graphs including quarks are of order N . These are planar diagrams with only one quark loop ($b = 1$) that forms the boundary of the surface.

What we would like to know is how correlation functions of gluon and quark gauge invariant operators depend upon the number of colours N . This can be explored easily, using the topological results presented in the previous part and a source term in the lagrangian [62,

⁵For example, a torus can be thought of as a sphere with just one handle ($b = 0$, $h = 1$), a disk as a sphere with just one hole ($b = 1$, $h = 0$) and a cylinder as a sphere with two holes and no handles ($b = 2$, $h = 0$).

63, 64, 65]. What one finds is that a pure gluon j -point correlation function is of order:

$$\langle G_1 G_2 \dots G_j \rangle \propto N^{2-j} \quad (1.17)$$

where G denotes a pure-gluon operator such as the Polyakov loop $\text{Tr} P e^{-i \int_C A_\mu dz^\mu}$ considered in our calculations. Therefore, two-point correlator functions, as those we calculate on the lattice, have a well-defined large- N limit of order N^0 . The diagrams that contribute to these correlation functions are pure-gluonic. Taking into account the Euler character we realise that the leading order correction associated with vacuum-to-vacuum diagrams with one handle is suppressed by N^{-2} . Although irrelevant for the purposes of this thesis, in the case of fermionic operators, such as quarks bilinears, one finds that the j -point correlation function is of order $N^{1-r/2}$, while the leading order correction is suppressed by N^{-1} . Hence, if O is some configuration of pure gluon gauge invariant operators that form a secondary operator the expectation value of which has a smooth large- N limit ($\sim N^0$) such as a correlator of two Polyakov loops, its average factorises as:

$$\langle O \rangle_N = \langle O \rangle_{N=\infty} + \mathcal{O}(1/N^2). \quad (1.18)$$

This shows that even for the finite value of $N = 3$, the leading correction term has a relatively high level of suppression of $1/9$. This makes us believe that large- N limit behaviour of an observable, in our case the spectrum of the closed flux tube, can in fact be understood by studying $SU(N)$ gauge groups with N slightly larger than 3, or even $N = 3$ (It is in fact supported by bibliography [66] that $SU(\infty) \approx SU(3)$). This is also the only possible scenario, since lattice simulation's time limitations prevent us from performing calculations at $N \gg 3$; this is due to the fact that time consumption increases cubically with N .

Using the same diagrammatical arguments one can derive a number of important properties for the large- N limit. One of the most important such properties is the one called factorisation. According to this, the connected Green functions of arbitrary products of operators O_i are suppressed in the large- N limit and, therefore, only the disconnected Green functions survive:

$$\langle O_1 \dots O_n \rangle_N = \langle O_1 \rangle_{N=\infty} \dots \langle O_n \rangle_{N=\infty} + \mathcal{O}(1/N^2). \quad (1.19)$$

In addition, and just qualitatively, we note that using this property one can show that in the large- N limit there are no exotic states [63] (this is known as the Zweig's Rule) and colour singlets are totally stable with suppressed decay amplitudes [62].

1.5 General Expectations

Let us consider a flux tube of length $l = aL_{\parallel}$, in a representation of colour \mathcal{R} and which winds around the toroidally compactified longitudinal direction. Translations leave its energy unaltered. However, under transverse translations the state changes. This is due to the fact that the choice of a position for the closed flux tube breaks this symmetry spontaneously; therefore, we expect to obtain corresponding massless fluctuations in the excitation spectrum of the closed flux tube.

The $SU(N)$ field theory has only one scale $l_\sigma = 1/\sqrt{\sigma_f}$ and, therefore, the width of the flux tube should in general be on this scale. This suggests that on length scales much larger than l_σ , and for excitation energies much smaller than $1/l_\sigma$, the flux tube should effectively

behave as an infinitesimally thin string. Classically, the fluctuations of such a periodic string have wave length $\lambda_n = l/n$ and thus frequency $\omega_n = 2\pi n/l$. The corresponding oscillators are quantised, and the resulting excitations can be thought of as made up of phonons of energy ω_n and relative momenta $p_n = \pm\omega_n$ along the string. These phonons are the expected Goldstone bosons, which are massless and can have any momentum allowed by the periodicity. Excitations corresponding to multi-wound flux tubes are characterised by the winding number w and will, therefore, be described by phonons of relative momentum $\omega_n = 2\pi n/wl$. The quantisation of the closed bosonic string is the topic of discussion in the next chapter. At very large flux tube lengths all the excitation energies are expected to behave according to the linearly rising formula:

$$E_n \stackrel{l \rightarrow \infty}{\simeq} \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l, \forall n, \quad (1.20)$$

where $\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$ is the string tension of the closed flux tube in a representation \mathcal{R} . At finite values of the flux tube length l there will be a shift in the ground-state energy levels coming from the zero-point energies of the oscillators. In addition, for higher excited states there will be shifts coming from the phonon energy contributions. The energy expression which incorporates the linearly rising behaviour and the shifts can be given through a large- l expansion in powers of $1/\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l^2$. This picture has been constructed gradually in several works which deal with effective string theoretical models. A historic overview of such attempts has already been presented in Section 1.2.2, and a more detailed description is provided in Chapter 2. Hence, we expect that the closed flux tube spectrum includes string-like states in the sense of Equation (1.20), which will be compared to the known theoretical predictions.

All the theoretical approaches proposed in the quest of describing the flux tube have something in common: They only hope to treat very long flux tubes and, in effect, only eigenstates that are string-like. Apart from such stringy states, one might expect that the spectrum will also include massive states reflecting the non-trivial structure of the flux tube. It is common to think of the confining flux tube as being qualitatively similar to a Nielsen-Olesen vortex [67]. This kind of vortex will in general also have a pattern of excitations that reflects the effective theory driving its non-trivial structure. These excitations will typically be massive, leading to string eigenstates energy levels that will typically be much larger compared to the string-like excitations at large enough l such as:

$$E_M(l) \simeq E_0 + \mu \stackrel{l \rightarrow \infty}{>} E_n(l) \simeq \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} + \frac{4\pi}{l} \left(n - \frac{D-2}{24} \right). \quad (1.21)$$

In the lack of a theoretical framework of reference, one is forced to make a guess of what the value of μ shall be. A first guess might be that μ is something on the order of the lightest glueball mass. It could also be something on the order of the splitting of this state and its first excitation. Taking [43] as a reference, this would suggest that:

$$\mu \sim \{2 - 4\} \sqrt{\sigma_f}. \quad (1.22)$$

In any case, we should be aware of such states since these might appear in a lattice calculation of the closed flux tube spectrum. However, even if such massive stringy states are indeed included in the “natural” spectrum of the flux tube, there is a great possibility that in a lattice calculation they will never show up. In fact that is what is more likely to happen since nothing is known about their structure, providing with clues on how we can encode this extra information that these particular states carry within the lattice operators.

Chapter 2

Nambu-Goto String

2.1 Introduction

This chapter is dedicated to the most important developments in the effort of physicists to provide a connection between the closed flux tube and string theory, by presenting the effective string theoretical approaches to which our results are compared. The discussion has the following structure.

In the first part of this chapter an effort is made to carry out the quantisation of the closed bosonic string under the action of Nambu-Goto, in as much detail as the goals of this thesis require. More precisely the Polyakov action is used, firstly proposed in [68], rather than the original Nambu-Goto action [69], since it provides a much more convenient quantisation framework and it is classically equivalent to the latter. Following the light-cone quantisation the formula that expresses the mass of the string-soliton at any dimension D is derived; this is Equation (2.56). This approach leads to an effective string theoretical description of the closed flux tube which breaks Lorentz invariance.

In the next four parts two other approaches are briefly discussed, which aim to give effective string theoretical descriptions for the long-distance dynamics of a closed flux tube at dimensions lower than the critical. The first approach was proposed in 1991 by Polchinski and Strominger [15] and it is presented in 2.3. Polchinski and Strominger constructed a Poincaré invariant action and derived the energy formula for the closed flux tube up to $1/l$ with l being the length of the flux tube. The next step was the derivation of the energy formula in higher orders. This has been worked out in two independent calculations; one by Drummond [16, 17] and one by Dass and Matlock [18, 19]. Although the adopted methods in these two papers were not the same, they provide the same result, namely the expression of the closed flux tube energy up to terms of $1/l^3$ at any number of dimensions D . This is presented in Section 2.4.

The second approach came by Lüscher and Weisz in [21], where they have developed an effective string action applicable at any dimension D . Using this action they have derived a formula for the spectrum of a closed flux tube in $D = 2 + 1$ up to $1/l^3$. Their result is consistent with the expression of Drummond and Dass-Matlock at $D = 2 + 1$. Recently, a new result has been derived by Aharony and Karzbrun in [20]; they have improved the result of Lüscher and Weisz up to order $1/l^5$ for $D = 2 + 1$. Their result is presented in Section 2.6.

A more detailed review on these topics and relevant issues can be found in the work of Kuti [26], which can be used as a general review. A detailed derivation of the string-

soliton mass formula in the Nambu-Goto bosonic string framework can be found in the books [70, 71, 72, 73] and in the online lecture notes [74].

2.2 Nambu-Goto closed bosonic string theory

2.2.1 Preamble

The purpose of this section is to introduce the reader to the simplest string theory, called the bosonic string. The reason for including such a topic is the following: As shown in previous work [39, 40, 41, 42, 26, 52], Nambu-Goto closed string theory provides an adequate description for the confining closed flux tube that winds around the compact direction at large values of the string length. To be more precise, it also provides a good description for the flux tube even at string lengths comparable to the width of the tube. This can be viewed in our results. Although this theory is unrealistic and does not give any interesting results, which can be used phenomenologically, it provides a description for solitonic objects. The latter provides us with strong evidence that large- N QCD is somehow related to string theory.

It should also be mentioned that this fundamental string theory can only be consistently quantised in the critical dimension of $D = 26$. Nevertheless, string-like defects or solitons occur in a number of physical circumstances, such as the Nielsen-Olesen vortices of quantum field theories and QCD strings. Although, these objects exist in dimensions other than the critical, they can still be described by the string theoretical model, which has the number of dimensions as a free variable. Of course, the challenge of finding consistently quantised effective string theories able in describing such objects has been an interesting topic of research for many years. The only such attempt will be briefly presented in Section 2.3.

For the sake of completeness a general discussion on p -branes follows, focusing on strings or, in other words, $p = 1$ branes. A p -brane is a p -dimensional extended object propagating through space-time; a string can be regarded as a special case for $p = 1$ and it can also be called one-brane. Strings share some properties with higher-dimensional p -branes at the classical level. However, they are very special compared to the other higher dimensional objects in the sense that their two-dimensional world-volume quantum theories are renormalisable.

To start with, let us define the action S of the p -brane theory. The action is usually given as the $(p + 1)$ -dimensional volume swept by the propagation of the p -brane multiplied by a coefficient. This coefficient must have dimensionality of $[\text{length}]^{-(p+1)}$ in order to leave the action dimensionless. In the case of the QCD string this coefficient is the string tension with value $\sigma_f = (440 \pm 30 \text{MeV})^2$. Although the string tension of our interest is denoted as $\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$, in this chapter the string tension will be denoted by T ; this is what is commonly used in string theory textbooks. The generalised form of the p -brane action reads:

$$S_p = -T_p \int d\mu_p, \quad (2.1)$$

where T_p the p -brane tension and $d\mu_p$ the $(p+1)$ -dimensional infinitesimal volume element. If we now parametrise the p -brane volume coordinates as $\xi^0 = \tau$ being the time-like coordinate and ξ^i being the space-like coordinate, $d\mu_p$ is given by:

$$d\mu_p = \sqrt{-\det G_{\alpha\beta}} d^{p+1}\xi, \quad (2.2)$$

where the induced metric $G_{\alpha\beta}$ is given by

$$G_{\alpha\beta} = n_{\mu\nu}(x) \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \xi^\alpha} \frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial \xi^\beta}. \quad (2.3)$$

Here $n_{\mu\nu}$ with $\mu, \nu = 0, 1, \dots, D-1$, describes the metric tensor in a curved Riemannian geometry. In the following section we restrict ourselves to $p = 1$ and $n_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{\mu\nu}$ the Minkowski action and we try to develop the Nambu-Goto bosonic string, aiming to reveal the bosonic string spectrum for a multiply-wound closed string propagating in a D -dimensional flat Minkowski space-time.

2.2.2 The Bosonic String Action

The purpose of this section is to introduce the basic string actions that describe a bosonic string propagating in a D -dimensional flat Minkowski space-time M_D . Analogously to a point particle, a string will evolve in time sweeping out a 2-dimensional surface while moving through the space-time, which is usually referred to as the world sheet. One can consider open strings and closed strings. An open string corresponds to a worldsheet with boundaries and a closed string corresponds to a world sheet with no boundaries. The world sheet can be parametrised by the coordinates $\xi^0 = \tau$, which plays the role of the time-like coordinate, and $\xi^1 = \sigma$, which plays the role of the space-like coordinate. The boundary conditions of σ will determine whether the string is either closed or open; if σ is periodic then the string is closed. In this thesis we are interested in closed strings.

2.2.2.1 The Nambu-Goto Action

The coordinates of the space-time are denoted with $X^\mu(\sigma, \tau)$. As shown in the previous subsection, a string can be thought of as a special case of the more general p -brane action presented in Equation (2.1) with $p = 1$. This action is called the Nambu-Goto action, it has first appeared in [69] and it is given by:

$$S_{NG} = -T \int d^2\xi (-h)^{1/2} = -T \int d\sigma d\tau \sqrt{(\dot{X} \cdot X')^2 - \dot{X}^2 \cdot X'^2}, \quad (2.4)$$

where:

$$h_{ab} = n_{\mu\nu} \frac{\partial X^\mu}{\partial \xi^a} \frac{\partial X^\nu}{\partial \xi^b}, \quad h = \det(h^{ab}), \quad \dot{X}^\mu = \frac{\partial X^\mu}{\partial \tau}, \quad \text{and} \quad X'^\mu = \frac{\partial X^\mu}{\partial \sigma}. \quad (2.5)$$

The scalar product notation is defined by Einstein's convention. The Nambu-Goto action has a physical interpretation; it corresponds to the area of the world sheet swept by the propagation of the string. Although this is a nice physical interpretation, the presence of the square root in the expression makes the quantisation of the world sheet inconvenient and it would be more favourable to find an alternative action that could be manipulated more easily. To this purpose a classically equivalent action has been introduced; this is the topic of discussion in the next paragraph.

2.2.2.2 The Polyakov Action

The new action which gives rise to the same equations of motion as Nambu-Goto, is called the Polyakov¹ action or the string sigma model action. The difference here stems from the fact that an additional degree of freedom is introduced. This degree of freedom is the auxiliary world-sheet metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ which in principle should be independent of the space-time metric $\eta_{\mu\nu}$. The Polyakov action has the following form:

$$S_P = -\frac{T}{2} \int d^2\xi (-g)^{1/2} g^{\alpha\beta}(\sigma, \tau) \partial_\alpha X^\mu \partial_\beta X^\nu \eta_{\mu\nu}. \quad (2.6)$$

To avoid any confusion, the auxiliary metric is denoted as $g_{\alpha\beta}$, the induced metric as $h_{\alpha\beta}$ and the space-time metric as $\eta_{\mu\nu}$, with $\alpha, \beta = 1, 2$ and $\mu, \nu = 0, 1, 2, \dots, D-1$. It can be easily shown that at classical level the Polyakov action is equivalent to the Nambu-Goto action. The Polyakov action is invariant under the action of the following symmetries: D -dimensional Poincaré invariance, reparametrisation invariance (or diffeomorphism) and the two-dimensional Weyl invariance. These will eventually lead to the simplification of the theory and thus to a more convenient quantisation.

2.2.3 Boundary Conditions

In order to give a complete definition of the problem the boundary conditions need to be specified. A string can be either open or closed, a description being defined by the boundary behaviour of the coordinate σ . In bibliography, coordinate σ usually appears as being ranged $0 \leq \sigma \leq \pi$ or $0 \leq \sigma \leq 2\pi$ or $0 \leq \sigma \leq l$. In this thesis we decided to use the latter convention. The temporal coordinate ranges $-\infty < \tau < +\infty$. The variation of the action with respect to X^μ gives:

$$\delta S_P = T \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\tau \int_0^l d\sigma (-g)^{1/2} \delta X^\mu \nabla^2 X_\mu - T \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\tau (-g)^{1/2} \delta X^\mu \partial^\sigma X_\mu \Big|_{\sigma=0}^{\sigma=l}, \quad (2.7)$$

where $\nabla^2 = g^{\alpha\beta} \partial_\alpha \partial_\beta$. The first term in the expression above determines the equation of motion: $(-g)^{1/2} \nabla^2 X^\mu = 0$, while the second term is the boundary term and should vanish. The boundary conditions under which this term vanishes can be specified as:

$$\partial^\sigma X^\mu(\tau, 0) = \partial^\sigma X^\mu(\tau, l) = 0. \quad (2.8)$$

This condition can be satisfied by the closed string boundary condition:

$$X^\mu(\tau, \sigma) = X^\mu(\tau, \sigma + l). \quad (2.9)$$

The next step is to analyse the closed string spectrum.

2.2.4 Light-Cone quantisation of the Closed bosonic string

The main purpose of this chapter is not to present a mathematically perfect description of the bosonic string, but instead an easy way to obtain the spectrum of the closed bosonic

¹Although this action is called the Polyakov action, it has been originally proposed by D. Brink, P. Di Vecchia, P. Howe, S. Deser and B. Zumino [68]. It has been later used by Polyakov for the path-integral quantisation of the string.

string. Using light-cone quantisation the diffeomorphism \times Weyl redundancy can be eliminated. Although this gauge hides the covariance of the theory, it is the rapidest way to obtain the spectrum of the closed bosonic string and reveal the characteristic features of the bosonic theory. It is noted that this quantisation is mostly based on [74, 71, 73]

2.2.4.1 Light-Cone gauge fixing

Here we define the light-cone coordinates in space-time:

$$X^\pm = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(X^0 \pm X^1), \quad \text{with} \quad X^i; \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, D - 1. \quad (2.10)$$

According to this, the scalar product can be expressed as:

$$a^\mu b_\mu = -a^+ b^- + -a^- b^+ + a^i b^i \quad \text{with} \quad a_- = -a^+, \quad a_+ = -a^-, \quad a_i = a^i. \quad (2.11)$$

Let us now make a gauge choice in order to fix the redundancies of the Polyakov action. Since diffeomorphism \times Weyl corresponds to three local symmetries, more specifically two world sheet coordinates and the Weyl scaling, we can impose the following three conditions, one on the world sheet time coordinate and two on the metric:

$$X^+(\sigma, \tau) = \tau, \quad \partial_\sigma g_{\sigma\sigma} = 0, \quad \det(g_{\alpha\beta}) = -1. \quad (2.12)$$

Let us now see how one can reach this gauge. According to the reparametrisation invariance we can set the world-sheet temporal parameter τ at every point of the world-sheet being equal to the spacetime light-cone coordinate $X^+(\sigma, \tau) = \tau$ (light-cone condition). We choose a line on the world-sheet $\sigma_0(\tau)$ that intersects all the constant τ slices orthogonally. This is translated to $g_{\sigma\tau}(\sigma, \tau) = 0$ at $\sigma = \sigma_0(\tau)$. Under reparametrisations of σ where τ is kept fixed, $f(\sigma, \tau) = (-g)^{-1/2} g_{\sigma\sigma}(\sigma, \tau)$ transforms as $f' d\sigma' = f d\sigma$. We can therefore define the invariant length $f d\sigma = dl$. Now, for slices of constant τ we define a new coordinate $\sigma' = c(\tau) \int_{\sigma_0}^\sigma dl$ where $c(\tau)$ is a σ independent coefficient determined by requiring that the total length of the string l is fixed. This is defined as the invariant distance to the reference line along the slice. In this coordinisation, f is independent of σ and, therefore, $\partial_\sigma f(\sigma, \tau) = 0$. Finally we make a Weyl transformation to satisfy the condition $\det(g_{\alpha\beta}) = -1$. Since f is Weyl-invariant, we can still satisfy $\partial_\sigma f(\sigma, \tau) = 0$. Using the gauge condition $\det(g_{\alpha\beta}) = -1$ and the definition of f , we conclude to $\partial_\sigma g_{\sigma\sigma} = 0$.

By solving the gauge condition $\det(g_{\alpha\beta}) = -1$ for $g_{\tau\tau}(\tau, \sigma)$, it can be shown that the inverse metric is given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} g^{\tau\tau} & g^{\tau\sigma} \\ g^{\sigma\tau} & g^{\sigma\sigma} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -g_{\sigma\sigma}(\tau) & g_{\tau\sigma}(\sigma, \tau) \\ g_{\tau\sigma}(\sigma, \tau) & g_{\sigma\sigma}(\tau)^{-1} [1 - g_{\tau\sigma}(\sigma, \tau)^2] \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.13)$$

2.2.4.2 Gauge-fixed Polyakov action

Let us now analyse the Polyakov Lagrangian in light-cone coordinates. Following the definition of the action expressed in Equation (2.6) and having in mind that according to the

reparametrisation of τ , $\partial_\sigma X^+ = 0$, the Lagrangian reads:

$$L = -\frac{T}{2} \int_0^l d\sigma \quad [g^{\tau\tau} \partial_\tau X^i \partial_\tau X^i - 2g^{\tau\tau} \partial_\tau X^+ \partial_\tau X^- + 2g^{\sigma\tau} (\partial_\sigma X^i \partial_\tau X^i - \partial_\tau X^+ \partial_\sigma X^-) + g^{\sigma\sigma} \partial_\sigma X^i \partial_\sigma X^i]. \quad (2.14)$$

Using the metric which appears in Equation (2.13) and the fact that $\partial_\tau X^+ = 1$ the above Lagrangian can now be expressed as:

$$L = -\frac{T}{2} \int_0^l d\sigma \quad [g_{\sigma\sigma} (2\partial_\tau X^- - \partial_\tau X^i \partial_\tau X^i) - 2g_{\sigma\tau} (\partial_\sigma X^- - \partial_\sigma X^i \partial_\tau X^i) + g_{\sigma\sigma}^{-1} (1 - g_{\sigma\tau}^2) \partial_\sigma X^i \partial_\sigma X^i]. \quad (2.15)$$

Now it would be easier to separate $X^-(\sigma, \tau)$ in two pieces, namely $x^-(\tau)$ defined as:

$$x^-(\tau) = \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l d\sigma X^-(\tau, \sigma) \quad (2.16)$$

and $Y^-(\tau, \sigma)$ defined as:

$$Y^-(\tau, \sigma) = X^-(\tau, \sigma) - x^-(\tau). \quad (2.17)$$

The first new variable $x^-(\tau)$ is, according to its definition, the mean value of the coordinate $X^-(\tau, \sigma)$ at a specific value for τ , while the variable $Y^-(\tau, \sigma)$ expresses a spatial coordinate with mean value of zero. If we now substitute the above two definitions in the Lagrangian (2.15), we obtain:

$$L = -Tl g_{\sigma\sigma} \partial_\tau x^-(\tau) - \frac{T}{2} \int_0^l d\sigma \quad [-g_{\sigma\sigma} \partial_\tau X^i \partial_\tau X^i - 2g_{\sigma\tau} (\partial_\sigma Y^- - \partial_\sigma X^i \partial_\tau X^i) + g_{\sigma\sigma}^{-1} (1 - g_{\sigma\tau}^2) \partial_\sigma X^i \partial_\sigma X^i]. \quad (2.18)$$

In this form of the Lagrangian, the field Y^- does not couple to any terms with time derivatives, showing us that it has non-dynamical appearance. We could also say that it behaves as a Lagrange multiplier imposing that $\partial_\sigma g_{\sigma\tau} = 0$. Having this in mind and the fact that $g_{\sigma\tau}(\sigma_0, \tau) = 0$ we can show that $g_{\sigma\tau}(\sigma, \tau) = 0, \forall \sigma, \tau$. Using this result, the Lagrangian then becomes:

$$L = -Tl g_{\sigma\sigma} \partial_\tau x^-(\tau) + \frac{T}{2} \int_0^l d\sigma [g_{\sigma\sigma} \partial_\tau X^i \partial_\tau X^i - g_{\sigma\sigma}^{-1} \partial_\sigma X^i \partial_\sigma X^i]. \quad (2.19)$$

This shows that the problem of quantising the closed bosonic string reduces to the variables x^- , $g_{\sigma\sigma}$ and the fields X^i . In the next subsection we proceed to the equations of motion.

2.2.4.3 Equations of motion - Wave equation

In the previous subsection we ended up expressing the most reduced expression for the Lagrangian of the closed bosonic string. In order to conclude to this we have exploited the symmetries of the Polyakov action. Now we will show what the resulting equations of motion are and how one can obtain the wave equation for the closed bosonic string.

The momentum conjugate to $x^-(\tau)$ is given by:

$$p_- = -p^+ = \frac{\partial L}{\partial(\partial_\tau x^-)} = -Tl g_{\sigma\sigma}. \quad (2.20)$$

The expression for the momentum conjugate shows that $g_{\sigma\sigma}$ is a momentum variable rather than just an independent coordinate variable. We can also calculate the momentum density conjugate to $X^i(\tau, \sigma)$:

$$\Pi_i = \frac{\delta L}{\delta(\partial_\tau X^i)} = T g_{\sigma\sigma} \partial_\tau X^i = \frac{p^+}{l} \partial_\tau X^i. \quad (2.21)$$

The Hamiltonian is then given by:

$$\begin{aligned} H &= p_- \partial_\tau x^- - L + \int_0^l d\sigma \Pi_i(\sigma, \tau) \partial_\tau X^i(\sigma, \tau) \\ &= \frac{T}{2} \int_0^l d\sigma [g_{\sigma\sigma} \partial_\tau X^i \partial_\tau X^i - g_{\sigma\sigma}^{-1} \partial_\sigma X^i \partial_\sigma X^i] \\ &= \frac{Tl}{2p^+} \int_0^l d\sigma \left[\frac{1}{T} \Pi_i \Pi_i + T \partial_\sigma X^i \partial_\sigma X^i \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.22)$$

We can now use the Hamiltonian to derive the equations of motion:

$$\partial_\tau x^- = \frac{\partial H}{\partial p_-} = \frac{H}{p^+}, \quad \partial_\tau p^+ = \frac{\partial H}{\partial x^-} = 0, \quad (2.23)$$

$$\partial_\tau X^i = \frac{\delta H}{\delta \Pi_i} = \frac{c}{T} \Pi_i, \quad \partial_\tau \Pi_i = -\frac{\delta H}{\delta X^i} = cT \partial_\sigma^2 X^i. \quad (2.24)$$

The above equations imply that p^+ is a conserved quantity, x^- is linear in τ and they also lead to the wave equation:

$$\partial_\tau^2 X^i = c^2 \partial_\sigma^2 X^i. \quad (2.25)$$

This is the wave equation for the two-dimensional fields $X^i(\sigma, \tau)$ with velocity $c = Tl/p^+$. Since p^+ is a conserved quantity, the total length of the string does not vary.

2.2.4.4 Oscillator Expansions

The general solution of the wave equation can be given as a superposition of left- and right-moving waves:

$$X^i(\sigma, \tau) = X_L^i(\sigma + c\tau) + X_R^i(\sigma - c\tau). \quad (2.26)$$

For closed strings the imposed periodic boundary condition for $D-2$ transverse coordinates which derives from Equation (2.9) is $X^i(\sigma + l, \tau) = X^i(\sigma, \tau)$. To be more precise this is the boundary condition for a closed bosonic string that does not wind around a compactified dimension or alternatively a closed bosonic string with a winding number of zero. The case of a multiple-wound closed string will be presented in a later section. The most general

solution that satisfies the boundary condition is:

$$X_L^i(\sigma + c\tau) = \frac{x^i}{2} + \frac{p_i}{2p^+}(\tau + \frac{\sigma}{c}) + i\sqrt{\frac{1}{4\pi T}} \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z} - \{0\}} \frac{\alpha_n^i}{n} e^{-2\pi i n(\sigma + c\tau)/l}, \quad (2.27)$$

$$X_R^i(\sigma - c\tau) = \frac{x^i}{2} + \frac{p_i}{2p^+}(\tau - \frac{\sigma}{c}) + i\sqrt{\frac{1}{4\pi T}} \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z} - \{0\}} \frac{\bar{\alpha}_n^i}{n} e^{-2\pi i n(\sigma - c\tau)/l}, \quad (2.28)$$

where the coefficients x^i and p_i denote the center of the mass coordinate and the center of the mass momentum. The two independent sets of oscillators α_n^i and $\bar{\alpha}_n^i$ correspond to left- and right-moving oscillators respectively that travel along the closed string. As can be seen, the oscillators are described by the direction of the oscillation and the harmonic mode n . The quantised closed bosonic string can now be described in terms of the transverse oscillators, and the transverse and longitudinal centre of mass variables, a_n^i , \bar{a}_n^i , x^i , p^i and x^- and p^+ . These satisfy the following commutation relations:

$$[x_-, p^+] = -i, \quad [x^i, p^j] = i\delta^{ij}, \quad (2.29)$$

$$[\alpha_m^i, \alpha_n^j] = [\bar{\alpha}_m^i, \bar{\alpha}_n^j] = m\delta_{ij}\delta_{m,-n}, \quad [\alpha_m^i, \bar{\alpha}_n^j] = 0. \quad (2.30)$$

The raising operators for each set of transverse oscillators are labeled by negative harmonic modes i.e α_{-n}^i and $\bar{\alpha}_{-n}^i$ and the lowering operators by positive harmonic modes i.e α_n^i and $\bar{\alpha}_n^i$.

Let us now define the states of a single closed bosonic string. A state can be defined as $|N, \bar{N}, k\rangle$ with $k = (k^+, k^i)$ the momentum vector. N and \bar{N} are the number operators and they present the total contribution of the oscillating part of the Lagrangian once acting on a particular state. They are defined as:

$$N = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_{-n}^i \alpha_n^i \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{N} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \bar{\alpha}_{-n}^i \bar{\alpha}_n^i. \quad (2.31)$$

The action of the operators α_n^i , $\bar{\alpha}_n^i$, p^i and p^+ , is defined by:

$$p^+ |N, \bar{N}, k\rangle = k^+ |N, \bar{N}, k\rangle, \quad (2.32)$$

$$p^i |N, \bar{N}, k\rangle = k^i |N, \bar{N}, k\rangle, \quad (2.33)$$

$$\alpha_n^i |0, 0, k\rangle = \bar{\alpha}_n^i |0, 0, k\rangle = 0. \quad (2.34)$$

A general state can be built by acting on $|0, 0, k\rangle$ with the raising operators.

The Hilbert \mathcal{H}_q space of a single q -string state is defined by the vacuum $|N = 0, \bar{N} = 0, k\rangle$ with $k = (k^+, k^i)$. Here it should be mentioned that $|0, 0, k\rangle$ does not denote the zero-string vacuum state, but the ground state of a single string with momentum k . In the same context, the raising and lowering operators do not create or annihilate strings, but appear to act on states that belong to the isolated space of states of a single string. A more detailed presentation on the algebra of the closed bosonic string theory can be found in [70, 71, 72, 70, 73].

By inserting the mode expansions presented in Equations (2.27) and (2.28) into the

Hamiltonian of Equation (2.22) we obtain:

$$H = \frac{2T\pi}{p^+} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [\alpha_{-n}^i \alpha_n^i + \bar{\alpha}_{-n}^i \bar{\alpha}_n^i] + \frac{2T\pi}{p^+} [A_0 + \bar{A}_0] + \frac{p_i p_i}{2p^+}. \quad (2.35)$$

The raising and lowering operators have been normal-ordered with the lowering operators on the right and the raising operators on the left and A_0, \bar{A}_0 the zero point energies which derive from the commutators.

2.2.4.5 String Mass Spectrum

Let us now construct the “physical spectrum” of the closed bosonic string. The spectrum of the closed bosonic string consists of all possible states that can be obtained from the action of all possible combinations of the left- and right-moving raising oscillators onto the vacuum. These states correspond to different particles or spin states. The mass of a string state can be calculated by imposing the mass-shell condition. The closed bosonic string mass-shell condition in the light-cone gauge reads:

$$M^2 = -p_\mu p^\mu = 2p^+ p^- - p_i p_i = 2p^+ H - p^i p^i, \quad (2.36)$$

where it can be easily shown [71] that p^- corresponds to the Hamiltonian, $p^- = H$. Therefore:

$$M^2 = 4\pi T \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [\alpha_{-n}^i \alpha_n^i + \bar{\alpha}_{-n}^i \bar{\alpha}_n^i] + A_0 + \bar{A}_0 \right] = 4\pi T [N + \bar{N} + A_0 + \bar{A}_0]. \quad (2.37)$$

The resulting Mass expression shows that the mass of the string states increases with the number of oscillators. Due to a remaining gauge freedom, namely the invariance under σ -translations (the line σ_0 can be chosen anywhere along the string), there is more work to be done. This restriction requires the net momentum along the σ direction to vanish. The operator that generates the σ -translations and expresses the net momentum along σ is given by:

$$P = - \int_0^l d\sigma \Pi^i \partial_\sigma X^i = -\frac{2\pi}{l} (N - \bar{N}). \quad (2.38)$$

Since the above expression must vanish, the result is that the overall momentum of left-moving oscillators should be exactly the same as the overall momentum carried by the right-moving oscillators. This forms the level matching constraint for a closed bosonic string with zero winding number:

$$N = \bar{N}. \quad (2.39)$$

The zero-point energies can be calculated properly using the Virasoro algebra. However, since the adopted method hides the covariance of the theory, this is going far beyond our aims and we avoid such a description² for the calculation of the zero-point energies. We

²We will try to sketch an alternative derivation of A_0 and \bar{A}_0 starting from the fact that:

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{D-2} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \alpha_{-n}^i \alpha_n^i = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{D-2} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} : \alpha_{-n}^i \alpha_n^i : + \frac{1}{2} (D-2) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n. \quad (2.40)$$

Figure 2.1: Pictorialisation representing a $w = 1$, a $w = -1$ and a $w = 0$ bosonic string states, in a space-time with one compact dimension.

note that the zero point energies are given by:

$$A_0 = \bar{A}_0 = -\frac{D-2}{24}. \quad (2.41)$$

A detailed description can be found in the books [70, 71, 73, 72]. An easy way [73, 74] to see that the critical number of dimensions should be equal to $D = 26$ is to consider the first zero-momentum excitation of the string $\alpha_{-1}^i \bar{\alpha}_{-1}^j |0\rangle$. This corresponds to the tensor product of two particles transforming under $SO(D-2)$. The symmetric part of this state should have corresponded to the graviton and, therefore, to a massless spin-two particle while the trace term to a massless scalar the dilaton. It should be mentioned that in a Lorentz invariant theory this state should belong to a representation of the $SO(D-2)$ little group of the Lorentz group and, therefore, should be massless; this is a general rule. The squared mass that rises from Equation (2.37) $M^2 = 4\pi T(2 - \frac{D-2}{12})$ vanishes at $D = 26$. Hence, if $D < 26$ then Lorentz invariance breaks.

2.2.4.6 Toroidal Compactification

In this subsection we discuss the physics of a closed bosonic string compactified on a circle. Generally, toroidal compactification is a procedure that forms the internal space in the attempt of physicists to obtain four-dimensional physics in the low energy regime³ out of a higher dimensional theory with $D > 4$. The curved background, in which a theory is considered, is denoted by $M_d \times X_{D-d}$ with M_d the d -dimensional Minkowski space-time and X_{D-d} the $(D-d)$ -dimensional compact manifold. The toroidal compactification first appeared in field theory in the Kaluza-Klein mechanism aiming to generate gauge vector bosons from a higher dimensional metric.

Until now we have been analysing the physics of a string propagating within an M_D

This results by normal ordering $\alpha_{-n}^i \alpha_n^i$ using the commutation relations of Equations (2.30). The right-hand side of the expression above has an obvious divergency and, therefore, needs to be regularised. This divergent term corresponds to the zero point energy, $A_0 = \bar{A}_0 = (D-2)/2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n$. The regularisation can be achieved [74] by taking the limit $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ of the function $\zeta(\epsilon) = 1/2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n e^{-n\epsilon}$. It can be easily shown that $\zeta(\epsilon) = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{d\epsilon} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n\epsilon} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{d\epsilon} \frac{1}{1-e^{-\epsilon}} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{d\epsilon} [\frac{1}{\epsilon} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{12}\epsilon + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)] = \frac{1}{2\epsilon^2} - \frac{1}{24} + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon)$. By dropping the infinite part and sending $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ we obtain that the zero point energy is equal to $A_0 = \bar{A}_0 = -\frac{D-2}{24}$.

³If the size of the compactified dimensions is L_c and the energy $E \ll 1/L_c$ then the physics can be described in four dimensions.

space-time. The physics we are about to study is slightly different since the space-time metric of the Polyakov action is not M_D anymore but $M_{D-1} \times \mathbf{S}^1$. The Polyakov action remains the same as in Equation (2.6) and the difference only arises at the level of the boundary conditions that one has to impose. The Hamiltonian is still the same with the only difference that additional terms will now appear. These terms will be introduced by the compactification of a spatial coordinate (see Figure 2.1). The Hamiltonian can be defined as:

$$H = \frac{lT}{2p^+} \int_0^l d\sigma \left[\frac{1}{T} \Pi_i \Pi_i + T \partial_\sigma X^i \partial_\sigma X^i \right]. \quad (2.42)$$

In order to obtain the additional terms that appear in the movers and consequently in the Hamiltonian it would be useful to specify the boundary conditions. The boundary conditions remain the same as before with an exception on the boundary condition associated with the compactified dimension X^{D-1} . Consequently, for X^i with $i = 2, \dots, D-2$ we impose:

$$X^i(\sigma + l, \tau) = X^i(\sigma, \tau) \quad i = 2, \dots, D-2 \quad (2.43)$$

as before. Diversely, for X^{D-1} we impose:

$$X^{D-1}(\sigma + l, \tau) = X^{D-1}(\sigma, \tau) + 2\pi R w, \quad w \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad (2.44)$$

where w is the winding number that indicates how many times the closed string winds around the compactified dimension. The fact that we impose periodic boundary conditions, such as (2.44), is responsible for two important effects, which make this case different from the non compact one analysed in the previous section. The first effect arises from the operator that is responsible for translations, $e^{2\pi i R p_{D-1}}$ which translates strings along the periodic direction. This operator must leave the string states invariant in order to be single-valued and, therefore, the center-of-the mass momentum, that we will be referring to as longitudinal momentum, must be quantised as:

$$p_{D-1} = \frac{Q}{R}, \quad \text{with} \quad Q \in \mathbb{Z}. \quad (2.45)$$

The momentum integer Q is called the Kaluza-Klein excitation number. The second effect, which has already been mentioned in the definition of the periodic boundary conditions (2.43) and (2.44), is that a closed string can wind several times around the compact direction. This effect is mathematically introduced with the winding number w . The winding number is a conserved quantity in string interactions and, therefore, can never change. States with non-zero winding number are topological solitons (see Figure 2.1). As will be shown in this thesis, the solitonic masses can model well the masses of torelons, topological solitons that appear in a formulation of QCD with imposed periodic boundary conditions along the direction of the flux in dimensions lower than $D < 26$, more precisely for $D = 3$.

The mode expansion for these boundary conditions will be given by Equations (2.26), (2.27)

and (2.28) for X^i with $i = 2, \dots, D - 2$ and by:

$$X^{D-1}(\sigma, \tau) = x^{D-1} + \frac{p_{D-1}}{p^+} \tau + \frac{2\pi R w}{l} \sigma + i \sqrt{\frac{1}{4\pi T}} \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z} - \{0\}} \left[\frac{\alpha_n^i}{n} e^{-2\pi i n(\sigma + c\tau)/l} + \frac{\bar{\alpha}_n^i}{n} e^{-2\pi i n(\sigma - c\tau)/l} \right], \quad (2.46)$$

for X^{D-1} . This can be expressed in terms of the left- and right-movers as:

$$X^{D-1}(\sigma, \tau) = X_L^{D-1}(\sigma + c\tau) + X_R^{D-1}(\sigma - c\tau), \quad (2.47)$$

with

$$X_L^{D-1}(\sigma + c\tau) = \frac{x^{D-1}}{2} + \frac{p_L}{2p^+} \left(\tau + \frac{\sigma}{c} \right) + i \sqrt{\frac{1}{4\pi T}} \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z} - \{0\}} \left[\frac{\alpha_n^i}{n} e^{-2\pi i n(\sigma + c\tau)/l} \right] \quad (2.48)$$

$$X_R^{D-1}(\sigma - c\tau) = \frac{x^{D-1}}{2} + \frac{p_R}{2p^+} \left(\tau - \frac{\sigma}{c} \right) + i \sqrt{\frac{1}{4\pi T}} \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z} - \{0\}} \left[\frac{\bar{\alpha}_n^i}{n} e^{-2\pi i n(\sigma - c\tau)/l} \right] \quad (2.49)$$

where p_L and p_R are given by:

$$p_L = \frac{Q}{R} + 2\pi T w R \quad \text{and} \quad p_R = \frac{Q}{R} - 2\pi T w R. \quad (2.50)$$

These new momentum variables are called left- and right-moving momenta, and they form the parts of the movers that contain all the new physics inserted by the compactification. Now we are equipped with all one needs to proceed to the spectrum of the compact case.

Let us now see how the Hamiltonian changes compared to the non-compact case. According to Equations (2.46) and (2.42) the additional term is inserted through the winding terms $\partial_\sigma X^{25}$. This will occur in the following expression:

$$H_w = H_{w=0} + \frac{lT}{2p^+} \int_0^l d\sigma T \left(\frac{2\pi R w}{l} \right)^2 \quad (2.51)$$

$$= \sum_{i=2}^{D-2} \frac{p_i p_i}{2p^+} + \frac{2\pi T}{p^+} \left(N + \bar{N} - 2 \left(\frac{D-2}{24} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{2p^+} \left(\frac{Q}{R} \right)^2 + \frac{2\pi^2 T^2 R^2 w^2}{p^+}. \quad (2.52)$$

Let us now obtain the level matching constraint. Again we calculate the net momentum along the σ direction:

$$P_w = - \int_0^l d\sigma \Pi_i \partial_\sigma X^i = - \frac{2\pi}{l} (N - \bar{N} + Qw). \quad (2.53)$$

If we now force the expression above to vanish we will be left with the level-matching constrain:

$$N - \bar{N} = -wQ. \quad (2.54)$$

This result is consistent with the non-compact case where $w = 0$, appearing in Equation (2.39). The mass formula for a string with one dimension compactified on a torus can

be interpreted from a $(D-1)$ -dimensional viewpoint according to which one regards each of the Kaluza-Klein excitations labeled by Q as particles. Each state, therefore, corresponds to a “particle” in a $D-1$ spacetime with mass given by:

$$M_{D-1}^2 = 2p^+H - \sum_{i=2}^{D-2} p_i p_i = \frac{Q^2}{R^2} + 4\pi^2 T^2 w^2 R^2 + 4\pi T \left(N + \bar{N} - 2 \left(\frac{D-2}{24} \right) \right). \quad (2.55)$$

This is the formula that gives the squared mass of the closed compact string. Compared to Equation (2.37), which corresponds to the non-compact case, Equation (2.55) contains two additional terms; the factor $\frac{Q^2}{R^2}$, which reflects the contribution from the quantised momenta along the compact dimension, and the term $4\pi^2 T^2 w^2 R^2$, which can be defined as the energy needed for wrapping the string around a circle with radius R , w times.

Although at first sight this expression looks unfamiliar, by imposing the following substitutions it could take a more recognisable form! If we substitute: $T \rightarrow \sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$, $R \rightarrow l/2\pi$ and $M^2 \rightarrow E^2$ where $\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$ denotes the string tension at representation \mathcal{R} and l denotes the length of the string around the wrapped dimension, Equation (2.55) becomes:

$$E^2 = (w\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}l)^2 + 8\pi\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} \left(\frac{N + \bar{N}}{2} - \frac{D-2}{24} \right) + \left(\frac{2\pi Q}{l} \right)^2. \quad (2.56)$$

As we have already argued, this theory is quantum mechanically consistent only at the critical dimension of $D = 26$ due to the loss of the Poincaré invariance in lower dimensions. However, Olesen in [14] showed that at large distances l this anomaly is asymptotically disappearing, demonstrating that this string model can still be used as an effective string theory in order to model the large-distance behaviour of the confining QCD string; in this particular case, of the confining closed QCD string. In addition, this theory suffers with the appearance of tachyonic modes. Although Olesen complementarily showed that this problem is also suppressed in large string lengths, we note that for physical reasons this is not a problem at all for a string like description for the torelon due to the following reason. According to Equation (2.56) the string becomes tachyonic only below the critical length $l_{\text{tach}} = \sqrt{\pi(D-2)/3\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}w^2}$ for $N = \bar{N} = 0$. The deconfining length l_c below which the flux tube dissolves appears to be slightly larger than l_{tach} , thus, “protecting” the effective string description from a tachyonic behaviour. We note that for a single-wound flux tube in $D = 3$ and the fundamental representation of $SU(N)$, $l_c \simeq 1.10\sqrt{\sigma_f}$ while $l_{\text{tach}} \simeq 1.05\sqrt{\sigma_f}$.

Nevertheless, the loss of Lorentz invariance led physicists to invest much effort in search of a Poincaré invariant effective string theory for the long distance dynamics of QCD string; this is a question that still remains unresolved.

2.3 The Polchinski-Strominger approach

It remains an open question the discovery of consistently quantised effective string theory without any restriction on the dimensionality, able to describe the long distance dynamics of the QCD string. The first to show how to do this were Polchinski and Strominger in [15]. They have shown that one could construct a string theory with a manifest D -dimensional Poincaré symmetry. This has been achieved by overcoming the traditional restriction related to the critical dimension $D = 26$ by inserting a term in the action which fixes the central charge to $c = 26$ when expanding around the long-string vacuum.

In this section we briefly discuss the method that Polchinski and Strominger followed

in order to derive a Poincaré invariant effective string theory without going into much detail. Integrating out the heavy degrees of freedom leads to an effective field theory of the transverse oscillations defined by the path integral:

$$\int \mathcal{D}X e^{iS}. \quad (2.57)$$

The authors worked with the Minkowski light-cone world-sheet coordinates $\tau^\pm = \tau \pm \sigma$. The collective string coordinates of the D unconstrained X^μ fields of the underlying theory (originally for the Abelian Higgs model) lead to the Gaussian action:

$$S_0 = T \int d\tau^+ d\tau^- \partial_+ X^\mu \partial_- X_\mu + \text{determinant}. \quad (2.58)$$

This can also be obtained by imposing the conformal gauge in the world sheet within the Polyakov action (2.6) framework. The measure in Equation (2.57) can be derived by the physical motion of the underlying gauge fields which appear in the original Nielsen-Olesen theory, and it should therefore be constructed by physical objects like the induced metric:

$$h_{ab} = \partial_a X^\mu \partial_b X_\mu. \quad (2.59)$$

The determinants of Equation (2.58) have been found by Polyakov in [75] and the only difference is that now they would be built out of the induced metric rather than the intrinsic metric e^ϕ . In terms of Polyakov's intrinsic metric e^ϕ , the determinant is written as:

$$S_L = \frac{26-D}{48\pi} \int d\tau^+ d\tau^- \partial_+ \phi \partial_- \phi. \quad (2.60)$$

Substituting the induced conformal gauge metric h_{+-} for e^ϕ i.e. $e^\phi \rightarrow h_{+-}$ and having also in mind that according to the equations of motion $\partial_+ \partial_- X^\mu = 0$, they obtained:

$$S'_L = \frac{26-D}{48\pi} \int d\tau^+ d\tau^- \frac{\partial_+^2 X^\mu \partial_- X_\mu \partial_+ X^\nu \partial_-^2 X_\nu}{(\partial_+ X^\lambda \partial_- X_\lambda)^2}. \quad (2.61)$$

Therefore the full effective string action is given by:

$$S_{PS} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int d\tau^+ d\tau^- \left[4\pi T \partial_+ X^\mu \partial_- X_\mu + \beta \frac{\partial_+^2 X^\mu \partial_- X_\mu \partial_+ X^\nu \partial_-^2 X_\nu}{(\partial_+ X^\lambda \partial_- X_\lambda)^2} \right]. \quad (2.62)$$

with $\beta = \frac{26-D}{12\pi}$. The appearance of non-polynomial terms in the action is not a problem, since they are well-defined in an expansion around the long-string vacuum (the first derivatives $\partial_+ X$ and $\partial_- X$ are never small).

This action is invariant under the modified conformal transformation:

$$\delta_- X^\mu = \epsilon^-(\tau^-) \partial_- X^\mu - \frac{\beta}{8\pi T} \partial_-^2 \epsilon^-(\tau^-) \frac{\partial_+ X^\mu}{\partial_+ X^\lambda \partial_- X_\lambda} + (+ \leftrightarrow -). \quad (2.63)$$

The authors considered a string wrapped around a compact spatial dimension, compactified on a circle of radius R as this is defined by the boundary conditions (2.43) and (2.44). This is clear evidence that their work could lead to the long distance description of the torelons and thus their result could be compared to ours. In the sector with unit winding number,

they expanded around the classical ground state given by:

$$X_{\text{cl}}^\mu = e_+^\mu R\tau^+ + e_-^\mu R\tau^-, \quad (2.64)$$

where $e_+^2 = e_-^2 = 0$ and $e_+ \cdot e_- = -\frac{1}{2}$. The form of Equation (2.64) tells us that the first derivatives of the variable X are of order R .

By calculating the energy-momentum tensor and expanding the Lagrangian around the long-string vacuum in powers of R^{-1} they extracted an expression for the Virasoro generators up to $\mathcal{O}(R^{-1})$. This led the authors to derive the ground state of the closed string up to $\mathcal{O}(R^{-1})$ and exclude terms of order $\mathcal{O}(R^{-2})$:

$$M = (-p^2)^{1/2} = 2\pi TR - \frac{D-2}{12R} + \mathcal{O}(R^{-3}). \quad (2.65)$$

Using once more the substitutions $M \rightarrow E$, $T \rightarrow \sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$ and $R \rightarrow l/2\pi$ the ground state takes the following form:

$$E(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}}l - \frac{\pi(D-2)}{6l} + \mathcal{O}(l^{-3}). \quad (2.66)$$

The first term is the linearly rising term and corresponds to the energy of a string of length l . The second universal term is the Casimir energy and corresponds to a contribution of $-1/12l$ per physical degree of transverse oscillations; it is the direct analog to the Lüscher term for the open string. We will be therefore referring to this term as the Lüscher term for the torelon. If we now expand the square root of the exact Nambu-Goto result presented in Equation (2.56) for the ground state, zero longitudinal momentum and unit winding number:

$$E(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}}l \sqrt{1 - \frac{\pi}{3\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}l^2}(D-2)} \quad (2.67)$$

in terms of $1/l^2$, we obtain that the two first terms are nothing else but the result (2.66). Equation (2.67) is the equivalent to the Arvis potential for the closed string. The result of Polshinski and Strominger can be generalised for the full spectrum of a torelon with zero longitudinal momentum:

$$E(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}}l + \frac{4\pi}{l} \left(n - \frac{D-2}{24} \right) + \mathcal{O}(l^{-3}), \quad (2.68)$$

with $n = (N + \bar{N})/2$. This can also be obtained by expanding the square root of Nambu-Goto for zero longitudinal momentum and unit winding number up to leading-order (L.O) in terms of $1/l^2$.

2.4 Drummond and Dass-Matlock corrections

The question of whether there are subleading universal terms in the R^{-1} expansion of the torelon energy spectrum, which would add to the first result of Polchinski and Strominger that appears in Equation (2.65) had been unresolved for around fifteen years. It was Drummond in 2004 [16] the first to calculate the subleading term in the spectrum that derives from the D -dimensional Poincaré invariant action (2.62). More specifically, Drum-

mond showed that Polchinski and Strominger action predicts a universal spectrum up to terms proportional to R^{-3} by extracting, and making use of, the Virasoro generators up to $\mathcal{O}(R^{-2})$. The conformal invariance did not lead to any free parameters in the spectrum and, therefore, all the terms up to R^{-3} were considered as universal. The ground state of the torelon presented in the Drummond paper is given by the formula:

$$M = (-p^2)^{1/2} = 2\pi T R - \frac{D-2}{12R} - \frac{1}{4\pi T R^3} \left(\frac{D-2}{12} \right)^2 + \mathcal{O}(R^{-4}). \quad (2.69)$$

Following again the substitutions $M \rightarrow E$, $T \rightarrow \sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$ and $R \rightarrow l/2\pi$, the above formula takes the form:

$$E(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l - \frac{\pi(D-2)}{6l} - \frac{2\pi^2}{\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l^3} \left(\frac{D-2}{12} \right)^2 + \mathcal{O}(l^{-4}). \quad (2.70)$$

The result of Drummond can be generalised to the excited states:

$$E(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l + \frac{4\pi}{l} \left(n - \frac{D-2}{24} \right) - \frac{8\pi^2}{\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l^3} \left(n - \frac{D-2}{24} \right)^2 + \mathcal{O}(l^{-4}). \quad (2.71)$$

This is the same spectrum as that given by the Nambu-Goto expanded to next-to-leading-order (N.L.O) in terms of $1/l^2$.

The same results were obtained by Dass and Matlock in [18, 19] two years later. The authors followed a diverse analysis, which does not include any field redefinitions in contrast to Drummond's approach. Nevertheless, both approaches led to the same result.

2.5 Lüscher-Weisz approach

The third approach to an analytic description for the QCD string has been proposed by Lüscher and Weisz in [21]. The authors developed a string effective action for the open string (quark-antiquark pair) that leads to an expansion of the excitations in powers of $1/l$ with weights expressed by unknown couplings which in principle describe the string self-interactions. These couplings have been constrained by the use of an open-closed string duality (dual interpretation of the Polyakov correlation function). Using this duality they have shown that for any number of dimensions D the corrections of order $1/l^2$ must vanish, and that in $D = 2 + 1$ the $1/l^3$ term has a universal coefficient while in $D = 3 + 1$ has a coefficient which depends on an adjustable coupling only. Using this duality they also obtained analogous results for the closed flux tube. The adopted method is being briefly presented in the next few paragraphs.

The authors considered the open string with Dirichlet boundary conditions. The fluctuations of the string are parametrised by the vector $X^i(\tau, \sigma)$; $i = 2, \dots, D-1$ with orthogonal world-sheet coordinates $X^0 = \tau$ and $X^1 = \sigma$. The fluctuations correspond to the transverse displacements of the string with $D-2$ field components in the directions that are orthogonal to the principal string axis. For reasons of simplicity the authors chose the metrics in space-time and world-sheet to be Euclidean. The open string has the boundaries $0 \leq X^1 \leq R_s$ and $0 \leq X^0 \leq R_t$. The authors imposed periodic boundary conditions along the time direction with periodicity of R_t . The vector $X^i(\tau, \sigma)$ should satisfy:

$$X^i|_{\sigma=0} = X^i|_{\sigma=R_s} = 0. \quad (2.72)$$

The action of Lüscher and Weisz S_{LW} is expressed as a series:

$$S_{LW} = TR_s R_t + \mu R_t + S_{LW0} + S_{LW1} + S_{LW2} + S_{LW3} + \int \mathcal{O}(\partial^6 X^{4,6}), \quad (2.73)$$

where T denotes the string tension, μ is just an arbitrary mass parameter and S_{LW1} , S_{LW2} , S_{LW3} , ..., up to fourth-derivative are self-interaction terms of increasing dimensions. The Gaussian free part of the action is given by:

$$S_{LW0} = \frac{1}{2} \int d\tau d\sigma (\partial_\alpha X^i \partial_\alpha X^i). \quad (2.74)$$

The area term of Equation (2.73) and the Gaussian part of the action S_{LW0} could also be obtained by expanding the square root of the Nambu-Goto action in the static gauge ($X^0 = \tau$, $X^1 = \sigma$) in the non-relativistic limit. This results in the loss of the full Poincaré invariance. The resulting action shall be invariant under Poincaré transformations in the (τ, σ) plane only. The first interaction term of the action should have a coupling of dimension [length]. Therefore by inspection, the only possible interaction is the boundary term:

$$S_{LW1} = b \int d\tau \{ (\partial_1 X^i \partial_1 X^i)|_{\sigma=0} + (\partial_1 X^i \partial_1 X^i)|_{\sigma=R_s} \}. \quad (2.75)$$

At the next order, the couplings have dimension of [length]². Thus the two possible interaction terms appearing in the action are:

$$S_{LW2} = c_2 \int d\tau d\sigma (\partial_\alpha X^i \partial_\alpha X^i) (\partial_\beta X^j \partial_\beta X^j) \quad (2.76)$$

and

$$S_{LW3} = c_3 \int d\tau d\sigma (\partial_\alpha X^i \partial_\beta X^i) (\partial_\alpha X^j \partial_\beta X^j). \quad (2.77)$$

In the effective string theory, the partition function can be expanded in powers of the couplings b , c_2 , c_3 , To leading⁴ order the partition function can be represented as:

$$\mathcal{Z}_0(R_s, R_t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} w_n e^{-E_n^0(R_s) R_t}, \quad (2.78)$$

with w_n being positive weights and E_n^0 open string energy levels given by the formula:

$$E_n^0(R_s) = TR_s + \mu + \frac{\pi}{R_s} \left(-\frac{1}{24}(D-2) + n \right). \quad (2.79)$$

By setting $\mu = 0$, the above energy expression can be obtained by expanding the square root which appears in the Arvis Potential of Equation (1.3) up to leading order in $1/R_s$ ($R_s \rightarrow l$). This also matches the first result of Lüscher which has been reported in [11] and is known as the Lüscher term.

The partition function is proportional⁵ to the Polyakov loop correlator $\langle P(x)^* P(y) \rangle$

⁴The exact expansion to leading order is being known for a long time in [76], expressed in terms of the Dedekind function.

⁵The full string partition function is expected to match the Polyakov loop only at a finite order in the

where the two Polyakov loops are located at spatial distance $r = |y - x|$ apart and they run along the Euclidean time annulus. In this picture the field-theoretical interpretation of the Polyakov loop correlator is the partition function of the gauge theory in the presence of a static quark-antiquark potential.

However, we could take the compact dimension, along which the Polyakov line runs, to be space-like. In this case the interpretation of the Polyakov correlator would be that it creates or annihilates a closed flux tube which winds around the compact dimension. The authors showed that the Polyakov correlator can be expanded as a series of Bessel functions and as a function of the energies of the closed string, thus constraining the analytic form of the Polyakov loop correlator. Therefore, the problem of determining the interaction couplings reduces to the question of whether the partition function \mathcal{Z} of the effective string theory can be expanded as a series of Bessel functions at large values of R_t and R_s :

$$\mathcal{Z}(R_s, R_t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |v_n|^2 2R_s \left(\frac{\tilde{E}_n(R_t)}{2\pi R_s} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}(D-1)} K_{\frac{1}{2}(D-3)} \left(\tilde{E}_n(R_t) R_s \right), \quad (2.80)$$

where $\tilde{E}_n(R_t)$ and coefficients u_n are the energies and transition matrix elements of the possible intermediate closed flux tube states respectively.

At leading order the authors showed that the open-closed string duality holds. At this order using the modular transformation property of the Dedekind function one could show that the partition function can be written as:

$$\mathcal{Z}_0(R_s, R_t) = e^{-\mu R_t} \left(\frac{R_t}{2R_s} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}(d-2)} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} w_n e^{-\tilde{E}_n^0 R_s}, \quad (2.81)$$

with the closed-string energy level given by:

$$\tilde{E}_n^0(R_t) = T R_t + \frac{4\pi}{R_t} \left(n - \frac{1}{24}(D-2) \right). \quad (2.82)$$

This agrees with the result of Polchinski and Strominger (2.68) by substituting $R_t \rightarrow l$.

At the next order order, by computing the partition function:

$$\mathcal{Z} = \mathcal{Z}_0(1 - \langle S_{LW1} \rangle_0) \quad (2.83)$$

and comparing it with the sum over closed string states presented in Equation (2.80) for large R_t and R_s , the authors showed that $b = 0$ and, therefore, that no-boundary terms appear in the energy expression of the open/closed flux tube.

The authors computed the associated partition function one order further:

$$\mathcal{Z} = \mathcal{Z}_0(1 - \langle S_{LW2} + S_{LW3} \rangle_0) \quad (2.84)$$

and using the duality comparison they showed that the spectrum of the closed flux tube is given by the following expression (with $T \rightarrow \sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$):

$$E(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l + \frac{4\pi}{l} \left(n - \frac{D-2}{24} \right) - \frac{C\pi^2}{l^3} \left(n - \frac{D-2}{24} \right)^2 + \mathcal{O}(l^{-4}). \quad (2.85)$$

perturbative expansion.

At $D = 2+1$, $C = 8/\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$ agreeing with the result of Drummond and Dass-Matlock presented in Equation (2.71). At $D = 3 + 1$, C is an unconstrained coefficient.

2.6 Aharony and Karzbrun results

Recently, Aharony and Karzbrun [20] revived the method that Lüscher and Weisz adopted, in order to improve the existing result of [21]. The authors included in the action sixth-derivative terms with weights expressed by unknown couplings and considered two separated analyses in order to constrain these couplings. The first analysis involves the open-closed string duality that Lüscher and Weisz used in [21]. A similar analysis was also performed for a string wrapping a torus in space-time which involves the periodic orthogonal coordinates $X^0 = X^0 + R_t$, $X^1 = X^1 + R_s$. Once more we can define the partition function as having the interpretation of the sum over closed string states, rather than open string states as in Equation (2.78), winding in the X^1 circle and propagating in the X^0 circle.

As before, by swapping $R_t \leftrightarrow R_s$ the partition function can also receive the interpretation of the Polyakov correlator that creates or annihilates a closed flux tube which winds around the X^0 circle. Within this interpretation, for large R_t and R_s , the partition function can be expanded in a series of Bessel functions according to:

$$\mathcal{Z}(R_s, R_t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} R_s \left(\frac{\tilde{E}_n(R_t)}{R_s} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}(D-1)} K_{\frac{1}{2}(D-1)}(\tilde{E}_n(R_t)R_s). \quad (2.86)$$

This sketches a closed-closed string duality that can be used to constrain the unknown couplings appearing in the action. Due to the consideration of the closed-closed string duality, any boundary terms and arbitrary mass parameters are by definition absent from the action. Hence, the action up to sixth-derivative order reads:

$$S_{AK} = TR_s R_t + S_{LW0} + S_{LW2} + S_{LW3} + S_{AK4} + S_{AK5} + S_{AK6} + \int \mathcal{O}(\partial^8 X^{4,6,8}). \quad (2.87)$$

At sixth-derivative order, where the couplings have dimension of $[\text{length}]^3$, the terms that contribute in the action independently and which also survive any equation of motion (EOM) eliminations and field redefinition simplifications are the following:

$$S_{AK4} = c_4 \int d\tau d\sigma (\partial_\alpha \partial_\beta X^i \partial_\alpha \partial_\beta X^i) (\partial_\gamma X^j \partial_\gamma X^j), \quad (2.88)$$

$$S_{AK5} = c_5 \int d\tau d\sigma (\partial_\alpha X^i \partial_\alpha X^i) (\partial_\beta X^j \partial_\beta X^j) (\partial_\gamma X^k \partial_\gamma X^k), \quad (2.89)$$

and

$$S_{AK6} = c_6 \int d\tau d\sigma (\partial_\alpha X^i \partial_\beta X^i) (\partial_\alpha X^j \partial_\beta X^j) (\partial_\gamma X^k \partial_\gamma X^k). \quad (2.90)$$

By calculating the partition function presented in Equation (2.84) and applying the closed-closed string duality one can show that the coefficient C of Equation (2.85) takes the value $C = 8/\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$ for any D .

By calculating the partition function at the next order:

$$\mathcal{Z} = \mathcal{Z}_0(1 - \langle S_{LW2} + S_{LW3} \rangle_0 + \frac{1}{2} \langle (S_{LW2} + S_{LW3})^2 \rangle_0 - \langle S_{AK4} + S_{AK5} + S_{AK6} \rangle_0), \quad (2.91)$$

and making use of the closed-closed string duality, one can show that the spectrum of the closed flux tube in $D = 2 + 1$ is given by the expression (with $T \rightarrow \sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$):

$$E(l) = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l + \frac{4\pi}{l} \left(n - \frac{D-2}{24} \right) - \frac{8\pi^2}{\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l^3} \left(n - \frac{D-2}{24} \right)^2 + \frac{32\pi^3}{\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}^2 l^5} \left(n - \frac{D-2}{24} \right)^3 + \mathcal{O}(l^{-7}). \quad (2.92)$$

For $D > 3$ and $n = 0$, it can also be shown that the energy is given by Equation (2.92), while for $D > 3$ and $n > 0$ the $1/l^5$ depends upon the unconstrained coefficient c_4 .

2.7 Corrections to the free string in $D = 2 + 1$

Going one step further, we would like to note that in the calculation of the $k = 1$ flux tube, we have discovered that the actual spectrum can be approached by the free string Nambu-Goto (Equation (2.56)) spectrum much better than by any other result such as Formulae (2.68), (2.71) and (2.92). In fact for the ground state there is even good agreement for values of the string length l where the expansion of Nambu-Goto form (2.56) in powers of $1/\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l^2$ completely diverges. The implication is more than obvious: The full Nambu-Goto expression should be used as a starting point with additional corrections considered. This can, therefore, be expressed quantitatively as:

$$E_n^2(l) = (\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} l)^2 + 8\pi\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} \left(n - \frac{1}{24} \right) - \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} \frac{C_p}{(l\sqrt{\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}})}. \quad (2.93)$$

This has been used for fitting the ground states in order to extract the string tension in terms of the lattice spacing $a^2\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$ and the dimensionless correction C_p , with minimum leading permitting correction of $p = 3$. The value of $p = 3$ corresponds to the $\mathcal{O}(l^{-4})$ correction in the results of Drummond and Dass-Matlock, and Lüscher-Weisz. Until recently, the value of $p = 3$ had been systematically used for fitting the ground states. The new result of Aharony and Karzbrun, which appeared a few months ago, suggests that the permitting correction p should be $p = 6$ rather than $p = 3$.

2.8 Nambu-Goto String in $D = 2 + 1$

Let us now see how Nambu-Goto string implements in $D = 3$ and set the framework on which the discussion of our results will be based. A single closed string that wraps w times along the toroidally compactified direction is being considered. The Nambu-Goto string spectrum can be characterised by quantised transverse oscillations that can also be thought of as phonon modes propagating clockwise - right-handed ($\bar{\alpha}_{-k}$) and anticlockwise - left-handed (α_{-k}) along the string. The momentum of the latter is taken to be positive and the momentum of the former is taken to be negative. These modes are massless and they correspond to Goldstone bosons arising from the fact that the presence of the string spontaneously breaks the transverse translation invariance. Therefore, the energy of the massless phonon modes is the absolute value of momentum. The vector of momentum directs along the string and is quantised according to the Lattice periodicity with eigenvalues

expressed as: $\pm 2\pi k/lw; k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

We can denote the number of left- and right-moving phonons with momentum $+2\pi k/lw$ and $-2\pi k'/lw$ by the numbers $n_L(k)$ and $n_R(k')$, respectively. Using this notation we can re-express the eigenvalues of the number operators presented in Equations (2.31) as:

$$N \mapsto N_L = \sum_k \sum_{n_L(k)} n_L(k)k, \quad \tilde{N} \mapsto N_R = \sum_{k'} \sum_{n_R(k')} n_R(k')k' \quad (2.94)$$

The total energy of a state would, therefore, be determined by these numbers and the zero point energy. As derived in Equation (2.54), these numbers are related by the level matching constrain $N_L - N_R = qw; q \in \mathbb{Z}$ (where $-Q \rightarrow q$).

Closed bosonic string states in the flat Nambu-Goto framework can be described as irreducible representations of the $SO(D-2)$ rotation group. In $D = 3$, however, $SO(D-2)$ reduces to $O(1)$ with corresponding quantum number the parity P . Parity, with eigenvalues $P = \pm$, demonstrates how a state transforms irreducibly under reflections over the longitudinal direction, or in other words it flips the sign of the movers:

$$X_L \xrightarrow{P} -X_L \quad \text{and} \quad X_R \xrightarrow{P} -X_R \quad (2.95)$$

The above relation also suggests that the corresponding creation operators, (the left-handed and right-handed phonon operators α_{-k} and $\bar{\alpha}_{-k'}$, respectively) change sign under the action of Parity P :

$$\alpha_{-k} \xrightarrow{P} -\alpha_{-k} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{\alpha}_{-k'} \xrightarrow{P} -\bar{\alpha}_{-k'} \quad (2.96)$$

Therefore, the overall parity of a state can be defined by the following relation:

$$P = (-1)^{\text{number of phonons}} \equiv (-1)^{\sum_k \sum_{n_L(k)} n_L(k) + \sum_{k'} \sum_{n_R(k')} n_R(k')}, \quad (2.97)$$

suggesting that if the total number of movers is even(odd) then the corresponding parity will be $P = +(-)$. The energy of a closed bosonic string in $D = 3$ reads as:

$$E_{N_L, N_R, q, w}^2 = (w\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}l)^2 + 8\pi\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} \left(\frac{N_L + N_R}{2} - \frac{1}{24} \right) + \left(\frac{2\pi q}{l} \right)^2 \quad (2.98)$$

The degeneracy pattern of the energy levels can be determined by the total number of the different ways one can get the same value for $N_L + N_R$. Working gradually and adding a unit time by time, we start from $N_L + N_R = 0$ which corresponds to the ground state and make use of the level matching constrain, in order to build the spectrum of Nambu-Goto in $D = 3$. As an example let us take $N_L + N_R = 2$. This can be obtained either by setting $N_L = N_R = 1$ that corresponds to a state with $q = 0$ and phonon structure $\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$ or $N_L = 2, N_R = 0$ with $q = 2$ and two possible phonon configurations $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}|0\rangle$ and $\alpha_{-2}|0\rangle$. As a more general example, in Table 2.1 we present the seven lowest energy levels of a single-wound closed bosonic string for $q = 0, 1, 2$, in terms of the left- and right-movers α_{-k} and $\bar{\alpha}_{k'}$, respectively. Additionally, the length dependence of these states is presented in Figure 2.2.

level	N_L	N_R	q	$P = +$	$P = -$
0	0	0	0	$ 0\rangle$	
1	1	1	0	$\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1} 0\rangle$	
2	2	2	0	$\alpha_{-2}\bar{\alpha}_{-2} 0\rangle, \alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1} 0\rangle$	$\alpha_{-2}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1} 0\rangle, \alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-2} 0\rangle$
3	1	0	1		$\alpha_{-1} 0\rangle$
4	2	1	1	$\alpha_{-2}\bar{\alpha}_{-1} 0\rangle$	$\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1} 0\rangle$
5	2	0	2	$\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1} 0\rangle$	$\alpha_{-2} 0\rangle$
6	3	1	2	$\alpha_{-3}\bar{\alpha}_{-1} 0\rangle, \alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1} 0\rangle$	$\alpha_{-2}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1} 0\rangle$

Table 2.1: The seven lowest energy levels for the $w = 1$ closed string. If the number of oscillators applied on the vacuum is even(odd) then the state has positive(negative) parity.

Figure 2.2: The seven lowest Nambu-Goto energy levels for $q = 0, 1, 2$, as these derive from Equation (2.98), in dimensionless units as a function of the dimensionless string length $l\sqrt{\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}}$ for a $w = 1$ string. Red denotes the energy levels for $q = 0$, green the energy levels for $q = \pm 1$ and blue the energy levels for $q = \pm 2$.

Chapter 3

Lattice Gauge Theories

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter we discuss lattice gauge theory, focusing on the lattice formulation of $SU(N)$ gauge fields and the tools that enable us to obtain the closed flux tube spectrum. The lattice has been known as a regularization scheme enabling high energy theorists to perform calculations without facing the ultraviolet divergences appearing in the continuum. Moreover, the importance of the lattice is not only restricted to its interpretation as a regularisation scheme, but it also expands to its usage as a formulation able in giving results in the strong¹ coupling regime of strongly coupled field theories, such as QCD. This feature of the lattice is going to be exploited in order to study numerically the properties of the closed confining flux tube. The chapter has the following structure:

A brief picture on the (non-)Abelian fields in the continuum is first presented, focusing on their geometrical properties in order to present the connection between the continuum and the discretised theories. The next step would be to derive the $SU(N)$ Yang-Mills Lagrangian density, the theory that governs the dynamics of the closed flux tube. Then, we introduce the elegant formulation of the $SU(N)$ fields on the lattice proposed by Wilson in 1974 [77]. In that section the Wilson action is presented in both $D = 3 + 1$ and $D = 2 + 1$ providing a demonstration of the fact that it has the right continuum limit defined by the Yang-Mills Lagrangian.

In the continuum, Feynman's stylish treatment of field theories taught that the calculation of a physical quantity can be reformulated as a path integral. Converting this integral according to lattice formulation we find that its high-multidimensionality makes it numerically incalculable using traditional mesh techniques due to CPU time limitations. The only possible way of approaching a solution is by treating it statistically through Monte-Carlo simulations. Hence, in the second part of this chapter the particulars of the adopted Monte-Carlo method are explained, focusing on the quasi-heat-bath Cabibbo-Marinari algorithm, the Kennedy-Pendleton algorithm for updating $SU(2)$ lattices and finally the over-relaxation algorithm. A brief presentation of our simulation is also included.

The mass or the energy of colour singlet states in lattice QCD can be calculated using correlation functions of gauge invariant operators which are expected to project onto the right physical states described by particular configurations of quantum numbers. In the section that follows a description of the procedure necessary for the extraction of the energy

¹Using the term "strong coupling" we do not refer to the strong coupling limit of lattice gauge theories, but just to couplings that are weak enough to use perturbation theory

of the torelon from correlation functions of fields is offered. This is divided into three parts. In the first part we explain how one could give an estimate of the ground energy using the definition of the effective energy, then we dedicate a few paragraphs to a discussion on the correlator fittings and their systematics; finally we present the variational calculation, the method that enables us to extract the excitation spectrum of the torelons.

This chapter closes by briefly discussing statistical issues such as the jackknife error analysis and Bayesian constrained fits. These statistical procedures enable us to estimate averages and variances on the calculated quantities and, moreover, to perform curve fits involving the derivation of averages and variances of fitting parameters. The significance of these matters, is important, since it is through them that the excitations of the closed flux tube and the string tension (in lattice spacing units i.e. $a^2\sigma_f$) are being statistically estimated.

3.2 The Geometry of Gauge Fields

3.2.1 Abelian Case

Although this work has been strictly restricted to the pure gauge theory, we will use the formulation of matter fields in order to address and discuss the tools used in this project. Let us begin with a complex Dirac field $\psi(x)$ and assume that our theory is invariant under local $U(1)$ transformations of the kind:

$$\psi(x) \longrightarrow e^{i\beta(x)}\psi(x). \quad (3.1)$$

If instead of a local gauge transformation we had a global one, forming a Lagrangian would be a very easy task. Now the Lagrangian is getting more complicated, since, apart from the mass term $m\bar{\psi}(x)\psi(x)$ which is totally permitted by the local invariance (3.1), we need to also consider the derivative terms. Let us now see how the quantity $\partial_\mu\psi(x)$ transforms under this local gauge transformation. By definition:

$$n^\mu\partial_\mu\psi(x) = \lim_{a\rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{a}[\psi(x+a\hat{n}) - \psi(x)], \quad (3.2)$$

where n^μ is the vector indicating the direction \hat{n} . What the above expression shows is that the derivative of the Dirac field has no straightforward transformation and that at first sight it has a useless geometric interpretation.

The resulting problem could be easily solved if we introduced the scalar quantity $U(x, y) \in U(1)$ that transforms as:

$$U(x, y) \longrightarrow e^{i\beta(y)}U(x, y)e^{-i\beta(x)}, \quad (3.3)$$

under the transformation (3.1). This scalar quantity is known in Field Theory as parallel transporter or comparator and is usually restricted to be unitary and set to $U(x, x) = 1$. In general, we can define a parallel transporter for every curve in space-time in a continuous and differentiable way. We require the parallel transporter to be given as a pure phase, such as:

$$U(x, y) = Pe^{i\phi(y, x)}, \quad (3.4)$$

with $\phi(x, y) = g \int_x^y dz_\mu A^\mu(z)$. The constant g is arbitrarily extracted and it corresponds to

the Abelian bare coupling constant and $A_\mu(x)$ is the vector field which carries the dynamics of the connection; the gauge field is also called “connection”. If we now define the curve in space-time from x to y as ℓ_{xy} , then the parallel transporters will satisfy the following conditions:

1. $U(\emptyset) = 1$.

where \emptyset denotes the path of zero length.

2. $U(\ell_1 \circ \ell_2) = U(\ell_1)U(\ell_2)$.

where $\ell_1 \circ \ell_2$ denotes the path consisting of ℓ_1 followed by ℓ_2

3. $U(-\ell) = U(\ell)^{-1} = U(\ell)^\dagger$.

where $-\ell$ denotes the path ℓ in the opposite way

Using now the parallel transporter for an infinitesimal $|y - x|$ separation, we can define the covariant derivative as follows:

$$n^\mu D_\mu \psi(x) = \lim_{a \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{a} [\psi(x + a\hat{n}) - U(x, x + a\hat{n})\psi(x)]. \quad (3.5)$$

The parallel transporter for infinitesimally separated points can be expressed as:

$$U(x, x + a\hat{n}) = 1 - igan^\mu A_\mu(x) + \mathcal{O}(a^2). \quad (3.6)$$

Using this definition we can show that the covariant derivative takes the form:

$$D_\mu \psi(x) = \partial_\mu \psi(x) + igA_\mu(x)\psi(x). \quad (3.7)$$

Under the local gauge transformation, the field A_μ transforms as:

$$A_\mu(x) \rightarrow A_\mu(x) - \frac{1}{g} \partial_\mu \beta(x). \quad (3.8)$$

To obtain that the resulting action would be invariant under local gauge transformations, we must use the fact that indeed the covariant derivative transforms covariantly under the transformations, allowing the derivative term of the Lagrangian to remain unaltered:

$$D_\mu \psi(x) \rightarrow e^{i\beta(x)} D_\mu \psi(x). \quad (3.9)$$

Until now we have been recovering the basic ingredients of the Abelian gauge theory $U(1)$, such as QED. It would be important though to emphasise that the vector field A_μ results as a consequence of the local $U(1)$ symmetry. Without this field we would not have been able to build an invariant Lagrangian under the local transformation (3.1).

We now proceed to the extraction of the kinetic part of the Lagrangian for the gauge field A_μ , in order to complete the presentation of the Abelian case. In order to do this, we use the path ordered product of parallel transporters than runs along the perimeter of an oriented infinitesimal square located on the discretised space-time, such as the one that appears in Figure 3.1. This gauge invariant construction will play a fundamental role in the development of the lattice formulation of the non-Abelian gauge theory. Since the field $A_\mu(x)$ appears as a connection in the definition of the parallel transporter we adopt the convention of locating it at somepoint, let us say at the middle, on the joint between two

discretised points linked together by the parallel transporter:

$$U(x, x + a\hat{n}) = \exp \left[-igan^\mu A_\mu(x + \frac{a}{2}\hat{n}) \right]. \quad (3.10)$$

Having in mind that $U(x, y) = U^\dagger(y, x)$, the path order product denoted as $\mathbf{U}(x)$ reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}(x) &= U(x, x + a\hat{\mu})U(x + a\hat{\mu}, x + a\hat{\mu} + a\hat{\nu})U(x + a\hat{\mu} + a\hat{\nu}, x + a\hat{\nu})U(x + a\hat{\nu}, x) \\ &= U(x, x + a\hat{\mu})U(x + a\hat{\mu}, x + a\hat{\mu} + a\hat{\nu})U^\dagger(x + a\hat{\nu}, x + a\hat{\mu} + a\hat{\nu})U^\dagger(x, x + a\hat{\nu}). \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

As mentioned before this is a locally invariant quantity² and will, therefore, give us a locally gauge invariant function of the gauge fields in the continuum limit $a \rightarrow 0$. Inserting the expression (3.10) in Equation (3.12) we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}(x) &= e^{-igaA_\mu(x + \frac{a}{2}\hat{\mu})} e^{-igaA_\nu(x + a\hat{\mu} + \frac{a}{2}\hat{\nu})} e^{+igaA_\mu(x + a\hat{\nu} + \frac{a}{2}\hat{\mu})} e^{+igaA_\nu(x + \frac{a}{2}\hat{\nu})} \\ &= e^{+iga \left[A_\mu(x + a\hat{\nu} + \frac{a}{2}\hat{\mu}) - A_\mu(x + \frac{a}{2}\hat{\mu}) \right] - iga \left[A_\nu(x + a\hat{\mu} + \frac{a}{2}\hat{\nu}) - A_\nu(x + \frac{a}{2}\hat{\nu}) \right]} \\ &\xrightarrow{a \rightarrow 0} 1 - ia^2 g F_{\mu\nu}(x) \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

with

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu(x) - \partial_\nu A_\mu(x). \quad (3.13)$$

being the field tensor which is invariant under the local transformation (3.1). So, the lagrangian would be made out of the tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$ and indeed the Abelian Lagrangian density that gives the right equations of motion for the gauge fields is given by:

$$\mathcal{L}_A = -\frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu}. \quad (3.14)$$

As we shall soon see, the gauge invariant quantity $\mathbf{U}(x)$ is directly related to the kinetic term of the Lagrangian. This will be shown for the case of our interest, namely the non-Abelian. Having described the, simpler, Abelian case, it is time to present the more complicated non-Abelian gauge theory.

3.2.2 The Non-Abelian case: The Yang-Mills Lagrangian

In the previous section we showed that the simple geometrical constructions can yield an Abelian gauge theory, such as Maxwell's theory of electrodynamics. The purpose of this section is the generalisation of the local symmetry from $U(1)$ to $SU(N)$ aiming at obtaining the derivation of the $SU(N)$ QCD Yang-Mills Lagrangian density.

Let us consider that instead of a single fermionic field, we have an N -plet of Dirac fields:

$$\psi(x) = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_1(x) \\ \psi_2(x) \\ \vdots \\ \psi_N(x) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.15)$$

²In the non-abelian case we need to take the trace of $\mathbf{U}(x)$ to make it invariant.

that transforms under the local transformation according to:

$$\psi(x) \rightarrow V(x)\psi(x), \quad (3.16)$$

with $V(x) \in SU(N)$ given by:

$$V(x) = e^{-i\beta^\alpha(x)T^\alpha}. \quad (3.17)$$

$V(x)$ belongs to the group $SU(N)$ and T^α $\alpha = 1 \dots N^2 - 1$ are hermitian traceless matrices that belong to the Lie algebra $\mathfrak{su}(\mathfrak{N})$ of the $SU(N)$ gauge group. For the case of $SU(3)$ a possible convention could be the well-known Gell-Mann matrices. To be able to proceed we note that T^α satisfies:

$$\text{Tr}(T^\alpha T^\beta) = \frac{1}{2}\delta^{\alpha\beta} \quad (3.18)$$

and the commutation relations:

$$[T^\alpha, T^\beta] = if^{\alpha\beta\gamma}T^\gamma, \quad (3.19)$$

where the numbers $f^{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ are the real and totally antisymmetric structure constants. However, the fact that the $N^2 - 1$ matrices T^α do not commute with one another introduces a number of additional complications. This is also the reason of naming these theories non-Abelian; the field theory associated to a non-commuting local symmetry is called a non-Abelian gauge theory. By applying similar methods as in the previous section but always having in mind the extra complications that arise by the presence of the non-Abelian gauge group let us see how the relevant gauge field Lagrangian density forms.

The fact that the gauge symmetry is local suggests that we must once more define a covariant derivative. Again the covariant derivative is given by Equation (3.5) with the exception that now the parallel transporter $U(y, x)$ must be an $N \times N$ matrix satisfying the following transformation law:

$$U(x, y) \rightarrow V(y)U(x, y)V^\dagger(x). \quad (3.20)$$

Again $U(x, y)$ is given by Equation (3.4) with $\phi = g \int_x^y dz_\mu A^\mu{}^\alpha(z)T^\alpha$. For an infinitesimal $|y - x|$ separation the parallel transporter can be written as:

$$U(x, x + a\hat{n}) = \mathbf{1} + igan^\mu A_\mu^\alpha T^\alpha + \mathcal{O}(a^2). \quad (3.21)$$

Here g denotes the bare coupling constant of the $SU(N)$ gluonic field. If we insert the above expansion into the definition of the covariant derivative (3.5) then we find that the covariant derivative for the non-Abelian case would be given by:

$$D_\mu = \partial_\mu - igA_\mu^\alpha T^\alpha. \quad (3.22)$$

This expression shows clearly that the covariant derivative requires $N^2 - 1$ vector fields, each one associated with one generator of the transformation group. It should be kept in mind that for $N = 3$ the theory includes 8 gluonic fields. The transformation of the gauge field can be derived by inserting the expression (3.21) into the transformation (3.20). After

some massage we obtain that:

$$A_\mu^\alpha(x)T^\alpha \rightarrow A_\mu^\alpha(x)T^\alpha + \frac{1}{g}(\partial_\mu\beta^\alpha(x))T^\alpha + f^{\alpha\beta\gamma}T^\alpha A_\mu^\beta(x)\beta^\gamma(x). \quad (3.23)$$

Comparing the transformation for the Abelian case presented in Equation (3.8) to that for the non-Abelian case given in Equation (3.23) we see that the latter has an additional term that rises from the non-commutativity of the transformations. The expression for the transformation of the gauge field (3.23) in combination with the infinitesimal transformation for the fermionic field $\psi \rightarrow (1 + i\beta^\alpha T^\alpha)\psi$ can lead to the infinitesimal transformation of the covariant derivative:

$$D_\mu(x)\psi \rightarrow (1 + i\beta^\alpha T^\alpha)D_\mu\psi(x). \quad (3.24)$$

This shows that the covariant derivative transforms in the same way as the fermionic field and, therefore, the kinetic term of the fermionic part of the action stays unchanged under the local transformation. The transformation of the covariant derivative under the local symmetry leads to the transformation:

$$[D_\mu, D_\nu]\psi(x) \rightarrow V(x)[D_\mu, D_\nu]\psi(x). \quad (3.25)$$

It can be shown that $[D_\mu, D_\nu]$ is not a differential operator, but instead a multiplicative factor that forms the Field Strength Tensor of $SU(N)$:

$$[D_\mu, D_\nu] = -igF_{\mu\nu}^\alpha T^\alpha \quad (3.26)$$

with the Field Strength Tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$ given by:

$$F_{\mu\nu}^\alpha T^\alpha = \partial_\mu A_\nu^\alpha T^\alpha - \partial_\nu A_\mu^\alpha T^\alpha + gf^{\alpha\beta\gamma}T^\alpha A_\nu^\beta A_\mu^\gamma. \quad (3.27)$$

The same relationship can also be obtained for the Abelian case with the term that contains the structure constants absent. This term breaks the local invariance of the Field Strength Tensor, since it transforms as:

$$F_{\mu\nu}^\alpha T^\alpha \rightarrow V(x)F_{\mu\nu}^\alpha T^\alpha V^\dagger(x). \quad (3.28)$$

However, the form of the right hand-side term of transformation (3.28) suggests that we could create gauge-invariant combinations of the Field Strength Tensors, such as the gauge-invariant kinetic term of the Lagrangian density for the gauge field $A_\mu^\alpha(x)$:

$$\mathcal{L}_{Y.M} = -\frac{1}{2}\text{tr}[F_{\mu\nu}^\alpha F^{\beta\mu\nu} T^\alpha T^\beta] = -\frac{1}{4}[F_{\mu\nu}^\alpha F^{\alpha\mu\nu}]. \quad (3.29)$$

This Lagrangian density describes the interacting non-Abelian $SU(N)$ field theory known as Yang-Mills theory.

Although we can still use the quantity $\mathbf{U}(x)$ to extract the gauge field kinetic part of the Lagrangian, we postpone this for the Section 3.3.3, where we perform the discretisation of the gluonic action on the lattice based on the gauge invariant structure $\mathbf{U}(x)$. The only difference now, is that we will be considering the Euclidean version of the action rather than the Minkowskian.

3.3 Lattice formulation

3.3.1 Generalities

As it has already been mentioned, physicists have been driven to the lattice formulation by the feature of confinement, which appears in QCD and is also assumed to occur in the Large- N QCD theory. It was K. Wilson in 1974 [77, 78] who was the first to introduce the lattice gauge theory in order to formulate QCD non-perturbatively, aiming to deliver an explanation of confinement and enabling high energy physicists to determine numerically the hadron spectrum.

On the lattice, the Field Theory becomes mathematically well-defined on a Euclidean lattice (by Wick rotating the real-Minkowskian time coordinate: $t \rightarrow -i\tau$). The basic degrees of freedom in the lattice QCD are the links, $SU(N)$ group elements corresponding to the discretised version of the parallel transporters and associated with the straight-line curves joining the nearest pairs of lattice sites and the fermionic matter fields located at the sites of the lattice. However, in the pure gauge theory sector, matter fields do not appear and, therefore, the Lagrangian density that governs the dynamics of the theory would be the Euclidean discretised version of the Yang-Mills Lagrangian density of Equation (3.42). Hence, in the next subsection we show how our theory should be modified in the Euclidean space-time, and subsequently we explain how one can construct the simplest equivalence of this theory on the lattice by means of deriving the simplest discretised action (Equation (3.42)) that tends to the right continuum limit (Equation (3.33)); this is called the Wilson action.

3.3.2 Minkowski \rightarrow Euclidean

In the previous section we derived the form of the $SU(N)$ Yang-Mills Lagrangian density which describes the theory of our interest. This is presented in Equation (3.29) and, according to it, the Minkowskian action describing the gauge fields is given by:

$$S_G = -\frac{1}{2} \int d^4x \operatorname{Tr} \left[F_{\mu\nu}^\alpha F^{\beta\mu\nu} T^\alpha T^\beta \right]. \quad (3.30)$$

Before proceeding to the lattice formulation it would be useful to derive the expression that gives the Euclidean version of the action. First we Wick-rotate the time variable: $x^0 \rightarrow -ix_4$. At the same time we replace the time component of the gauge-field A^0 with iA_4 . According to the above conventions, the gauge field action takes the following form:

$$S_G \rightarrow \frac{i}{2} \int d^4x \operatorname{Tr} \left[F_{\mu\nu}^\alpha F^{\beta\mu\nu} T^\alpha T^\beta \right]. \quad (3.31)$$

The probability amplitude in the Feynman path integral under a Wick-rotation transforms as:

$$e^{iS_G} \xrightarrow{\text{Wick Rotation}} e^{-S_E} \quad (3.32)$$

and therefore the Euclidean action is given as:

$$S_E = \frac{1}{2} \int d^4x \operatorname{Tr} \left[F_{\mu\nu}^\alpha F^{\beta\mu\nu} T^\alpha T^\beta \right]. \quad (3.33)$$

3.3.3 Wilson Action

In this subsection the Wilson action is presented; this is the simplest form of gauge action one can construct on the lattice. In order to construct the gauge field action, the continuum action needs to be discretised. This action should be gauge invariant, and the only gauge invariant quantity one can construct on the lattice is the path order product of links along closed paths with the simplest such path the plaquette presented in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Plaquette: The simplest closed path ordered product of link matrices

If now a parallel transporter $U \in SU(N)$ associated with a link b that initiates from x can also be denoted as:

$$U(b) \equiv U(x + a\hat{\mu}, x) \equiv U_{x, x+a\hat{\mu}} \equiv U_{\mu}(x), \quad (3.34)$$

where the Lorentz index μ is the direction of the link b , then a plaquette containing the points i, j, k and l defined in Figure 3.1 can be expressed as:

$$\text{Tr}U_P = \text{Tr} [U(x, x + a\hat{\mu})U(x + a\hat{\mu}, x + a\hat{\mu} + a\hat{\nu})U(x + a\hat{\nu} + \hat{\mu}, x + a\hat{\nu})U(x + a\hat{\nu}, x)] \quad (3.35)$$

or equivalently:

$$\text{Tr}U_P = \text{Tr} \left[U(x, x + a\hat{\mu})U(x + a\hat{\mu}, x + a\hat{\mu} + a\hat{\nu})U^{\dagger}(x + a\hat{\nu}, x + a\hat{\nu} + \hat{\mu})U^{\dagger}(x, x + a\hat{\nu}) \right] \quad (3.36)$$

It is easy now to show that the trace of the plaquette $\text{Tr}U_P$ remains the same under gauge transformations:

$$\text{Tr} \{U'_P\} = \text{Tr} \{U_P\}. \quad (3.37)$$

This tells us that the trace of the plaquette is a “good” observable, since it is gauge invariant and, therefore, can provide the basic element for the construction of the lattice gauge fields action. Group elements $U(x, x + a\hat{\mu}) \in SU(N)$ with $i = x$ and $j = x + a\hat{\mu}$ can be written as:

$$U_{i,j} = e^{igaA_{\mu}(\xi_{\mu})}, \quad (3.38)$$

where $A_{\mu} \in \mathfrak{su}(\mathfrak{N})$ is an element of the Lie algebra of $SU(N)$ and ξ_{μ} denotes the middle of the straight-line path connecting two neighbouring sites on which the gauge field is located at:

$$\xi_{\mu} = \frac{1}{2}a(i + j). \quad (3.39)$$

Having defined the gauge invariant plaquette, let us now demonstrate how this leads to the relevant action. Wilson has proposed that the gauge action on the lattice could be expressed as the sum over the actions of each lattice plaquette:

$$S = \sum_{\text{plaquettes}} S_{\text{plaquette}}. \quad (3.40)$$

The action for each plaquette in $SU(N)$ is given by the following expression:

$$S_{\text{plaquette}} = \beta \left[1 - \frac{1}{N} \text{Tr}(U_{i,j} U_{j,k} U_{k,l} U_{l,i}) \right], \quad (3.41)$$

where $i, j, k,$ and l are the four lattice sites associated with the four plaquette corners and being oriented as in Figure 3.1. The factor $1/N$ is used for the normalisation of the expression (3.41). The additional constant in Equation (3.41) ensures that the action would vanish when the link variables approach the unit. The definition of β will be determined in the next page. Therefore the gluonic action will be given by:

$$S = \sum_{\text{plaquettes}} \beta \left[1 - \frac{1}{N} \text{Tr}(U_{i,j} U_{j,k} U_{k,l} U_{l,i}) \right] \quad (3.42)$$

Having expressed the gauge action on the lattice, a reasonable question rises. How is the Wilson's action for $SU(N)$ related to the pure Yang-Mills action for gauge fields in the continuum? In other words, does the Wilson action give the right form in the continuum limit? This is a question that can be easily answered by taking the continuum limit of the expression (3.42). In order to send the Wilson action to the continuum limit, one should use the fact that:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr} U_P &= \text{Tr} \left[U_{n\hat{x}, n\hat{x}+a\hat{\mu}} U_{n\hat{x}+a\hat{\mu}, n\hat{x}+a\hat{\mu}+a\hat{\nu}} U_{n\hat{x}+a\hat{\nu}, n\hat{x}+a\hat{\nu}+a\hat{\mu}}^\dagger U_{n\hat{x}, n\hat{x}+a\hat{\nu}}^\dagger \right] \\ &= \text{Tr} \left[e^{igaA_\mu(na\hat{x}+\hat{\mu}a/2)} e^{igaA_\nu(na\hat{x}+\hat{\mu}a+\hat{\nu}a/2)} e^{-igaA_\mu(na\hat{x}+\hat{\nu}a+\hat{\mu}a/2)} e^{-igaA_\nu(na\hat{x}+\hat{\nu}a/2)} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3.43)$$

and then the Campbell-Baker-Hausdorff formula:

$$e^A \cdot e^B = e^{A+B+\frac{1}{2}[A,B]+\dots} \quad (3.44)$$

It can be shown that:

$$\begin{aligned} U_{n\hat{x}, n\hat{x}+a\hat{\mu}} U_{n\hat{x}+a\hat{\mu}, n\hat{x}+a\hat{\mu}+a\hat{\nu}}^\dagger U_{n\hat{x}+a\hat{\nu}, n\hat{x}+a\hat{\nu}+a\hat{\mu}}^\dagger U_{n\hat{x}, n\hat{x}+a\hat{\nu}} &= e^{iga^2(\partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu + ig[A_\mu, A_\nu]) + \mathcal{O}(a^3)} \\ &= e^{iga^2 F_{\mu\nu}}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.45)$$

Where $F_{\mu\nu}$ is the gauge field Strength Tensor. If we now expand the exponential in Equation (3.45), and use that:

$$a^4 \sum_{\text{plaquettes}} = a^4 \sum_{n, \mu < \nu} = \frac{1}{2} a^4 \sum_{n, \mu \neq \nu} = \frac{1}{2} a^4 \sum_{n, \mu, \nu}, \quad (3.46)$$

denoting the symmetry under $\mu \leftrightarrow \nu$ interchange, we can show that the lattice Wilson

action is equal to:

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\beta g^2}{2N} a^4 \sum_{n,\mu,\nu} \text{Tr}(F_{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\nu}) + \mathcal{O}(a^2). \quad (3.47)$$

The continuum limit can now be obtained by the replacement:

$$a^4 \sum_n \longrightarrow \int d^4x. \quad (3.48)$$

The final form of the gauge action would be:

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\beta g^2}{2N} \int d^4x \text{Tr}(F_{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\nu}) + \mathcal{O}(a^2). \quad (3.49)$$

Matching the action (3.49) to that of Equation (3.33) amounts to choosing the right value for β . Therefore, in $D = 3 + 1$ Euclidean dimensions, β would be given by the following expression:

$$\beta = \lim_{a \rightarrow 0} \frac{2N}{g^2}. \quad (3.50)$$

Using exactly the same procedure one can also show that in $D = 2+1$ Euclidean dimensions, the value of β would be given by:

$$\beta = \lim_{a \rightarrow 0} \frac{2N}{ag^2}, \quad (3.51)$$

where now g^2 has dimensionality of [mass]. The above definition of β shows that, tending to the continuum, the value of β goes to infinity. This is crucial, since we can approach the continuum on the lattice by choosing larger and larger values of β . This is systematically used in our calculations in order to approach the continuum limit.

3.3.4 Feynman Path Integral

Having defined the lattice gauge theory and the simplest action that drives the pure gauge field sector of the $SU(N)$ QCD on the lattice, let us proceed to the quantum theory. This can be achieved by inserting the action into the path integral defined by:

$$Z = \int dU e^{-S(U)}. \quad (3.52)$$

In the expression above we integrate over all the possible values of the gauge field $U \in SU(N)$. The link variables are elements of a compact group and thus it would be reasonable to use the invariant group measure or Haar measure dU for the integration. The expression (3.52) is nothing else but the partition function of the system.

The calculation of physical quantities in lattice QFT can be translated into the calculation of correlation functions. A correlation function is the expectation value of a quantity O that can be expressed as a function of the variables U .

$$\langle O \rangle = \frac{1}{Z} \int dU O(U) e^{-S(U)}. \quad (3.53)$$

As we will see later on the calculation, the closed flux tube spectrum is based on the calculation of correlation functions of torelons located onto two different time slices. Here the correlation function has the simple interpretation of creating a flux tube at some initial, and annihilated at some later, time.

For any compact group G , the Haar measure is the unique measure dU that satisfies the following properties:

1. The measure should be left- and right-invariant defined by:

$$\int dU f(U) = \int dU f(U'U) = \int dU f(UU''), \quad (3.54)$$

with $U', U'' \in G$

2. The measure should be normalised such that:

$$\int dU = 1. \quad (3.55)$$

3.4 Monte Carlo Simulations

3.4.1 Generalities

In this section we discuss some introductory issues on Monte Carlo simulations, starting from the obstacles one faces in calculating a Feynman path integral with variables belonging to a non-trivial gauge group, and moving to the overcoming of these problems using a statistical treatment. Generally, the Monte-Carlo simulation is an old technique firstly proposed in Statistical Physics by Metropolis in [79]. Using this method one can perform virtual experiments in solid state systems with properties driven by an arbitrary Hamiltonian. This enabled physicists to probe the dynamical features of several complex statistical systems that could not be approached analytically. It also played an important role in the study of the phase structure in several statistical systems. Breaking the low-energy physics limitations, Monte Carlo simulations have also been applied to high-energy physics equipping the particle physicist with a very powerful tool. This tool has helped lattice gauge theorists to fulfill their goals and it will be our topic of discussion in the next few paragraphs.

In the previous subsection we have seen that the calculation of physical quantities on the lattice can be reformulated into a multiple integral over all the possible values for the gauge fields. A first approach to such an integration would be to try to numerically evaluate the integral using traditional mesh techniques. At first view, this way of approaching the evaluation of the integral sounds reasonable. However, at the level of multidimensionality of such integrals, one soon realises that it would be impossible to perform this kind of computational work due to time shortage. As Creutz mentions in his book, we can consider a lattice with 10^4 sites and consequently 4×10^4 link variables. Let us now take the simplest non-trivial gauge group Z_2 , the partition function will be reduced to a sum with a number of terms being equal to 2^{40000} . This tells that the computational calculation of this sum will never be performed and it also suggests that we need a more sophisticated approach to calculate these integrals.

Having expressed the time-consuming difficulties in calculating Feynman integrals on the lattice occurring from the high dimensionality of variables, it is time to investigate whether a more “friendly” approach can be applied. The only possible way to achieve our

goals is the usage of a statistical treatment; by means of rather than summing exactly the vast number of terms that appear in the previous paragraph's example, we can just use a smaller number of terms associated with typical configurations which highly dominate the behaviour of the sum. This can be materialised through a Monte Carlo approach.

The aim of the Monte Carlo algorithm is to generate a relatively small number of field configurations which characterise a thermal equilibrium state in a statistical analog. Therefore, it begins with an initial field configuration, for example fully random or fully ordered in a particular way, and then it iteratively performs random changes on the field variables with a total probability density for encountering any field configuration C given by the Boltzman expression:

$$P(C) \propto e^{-S(C)}. \quad (3.56)$$

This is repeated until the thermal equilibrium or “thermalisation” has been achieved. Then we produce a “Markov Chain” of configurations by continuously applying random changes on the field variables with the right probability density.

In order to emphasise the relationship between lattice gauge theories and statistical mechanics we could re-define the lattice action as: $S(U) \rightarrow S(U)/\beta$ in such a way that β , which has been absorbed in the action expression, appears as a pre-factor of the action in the exponential of the Feynman Integral, and, therefore, in the Boltzman factor. From now on we can think of the computer as a “heat-bath” adjusted at inverse temperature β and Boltzman factor:

$$P(C) \propto e^{-\beta S(C)}. \quad (3.57)$$

The basic goal in numerical simulations is the generation of samples that consist of a large number N_c of field configurations \tilde{U}_n , $n_c = 1, 2, \dots, N_c$. After the thermal equilibrium has been reached, every time we update the gauge fields that is to say every time we force the field variables to fluctuate throughout the $SU(N)$ group manifold with canonical Boltzman factor given by Equation (3.57), we measure the value of a quantity O that can be expressed in terms consisting of colour singlet quantities of the fields U . At the end, a sample average of this quantity can be calculated as:

$$\langle O_L(U) \rangle = \frac{1}{N_c} \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} O_L(U_i) \pm \mathcal{O} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{n_c}} \right). \quad (3.58)$$

The expression above shows that the statistical fluctuations decrease with the square root of the number of different field configurations and consequently with the square root of the computing time. This can be viewed in [80]. The particular dependence of the statistical fluctuation on the computational time, could be a serious obstacle for one that needs to accurately derive a quantity aiming for a low noise to signal ratio. Just an example, to reduce the error by a factor of 10 we must increase the computational time a hundred times.

3.4.2 Cabibbo-Marinari Algorithm

An algorithm using the heat-bath method on the $SU(2)$ gauge group has been proposed by Creutz in [81]. This algorithm replaces a link U with a link variable chosen randomly with

The new updated link U' is obtained by multiplying the value of the previous link matrix U by m elements from the subgroups $SU(2)_q$ such as:

$$U' = A_m A_{m-1} \dots A_1 U, \quad A_q \in SU(2)_q, \quad (q = 1, \dots, m). \quad (3.63)$$

For simplicity we can now define:

$$U^{(q)} = A_q A_{q-1} \dots A_1 U, \quad U^{(0)} = U, \quad (3.64)$$

such as:

$$U^{(q)} = A_q U^{(q-1)}. \quad (3.65)$$

Each element A_q is being chosen randomly with measure:

$$dP(A_q) = d^{(q)} A_q \exp(-\beta S(A_q U^{(q-1)})) / Z_q(U^{(q-1)}), \quad (3.66)$$

with $d^{(q)} A_q$ being the Haar measure on $SU(2)_q$ and

$$Z_q = \int_{SU(2)} da \exp(-\beta S(AU)). \quad (3.67)$$

The problem of updating the $SU(N)$ link can now be reformulated to a problem of thermalising a matrix A with probability distribution given by Equation (3.66). In order to generate this distribution we use the action $S(AU)$ as this has been indicated in Equations (3.66) and (3.67). Therefore, we note that the Wilson action can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \beta S(AU) &= -\frac{\beta}{N} \text{Re}(\text{Tr} AUR) + \{\text{terms independent of } A\} \\ &= -\frac{\beta}{N} \text{Re}(\text{Tr} \mathcal{A} \mathcal{R}) + \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (3.68)$$

where R denotes the sum of the $2(D-1)$ path order products \tilde{U}_i of link variables that compose the ‘‘stables’’ which interact with the link being updated with $R = \sum_{i=1}^{2(D-1)} \tilde{U}_i$. \mathcal{R} is the 2×2 submatrix of R embedded in an $N \times N$ matrix with the same block structure as A .

The problem, therefore, reduces to the generation of an $SU(2)$ matrix according to the distribution:

$$Q(\mathcal{A}) d\mathcal{A} \propto \exp\left\{\frac{\beta}{N} \text{Tr} \mathcal{A} \mathcal{R}\right\} d\mathcal{A}, \quad (3.69)$$

with $d\mathcal{A}$ being the $SU(2)$ invariant Haar measure.

The problem can now be simplified if we consider the fact that the matrices $\mathcal{A} \in SU(2)$ and \mathcal{R} which is equal to a sum of $SU(2)$ can be parametrised in terms of the Pauli matrices,

$$\mathcal{A} = \alpha_0 \mathbf{1} + i \vec{\alpha} \cdot \vec{\tau} \quad (\alpha \in \mathbb{R}, \quad \alpha_0 \cdot \alpha_0 + \vec{\alpha} \cdot \vec{\alpha} = \mathbf{1}) \quad (3.70)$$

and

$$\mathcal{R} = r_0 \mathbf{1} + i \vec{r} \cdot \vec{\tau} \quad (r \in \mathbb{C}). \quad (3.71)$$

Now, we can show that:

$$\text{Re Tr } \{\mathcal{R}\mathcal{A}\} = \text{Re Tr } [(r_0\alpha_0 - \vec{r} \cdot \vec{\alpha})\mathbf{1}] = \xi \text{ Tr } \{u\mathcal{A}\}, \quad (3.72)$$

where $u \in SU(2)$, $\xi u_0 = \text{Re } r_0$, $\xi \vec{u} = \text{Re } \vec{r}$, $\xi = \sqrt{\det \mathcal{R}}$, and it can be easily shown that:

$$\xi = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\det(\mathcal{R} - \mathcal{R}^\dagger + \mathbf{1} \text{Tr} \mathcal{R}^\dagger)} \quad (3.73)$$

and

$$u = \frac{1}{2\xi} (\mathcal{R} - \mathcal{R}^\dagger + \mathbf{1} \text{Tr} \mathcal{R}^\dagger). \quad (3.74)$$

Simplifying the problem, we set $a = u\mathcal{A}$ with $a \in SU(2)$. This matrix can be parametrised as $a = a_0\mathbf{1} + i\vec{a} \cdot \vec{\tau}$ with ($a \in \mathbb{R}$, $a_0 \cdot a_0 + \vec{a} \cdot \vec{a} = \mathbf{1}$) Going back to Equation (3.69), we note that the distribution can now be expressed as:

$$Q(a)da \propto \exp\left\{\frac{\beta}{N}\xi \text{Tra}\right\} da = \exp\left\{\frac{2\beta}{N}\xi a_0\right\} da, \quad (3.75)$$

with Haar measure:

$$\begin{aligned} da &= da_0 d^3 a_i \delta(1 - a_0^2 - \vec{a} \cdot \vec{a}) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 - a_0^2} da_0 dr d\theta d\phi \sin\theta \delta(r - \sqrt{1 - a_0^2}). \end{aligned} \quad (3.76)$$

Finally, it is easy to understand that the problem of updating an $SU(2)$ matrix with probability distribution (3.69) has reached its simplest form. This suggests that one has to generate a_0 with distribution:

$$P(a_0)da_0 \propto \sqrt{1 - a_0^2} \exp\left\{\frac{2\beta}{N}\xi a_0\right\} da_0 \quad (3.77)$$

and a uniformly distributed vector \vec{a} onto an S^2 sphere.

In the next subsections we describe one of the most common heat-bath algorithms, proposed by Cabibbo and Marinari.

3.4.3 Kennedy-Pendleton Algorithm

A summary of this algorithm [82] follows. We denote with f a uniformly distributed pseudo-number within the unit interval $[0,1]$.

1. We set: $y_1 = \ln f_1$ and $y_2 = \ln f_2$.
2. We set $\omega = \cos^2(2\pi f_3)$.
3. Let $k = 1 + \frac{1}{4\beta\xi}(y_1 + y_2\omega)$.
4. Let $l = f_4^2 + k$.
5. As long as $l > 0$ go back to step 1, otherwise set $a_0 = 1 + \frac{1}{2\beta\xi}(y_1 + y_2\omega)$.

3.4.4 Over-relaxation Algorithm

It has been shown that, if the update simulation does not entirely consist of heat-bath updates, but it also includes over-relaxation steps [85, 86, 87, 88, 89], then the configurations and, consequently, the measurements get less correlated. This is of high importance since the less correlated the better the results by means of strong reduction on the fluctuations. The basic idea that one relies on is that by an over-relaxation sweep one could make the maximal possible change on a link without changing the action at all. The over-relaxation update is much faster than a heat-bath update since it does not go through accept-reject steps. Although its rapidness sounds attractive, it is not ergodic and has to be used in combination with the heat-bath algorithm. Since it is faster we could choose a ratio of one heat-bath to four over-relaxation sweeps (1 : 4). This is what has been used systematically throughout this project. A test on the over-relaxation method can be found in [43].

The simplest possible way of performing the over-relaxation is used. According to this, we can use the Cabibbo-Marinari algorithm and instead of proceeding to a heat-bath update, we replace the $SU(2)$ submatrix \mathcal{A} as this is defined in Equation (3.62) with $\mathcal{A}' = u^\dagger \mathcal{A}^\dagger u^\dagger$. It is easy to see that this replacement does not alter the action ($\sim \text{Tr} u \mathcal{A}$).

3.4.5 Our Simulation

1. Create $n_{\text{CPU}s}$ different “frozen” gauge-field configurations. This means that each link variable is set to unit. Each field configuration consists of $D \times L_{\parallel} \times L_{\perp} \times L_T$ link variables, with D being the dimension which in our case is $D = 3$, L_{\parallel} is the longitudinal size of the lattice, L_{\perp} is the transverse size of the lattice and L_T is the temporal size. We note that we impose periodic boundary conditions in each of the three lattice directions.
2. We thermalise them using different values of β associated with the confining phase. Each thermalisation consists of ~ 10000 thermalisation sweeps. Each resultant field configuration is written in the memory, in order to form the initial configuration for each different simulation which is about to be submitted on a single CPU.
3. Each simulation running on each one of the $n_{\text{CPU}s}$ different CPUs now reads the pre-existing field configurations.
4. All runs now use the same value of β which is associated with a given lattice spacing. It would be important to explain here that by thermalising the $n_{\text{CPU}s}$ different field configurations with different values of β to create initial configurations and then by thermalising them at the same value of β serves as a way to decorrelate the results obtained from runs on different CPUs.
5. On each CPU:
 - (a) We perform 10000 thermalisation sweeps in which we first run four over-relaxation sweeps and then one heat-bath sweep.
 - (b) After the thermalisation procedure described above has finished, we start taking measurements.
 - (c) We keep combining over-relaxation and standard heat-bath in the ratio 4 : 1 for updating the field configurations; every 5 or 10 sweeps we measure the average value of each operator $\Phi_i(t, p)$ with momentum p which is located onto a temporal

slice t and is expected to project onto the quantity under investigation, over all spatial lattice points $\{x_\perp(t), x_\parallel(t)\}$ and for each different lattice temporal slice $n_t = 1, \dots, L_T$:

$$\Phi_i(t, p) = \frac{1}{L_\parallel L_\perp} \sum_{x_\perp, x_\parallel} \Phi_i(t, x_\perp, x_\parallel) e^{ip_\parallel x_\parallel + ip_\perp x_\perp}, \quad (3.78)$$

as this is described in detail at Section 4.24. Next, we calculate the correlator components for different operators located onto different time slices that are a temporal distance Δt apart. This is done in such a way to impose Hermiticity at the correlator:

$$C_{ij}^m(\Delta t) = \frac{1}{2} [\langle \Phi_i(n_t) \Phi_j^*(n_t + \Delta n_t) \rangle + \langle \Phi_j^*(n_t) \Phi_i(n_t + \Delta n_t) \rangle], \quad (3.79)$$

where $\Delta n_t = 1, \dots, L_T/2$. Index m denotes the measurement.

- (d) We continue the same procedure of updating until we collect five different bins $n_c = 1, \dots, 5$ of equal number of measurements $m = 1, \dots, N_m$. The value of the correlator at each bin would be given by:

$$\langle C_{ij}(t) \rangle_{n_c} = \frac{1}{N_m} \sum_m^{N_m} C_{ij}^m(\Delta t). \quad (3.80)$$

6. The simulation has finished with $5 \times n_{\text{CPU}_s}$ bins of measurements.
7. The next step would be to analyse the results.

3.5 Energy Extraction

3.5.1 Effective Energy Calculation

Typically we want to calculate the energy spectrum of some sector of states described by specific quantum numbers such as momentum and parity. We do so from correlation functions of operators $\Phi(t)$ constructed in a way to project onto the same quantum numbers. In a gauge-invariant calculation, the elementary components of such operators are typically traces of closed loops, where contractible loops typically project onto glueballs and non-contractible (winding around a compact direction) loops typically project onto winding loops of flux. In general we have

$$\begin{aligned} C(t) &= \langle \Omega | \Phi^\dagger(t) \Phi(0) | \Omega \rangle = \langle \Omega | \Phi^\dagger e^{-t\hat{H}} \Phi | \Omega \rangle = \sum_{n,m=1}^{\infty} \langle \Omega | \Phi^\dagger | n \rangle \langle n | e^{-t\hat{H}} | m \rangle \langle m | \Phi | \Omega \rangle \\ &= \sum_{n,m=1}^{\infty} \langle \Omega | \Phi^\dagger | n \rangle \langle m | \Phi | \Omega \rangle \delta_{nm} e^{-tE_n} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \langle \Omega | \Phi^\dagger | n \rangle \langle n | \Phi | \Omega \rangle e^{-tE_n} \\ &= |\langle 0 | \Phi | \Omega \rangle|^2 e^{-tE_0} + \sum_{n>1}^{\infty} |\langle 0 | \Phi | \Omega \rangle|^2 e^{-tE_n} \end{aligned} \quad (3.81)$$

$$\xrightarrow{t \rightarrow \infty} |\langle 0 | \Phi(0) | \Omega \rangle|^2 e^{-E_0 t}, \quad (3.82)$$

where:

$$\hat{H}|n\rangle = E_n|n\rangle, \quad \text{and} \quad E_i \leq E_{i+1}. \quad (3.83)$$

In the expression above we first extract the transfer matrix $e^{-t\hat{H}}$ from $\Phi^\dagger(t)$ and then we insert two complete sets of states. After some simple quantum mechanical operations we derive that the correlator can be written as a sum of terms each one multiplied by a factor e^{-tE_n} (Equation (3.81)). As $t \rightarrow \infty$ the term with the lowest value on E_n will dominate the sum (Equation (3.82)).

The mass of a state can be estimated by calculating the effective mass or effective energy defined as:

$$aE_{eff}(t) = -\ln \left\{ \frac{C(t)}{C(t-a)} \right\} = -\ln \left\{ \frac{\langle \Phi^\dagger(t)\Phi(0) \rangle}{\langle \Phi^\dagger(t-a)\Phi(0) \rangle} \right\}. \quad (3.84)$$

With some massage we can show that as $t \rightarrow \infty$ the energy tends to E_0 . From the fact that all the coefficients in the final expression in Equation (3.81) are positive:

$$aE_{eff}(t) \geq aE_{eff}(t+a); \quad \forall t. \quad (3.85)$$

This is a very useful property which suggests that aE_{eff} should always provide us with an upper bound of the energy of the lightest state with quantum numbers that have been encoded in the construction of the operator Φ ; whatever the value of t is and whatever the operator Φ is. Since $C(t)$ decreases with t and as we argue later the statistical error on this is approximately independent of t , the statistical error on aE_{eff} increases. The increase of the statistical errors on aE_{eff} with t pushes us to assume that any apparent increase on the value of the effective energy as t increases is in fact a statistical fluctuation and therefore should be ignored.

The next step of the procedure is to identify an effective energy plateau $t \geq t_{min}$ with:

$$aE_{eff}(t_{min}) \geq aE_{eff}(t), \quad (3.86)$$

for $t \geq t_{min}$ within the errors. We can, therefore, regard the correlator $C(t \geq t_{min})$ as being given by a single exponential and we can then use $aE_{eff}(t_{min})$ as our estimate of the actual energy. It is obvious that the effective energy criterion becomes convincing only in the case where the errors are small enough. Only then this criterion will represent a significant constrain on which we could count. This could only happen if we use “good” operators. A good operator would be the one that maximises the normalised correlator $C(t) = \langle \Phi^\dagger(t)\Phi(0) \rangle / \langle \Phi^\dagger(0)\Phi(0) \rangle$.

3.5.2 Fitting

Albeit that effective energy criterion can provide us with a good estimate for the mass, we additionally estimate the mass by fitting the exponential in expression (3.82) from t_{min} onwards. This is a way to estimate the asymptotic exponential decay in Equation (3.82). The fluctuations that determine the error in the Monte Carlo calculation of $C(t)$ are themselves proportional to a higher order correlation function which can be seen to possess a disconnected piece. The error is, therefore, approximately independent of t , whereas $C(t)$, as we see from Equation (3.82), decreases at least exponentially with t . Thus the error/signal ratio increases exponentially with t and one can only obtain an accurately estimate for E_0

if the corresponding ground state already dominates $C(t)$ at small values of t . Once more the need of “good” operators that have a large projection onto the desired ground state rises. This can be achieved using standard smearing/blocking techniques, which produce operators that are smooth on physical length scales, with little computational effort.

If aE_0 is small enough so that the error/signal ratio is small for a nontrivial range of $t = an_t \geq t_1$, then the success of a single exponential fit provides significant evidence for it being appropriate. If, however, aE_0 is so large that this range is small, then we lose such evidence, and we will be, typically, using a single exponential fit over a range of t where the contribution of higher excited states as in Equation (3.81) may still be significant. Thus, our estimate of aE_0 will tend to become too high as the energy increases. This is an important systematic error that will be visible in some of our results in particular when we consider very long flux tubes (which are very massive) or highly excited flux tubes, even when they are not very long. This is also discussed in more detail in Section 5.4.

In Figure 3.2 we present a pictorialisation of a correlator between two operators that are supposed to project onto torelons states. These two operators are winding in opposite directions and separated by a temporal distance t . That is how the torelon correlators can be visualised in a $D = 1 + 1$ periodic lattice with time periodicity $T = aL_t$. The same picture could also be used to visualise the $D = 2 + 1$ and $D = 3 + 1$ cases with the only difference that there will exist one and two transverse directions equivalently on the tangent plane defined by the longitudinal (along the tube) and temporal directions. An additional piece of information that Figure 3.2 gives is that the periodicity of the temporal lattice is contributing to the correlator. This could be controlled by maximising the temporal size of the lattice, in order to minimise such contribution, and by using hyperbolic cosine fits, such as Equation (3.88), rather than just exponential fits, in order to take into account the contribution from the back of the torus. Taking into account this extra contribution, the correlation function now reads as:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Phi^\dagger(t)\Phi(0) \rangle &= \langle \Omega | e^{-(T-t)\hat{H}} \Phi^\dagger e^{-\hat{H}t} \Phi | \Omega \rangle \\ &= \sum_{n,m} |\langle n | \Phi | m \rangle|^2 e^{-(E_n + E_m)\frac{T}{2}} \cosh \left[(E_n - E_m) \left(\frac{T}{2} - t \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.87)$$

For $t \ll T$ and a large energy gap $(E_1 - E_0)t \gg 1$ the Equation (3.87) would be dominated by:

$$\langle \Phi^\dagger(t)\Phi(0) \rangle = 2|\langle 0 | \Phi | \Omega \rangle|^2 e^{-E_0\frac{T}{2}} \cosh \left[E_0 \left(\frac{T}{2} - t \right) \right]. \quad (3.88)$$

3.5.3 Variational Technique

In this section we briefly discuss the variational calculation, the procedure that enables us to extract the excitation spectrum of the torelons. The question of determining the excited spectrum of physical states in lattice QCD has been an open and still evolving task, receiving a lot of effort by the lattice community.

In Section 3.5.1 we close by suggesting that a good operator would be the one maximising the normalised correlator $C(t) = \langle \Phi^\dagger(t)\Phi(0) \rangle / \langle \Phi^\dagger(0)\Phi(0) \rangle$. Obviously, if we use a complete set of operators, there would be an operator maximising the above expression; more precisely, the operator associated with the wave-functional of the lightest state. How-

Figure 3.2: Pictorialisation of the torelon correlator on a toroidally compactified $D = 1 + 1$ space-time lattice. The two torelon operators are winding in opposite directions and are located onto temporal planes separated by $t = n_t a$ lattice spacings with T the temporal size of the periodic lattice.

ever, the basis is not complete, so we must find a more sophisticated approach to this maximisation. Furthermore, the problem does not stop here; all the methods of extracting the energy of the torelon are strictly restricted in the ground state. Since the important physics we are aiming for are “hidden” within the excitation spectra, projecting onto the ground state is almost useless. Apparently, there is need for a procedure able to project onto excited states. One can in principle consider that the sum (3.81) as $t \rightarrow \infty$ will lead to two or more exponentials [39] in an attempt to project onto the ground and additionally to the first and higher excited states. Although this method sounds plausible, it is unrealistic since one would have to fit on many parameters, maximising the errors and the uncertainties and demonstrating the need for more and more statistics. The answer to these obstacles is delivered by the variational technique [90].

The variational technique has first been encountered in the ordinary quantum mechanics [91, 92] (Rayleigh-Ritz variational principle) according to which one finds an upper bound estimate for the energy of a physical state, using trial states and minimising the energy of the system. Now instead of minimizing the action of the Hamiltonian \hat{H} we maximize the action of the transfer matrix $e^{-\hat{H}t}$.

According to the variational technique, the general strategy one has to adopt in order to obtain estimates for the ground state and the excited states of a particular sector of the theory, characterised by a specific configuration of quantum numbers, is as follows. First we construct a set of N_O Polyakov lattice operators $\phi_i : i = 1, \dots, N_O$, normalised such as $\langle \phi_i^\dagger \phi_i \rangle = 1$ and able to project onto states characterised by particular quantum numbers. In this project the quantum numbers of our interest are the Parity P and the longitudinal momentum $2\pi q/aL_{\parallel} : q = 1, 2, \dots$. The construction of the operators is an issue that is discussed in detail in Chapter 4. Secondly, we calculate the $N_O \times N_O$ correlation matrix $C(t)$. It is noted that this is the quantity being measured in the simulation (Section 3.4.5). The correlation matrix $C(t)$ is defined as:

$$C_{ij}(t) = \langle \phi_i^\dagger(t) \phi_j(0) \rangle. \quad (3.89)$$

Then we extract the normalised correlation function: $C^{-1}(0)C(a)$. The next step would be to find the normalised linear combination of the operators ϕ_i , which maximises $C(a) = \langle \phi^\dagger(t) \phi(0) \rangle$. This operator, namely Φ_0 , would be the best estimate for the ground state wave-functional, within the basis $\{\phi_i\}$. The best estimates for wave-functionals of excited

states can also be found. First we construct a basis of operators $\{\phi'\}$ that spans the $(N-1)$ -dimensional subspace of $\{\phi_i\}$ that is orthogonal to Φ_0 and then we find their linear combination that maximises $C'(a) = \langle \phi'^{\dagger}(t)\phi'(0) \rangle$; this will result to operator Φ_1 , the best estimate for the first excited state wave-functional. Following the same procedure we can also extract Φ_2, Φ_3, \dots .

In practice the wave-functionals Φ_0, Φ_1, \dots can be obtain just by a simple diagonalisation of the correlator matrix $C^{-1}(0)C(a)$. If $\vec{a}_i : i = 1, \dots, N_O$ are the eigenvectors of $C^{-1}(0)C(a)$, then the wave-functional of an excitation n would be given by:

$$\Phi_n(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_O} a_{nk} \phi_k(t). \quad (3.90)$$

Using this operator, we can calculate the correlator:

$$\langle \Phi_n^{\dagger}(t)\Phi_n(0) \rangle = \sum_{k,l=1}^{N_O} a_{nk}^* a_{nl} \langle \phi_k^{\dagger}(t)\phi_l(0) \rangle \equiv \sum_{k,l=1}^{N_O} a_{nk}^* a_{nl} C_{kl}(t). \quad (3.91)$$

To obtain the energies associated with the approximate wave-functionals $\langle \Phi_n^{\dagger}(t)\Phi_n(0) \rangle$, we perform effective energy estimations and fits according to Sections 3.5.1 and 3.5.2 with $\langle \Phi^{\dagger}(t)\Phi(0) \rangle \rightarrow \langle \Phi_n^{\dagger}(t)\Phi_n(0) \rangle$.

3.6 Statistical Issues

3.6.1 Jackknife error analysis

In the following paragraph we briefly discuss the jackknife analysis, a method which is commonly used for the estimation of the error (variance) of an observable such as the energy of an excitation of the flux tube. The correlator $C_{ij}(t)$ is a quantity that can be characterised as “primary”, because it is what we primarily calculate in a simulation. Using the correlation functions we can later estimate the mass which can be characterised as a “secondary” quantity.

Let us now consider a primary quantity X and a secondary which can be expressed as a function of the primary $f(X)$. The sample average of the measured values of the quantity X_i with $(i = 1, \dots, N_s)$ can be obtained by:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} X_i. \quad (3.92)$$

If there is a secondary quantity that needs to be estimated, the way of doing this is to adopt the following. Firstly, we calculate N_s jackknife averages $X_{(J)i}$ by omitting a single measurement from each sum over all the measurements:

$$X_{(J)s} \equiv \frac{1}{N_s - 1} \sum_{i \neq s} X_i. \quad (3.93)$$

We, therefore, redistribute the measurements into N_s “jackknife bins”. Typically for each string length we distribute our measurements into ~ 50 jackknife bins. Secondly, the corre-

sponding average of the secondary quantity can be obtained by:

$$\bar{f}(X) \equiv \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} f(X_{(J)i}), \quad (3.94)$$

with variance $\Delta(\bar{f}(X))$ given by:

$$\Delta(\bar{f}(X)) \equiv \sqrt{\frac{N_s - 1}{N_s} \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} (f(X_{(J)i}) - \bar{f}(X))^2}. \quad (3.95)$$

3.6.2 Bayesian Fits: Constrained Curve Fitting

Lattice calculations produce lots of numbers which should result to a physical conclusion, such as the calculation of an observable. Usually these numbers, or any other secondary quantity $\mathbf{A} \equiv \{A_1, \sigma_{A_1}, A_2, \sigma_{A_2}, \dots\}$ that derives from those, are expected to behave in some particular way that can be expressed by a function $f_n(\mathbf{u})$ on a number of arbitrary parameters denoted as $\mathbf{u} \equiv \{u_1, u_2, \dots\}$. This is highly significant since one could receive important information by fitting the curve $f_n(\mathbf{u})$ onto these parameters. In fact our work is entirely based on curve fits from which we obtain quantities such as the effective energies by fitting single exponentials or hyperbolic cosines and the string tension and empirical corrections by fitting the Equation (2.93).

According to least squares the favorable configuration of the fitting parameters would be the one that minimises χ^2 which can be defined as:

$$\chi^2(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_{n=1} \frac{(A_n - f_n(\mathbf{u}))^2}{\sigma_{A_n}^2}. \quad (3.96)$$

Therefore, one could perform a jackknife statistical analysis treating these favourable fitting parameters as secondary quantities as this is described in the previous section, and calculating their corresponding averages and variances; relying on the fact that the quantity \mathbf{A} is delivered in a large statistical sample.

However, it is not always possible to have large statistical samples on the quantity \mathbf{A} , and, therefore, a more sophisticated method has to be used. A ‘‘friendly’’ framework to this purpose can be obtain from exploiting Bayesian statistics. For more information on this see [93, 94]. According to Bayesian analysis and assuming that the distribution $P(\mathbf{u}) = e^{-\chi^2(\mathbf{u})/2}$ is approximately Gaussian, the mean value of a fitting parameter u_i can be derived by:

$$\langle u_i \rangle = \frac{\int d^n u u_i e^{-\chi^2(\mathbf{u})/2}}{\int d^n u e^{-\chi^2(\mathbf{u})/2}}, \quad (3.97)$$

with variance given by:

$$\Delta(u_i) = \sqrt{\frac{\int d^n u (u_i - \langle u_i \rangle)^2 e^{-\chi^2(\mathbf{u})/2}}{\int d^n u e^{-\chi^2(\mathbf{u})/2}}}. \quad (3.98)$$

Chapter 4

Construction of Operators

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter we present in detail the construction of the operators that have been used for the calculation of the $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ spectra in $D = 2 + 1$. In $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories the quantum numbers of interest in which our operators would be encoded are the parity P and the longitudinal momentum q ; thus, it is important to explain how one can build operators that carry these quantum numbers. We first discuss the smearing/blocking procedure, which provides a way to construct operators able to project onto the physical length scales of the system and to be smooth on these scales. In practice this procedure involves addition of $SU(N)$ matrices causing the loss of unitarity, therefore we spend some-time explaining how one could project an operator (before being traced) back to $SU(N)$. Finally, we show how our operators can be constructed in such a way so as to project onto the different quantum numbers and we present all the lattice paths used in the calculation.

4.2 Smearing/Blocking Procedure

In these lattice calculations, flux tube operators consist of linear combinations of path ordered colour singlet products of link variables, which wind around the compactified direction of our space-time lattice, creating Polyakov loops. Each link variable U corresponds to a “physical length” of one lattice spacing a . If this spacing is small then we would expect that a good operator which approximates a wave-functional for the light states has to be smooth on the associated physical length scales of the states under investigation, and simultaneously on the lattice spacing a . This has been sorted out in [95], according to which instead of using the original link matrices as the basic components of the operators, one can use combinations of these (by summing and multiplying); this is the basic idea. Two common variants¹ used for this purpose are smearing [96, 97] and blocking [95, 98]. The only link matrices involved in such products are space-like and therefore, the positivity of the correlation functions is preserved.

In the next paragraph the smearing algorithm is presented. The first part of the usual smearing algorithm sums up the shortest paths between nearest neighboring sites. In the case of $D = 2 + 1$ we have just three such paths, the link $U_\mu(\vec{x})$ and the “staples”, for example see Equation (4.1) and Figure 4.1. The contribution of these staples in the final operator

¹It has also been shown that in an accurate calculation of either a glueball or a flux tube state, these methods lead to a gain in computer time that can be several orders of magnitude.

can be adjusted using the relative weight p_a , which can in principle be chosen empirically. This parameter determines how fast the link field spreads outwards as the procedure of smearing is being iterated. If one chooses p_a to be small, then a lot of smearing steps will be needed to produce links projecting onto the physical lengths. This suggests that the iterative procedure would be very expensive, but conversely it leads to operators extending over the desired length scales with fine resolution. On the other hand, if p_a is chosen to be large, the result will be operators that extend over all length scales, very rapidly, thus gaining computing time. The best option would therefore be to choose an intermediary value for p_a of order $\mathcal{O}(1)$, so that the width of the superlink increases relatively the same with its length. If s denotes the smearing level of a link then in $D = 2 + 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} U_\mu^{s+1}(\vec{x}) &= U_\mu^s(\vec{x}) + p_a U_\nu^s(\vec{x}) U_\mu^s(\vec{x} + a\hat{\nu}) U_\nu^{s\dagger}(\vec{x} + a\hat{\mu}) \\ &\quad + p_a U_\nu^{s\dagger}(\vec{x} - a\hat{\nu}) U_\mu^s(\vec{x} - a\hat{\nu}) U_\nu^s(\vec{x} + a\hat{\mu}), \\ U_\mu^{s=0}(\vec{x}) &= U_\mu(\vec{x}) \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

with

$$U_\mu^{s+1}(\vec{x}) = \mathcal{U}\{U_\mu^{s+1}(\vec{x})\}, \tag{4.2}$$

where operation \mathcal{U} denotes the unitarisation operation which is described in Section 4.3. As it has already been mentioned in Section 4.1 the sum (4.1) causes loss of unitarity and, therefore, one tends to reimpose it before proceeding to measurements.

The next step of this algorithm would be to introduce the blocking procedure. With blocking, the basic degrees of freedom are now “superlinks” characterised by the additional index b . Each blocking step b is achieved by the path order multiplication of two smeared links aligned on the same direction and separated by a distance $a \cdot 2^{b-1}$. This can be materialised by the following routine, which incorporates both blocking and smearing procedures:

$$\begin{aligned} U_\mu^{b=1}(\vec{x}) &= U_\mu^{s=1}(\vec{x}), \\ U_\mu^{b=1,s}(\vec{x}) &= \mathcal{S}^s\{U_\mu^{b=1}(\vec{x})\}, \\ U_\mu^{b+1}(\vec{x}) &= U_\mu^{b,s}(\vec{x}) U_\mu^{b,s}(\vec{x} + 2^b \hat{\mu}), \end{aligned} \tag{4.3}$$

where \mathcal{S} denotes the smearing operation defined in Equations (4.1) and (4.2).

By iterating this procedure we ensure that the lattice spacing a would be small enough comparing to the physical length scales; this way we can probe throughout the interesting physics of the flux-tube, while the wave-functional has the right projection onto the physical length scales.

4.3 Unitarisation

To begin with, it is important to emphasise that there is not an *a priori* reason for a torelon operator to belong to the $SU(N)$ group, unless we want to probe the group-theoretical structure of bound states of $k = 1$ flux tubes, such as $k = 2$ fluxes. In practice, the projection of an operator onto $SU(N)$ can lead to a slight reduction of the overlaps, but usually these effects are negligible and can, therefore, be ignored. Thus, in the best case one may obtain overlaps that are as good as those that may be obtained with any other possible normalisation of the final form of the operators, and the importance of reimposing

Figure 4.1: A pictorialisation of the smearing procedure in $D = 2 + 1$. We add to the link $U_\mu^s(\vec{x})$ the two nearest parallel links going outwards along the lattice axes; these are called the staples. The contribution of the staple is adjusted by the weight p_a . The associated blocked lattice spacing a' is defined as $a' = 2^{b-1}a$ with b being the blocking level.

$SU(N)$ -arity should only be restricted to the group theoretical structure of k -strings.

Loss of unitarity is usually caused by summing up “primary” Wilson lines that are, presumably, given by path order products of links or by single links, in order to obtain a “secondary” Wilson line. This kind of effects rise in the contexts of “smearing” and “fattening”, since these are the only algorithmic procedures that involve summation of non-traced Wilson loops. Having set the problem, let us now see how we can resolve it. Let us say that we have an invertible complex $N \times N$ matrix² $\check{U} \in GL(N, \mathbb{C})$ that can be obtained by a function on $SU(N)$ matrices. Then the problem is simplified to finding a mapping that could take us from $GL(N, \mathbb{C})$ to $SU(N)$, namely $F(\check{U} \in GL(N, \mathbb{C})) \rightarrow U \in SU(N)$. This mapping should satisfy the following two conditions:

- Firstly, if \check{U} belongs to $SU(N)$ then $F(\check{U}) = \check{U}$. The unitarisation should, therefore, keep the matrix \check{U} unchanged.
- Secondly, the final unitary matrix should have the right transformation properties. Namely, for $G_1, G_2 \in SU(N)$ then, $F(G_1 \check{U} G_2^\dagger) = G_1 F(\check{U}) G_2^\dagger$.

A way to achieve the reunitarisation has been proposed in [99]. According to this, first we divide the matrix \check{U} by its determinant $\tilde{U} = \check{U}/\det\check{U}$. Then we factorise \tilde{U} into a positive definite Hermitian matrix H (on the right) times a unitary matrix U (on the left) such as $\tilde{U} = UH$. Under a gauge transformation $\tilde{U} \rightarrow G_1 \tilde{U} G_2^\dagger$ with $G_1, G_2 \in SU(N)$; by the uniqueness of the factorisation we know that $U \rightarrow G_1 U G_2^\dagger$ and $H \rightarrow G_2 H G_2^\dagger$. The uniqueness of the factorisation also suggests that $H = 1$ and $\tilde{U} = U$ if \tilde{U} is unitary. We can therefore convert \check{U} to U since both conditions are satisfied. In practice, firstly we calculate the positive definite Hermitian matrix $H = \tilde{U}^\dagger \tilde{U}$. Then we diagonalise H such as $H^2 E = E \Lambda$ with Λ being the diagonal matrix of eigenvalues and E is the orthonormalised unitary matrix of eigenvectors of the matrix H^2 . Finally, we obtain $U = \tilde{U} H^{-1}$ with $H^{-1} = E \Lambda^{-1/2} E^\dagger$.

The above procedure requires time-consuming operations and, hence, it is not favourable. One can instead use another approach, which has been systematically used by lattice gauge theorists and according to which the problem is simplified in finding a matrix $U \in SU(N)$ that maximises the expression:

$$\max_{U \in SU(N)} \text{ReTr}\{U^\dagger \check{U}\}. \quad (4.4)$$

²We note that if $N = 2$ then the problem of reunitarisation is trivial since a sum on matrices that belong to $SU(N)$ is proportional to an $SU(N)$ matrix.

This is equivalent to the use of Cabibbo and Marinari heat-bath algorithm at $\beta = \infty$. This procedure which is used in “colling” the lattice fields in order to calculate their topological charge [100], where the matrix U replaces the link being updated and \check{U} replaces the sum of the neighboring plaquettes. This procedure can be presented in the following steps:

- Firstly, we need to start from some initial value of U . We do so by orthonormalising either the columns or the rows of \check{U} according to Gram-Schmidt algorithm. We, therefore obtain a very first approximation³ to U .
- Using the notation of Section 3.4.2, the problem now is simplified to the “cooling” of an \mathcal{A} with probability distribution defined by the action:

$$\lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \beta S(AU) = \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\beta}{N} \text{Re}(\text{Tr} \mathcal{A} \mathcal{R}), \quad (4.5)$$

where \mathcal{R} is the 2×2 submatrix of the matrix $R = \check{U}^\dagger U$ embedded in an $N \times N$ matrix with the same block structure as A . So, the next step would be to obtain $R = \check{U}^\dagger U$.

- Then we extract a subgroup \mathcal{R} from R and perform a heat-bath update at $\beta = \infty$; this is explained in Section 3.4.3. After the matrix \mathcal{A} is obtained, it gets embedded into $A \in SU(N)$. Using this we update: $U \mapsto AU$.
- We perform the same for all $N(N-1)/2$ $SU(2)$ subgroups \mathcal{A}
- The same procedure can be repeated until the matrix U is completely “cooled”.

Finally to ensure $SU(N)$ -arity we send the resultant link matrix to a matrix whose determinant is set to unit. This can be achieved by the following routine:

$$U_{ij} \rightarrow U'_{ij}, \quad (4.6)$$

with

$$U'_{ij} = \frac{U_{ij}}{[\det U]^{\frac{1}{N}}}. \quad (4.7)$$

4.4 Construction of the operators

In general, torelon operators can be formed by path ordered multiplying the blocked/smeared link matrices around closed loops \mathcal{C} , which run along a spatial compactified direction. If the operator is named Φ , then it can read as:

$$\Phi(\mathcal{C}) = \sum_{\mathcal{C} \in \mathcal{C}} \prod_{l \in \mathcal{C}} U_l^b. \quad (4.8)$$

³This is just an approximation by means that it does not maintain exact gauge invariance, increasing slightly the statistical noise in the correlator calculations. A potential problem arises here, related to the fact that if one orthonormalises either the columns or the rows one by one, then the crude starting point for U will not be the same for its hermitian conjugate U^\dagger . This corresponds to a break of the rotational symmetry and, hence, it can cause uncertainties to accurate investigations of quantities that strictly depend upon it, such as the angular momentum. Nevertheless, this does not pose a “threat” given that after a few cooling iterations the resulting matrix loses all its memory on its initial value.

The collection of closed loops C can be chosen in such a way as to give the operator Φ the desired quantum numbers. In the case of $D = 2 + 1$ the use of closed loops, whose shape is the reflection of each other over the longitudinal plane, will define the parity content of the operators.

In $D = 3 + 1$ dimensions the flux tube states could be described by the lattice symmetry of rotations $C_{4\nu}$ about the principal tube axis. This symmetry consists of rotations of $\pi/2$ and their reflections on the plane defined by the two transverse directions. However, in $D = 2 + 1$ there are no rotations around this axis and, therefore, the symmetry of rotations reduces to reflections on the transverse line; in other words reflections over the plane defined by the longitudinal and temporal lattice directions (see Figure 4.4). We will be referring to this symmetry as the two dimensional parity P .

At this point we should mention that there is also charge conjugation C . This operator changes the direction of the arrow such as $l_C \rightarrow l_C^\dagger$. This indicates that $\text{Re}\Phi(C)$ is $C = +$ and $\text{Im}\Phi(C)$ is $C = -$. Under the centre transformation, $l_C \rightarrow z l_C$ and $l_C^\dagger \rightarrow z^\dagger l_C^\dagger$ and, therefore, there is in general zero overlap between l_C and l_C^\dagger . According to this the $C = +$ and $C = -$ sectors are degenerate and the label C is then uninteresting. However, we must be careful since this is not the case when $k = N/2$. In this case there can be mixing between the two $C = \pm$ sectors and they need not be degenerate. In our calculation this occurs for $k = 2$ in $SU(4)$. However, for $SU(4)$ $\text{Im}\Phi_{k=2A}(C) \equiv 0$. To the extent that there is a $k = 2A$ sector of states we will only, therefore, have $C = +$ therein. For $k = 2S$ controversially, $C = \pm$ can be a useful label in $SU(4)$. Nonetheless what we obtained is that for $k = 2S$ in $SU(4)$ $C = +$ and $C = -$ sectors are, within the errors, approximately degenerate and the label C is then uninteresting.

Hence, in order to construct Polyakov lines of definite parity P , one has first to choose a lattice path \mathcal{C}_i , which in principle can be thought of as a straight line running along the compactified dimension $\hat{\mu}$ of length L_\parallel with a transverse deformation. Secondly, the closed loop has to be expressed in terms of link matrices; starting from an initial (and final at the same time) lattice point, let us say, from \vec{x} we path ordered multiply the link variables that “live” along the closed loop at certain blocking level⁴ b ending up having an operator $\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +) \in SU(N)$ where the sign (+) denotes that this corresponds to the original lattice path and not to its reflection denoted by (-). Equivalently, we do the same for the associated reflection of the lattice path \mathcal{C}_i . This leads to the operator $\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -) \in SU(N)$. Using this notation we demonstrate how the $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ operators are built.

1. Operators for $k = 1$:

The construction of $k = 1$ Polyakov lines with definite parity P can be achieved by adding (subtracting) the reflection of a single winding Polyakov line with a transverse deformation over the longitudinal plane, to itself in order to obtain $P = +(-)$. This can be encoded as:

$$\Phi_{i,\pm}^b(\vec{x}) = \text{Tr}\{\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +)\} \pm \text{Tr}\{\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -)\}. \quad (4.9)$$

An example of this operator, using the square pulse-like deformation can be visualised as:

$$\Phi_{k=1}^{P=\pm} = \text{Tr} \{ \text{—} \square \text{—} \} \pm \text{Tr} \{ \text{—} \square \text{—} \}. \quad (4.10)$$

⁴We can also combine link matrices of different blocking levels (see Section A).

Figure 4.2: The parity plane or longitudinal plane (plane in blue) is defined by the longitudinal and temporal lattice directions as shown in the figure. The figure also pictorialises the parity transformation of the pulse like operator \mathcal{C}_2 which is presented in Table 4.1 and Equation (A.2).

2. First set of $k = 2$ operators:

The first set of $k = 2$ operators is a generalisation of the operator $\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}\}^2$. Firstly we construct a $k = 1$ Polyakov line with a transverse deformation that winds once around the toroidally compactified dimension and we insert it into the operation $\text{Tr}\{\dots\}^2$. Secondly, we construct the associated reflection of the Polyakov line, we insert it in the same operation $\text{Tr}\{\dots\}^2$ and finally we add (subtract) it from the operation described in the previous line. This procedure can be encoded as:

$$\Phi_{i,\pm}^b(\vec{x}) = \text{Tr}\{\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +)\}^2 \pm \text{Tr}\{\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -)\}^2. \quad (4.11)$$

An example of this operator using once more the square pulse-like deformation is given by:

$$\Phi_{k=2}^{P=\pm} = \text{Tr} \{ \text{—} \square \text{—} \}^2 \pm \text{Tr} \{ \text{—} \square \text{—} \}^2. \quad (4.12)$$

3. Second set of $k = 2$ operators:

The second set of $k = 2$ operators that corresponds to a generalisation of the operators $\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}^2\}$, can be constructed using the procedure for the construction of the first set with the only difference now being that the operation is $\text{Tr}\{(\dots)^2\}$ than $\text{Tr}\{\dots\}^2$. The operators can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{i,\pm}^b(\vec{x}) &= \text{Tr}\{\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +)\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +)\} \\ &\pm \text{Tr}\{\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -)\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -)\}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

and an example is the following:

$$\Phi_{k=2}^{P=\pm} = \text{Tr} \{ \text{—} \square \text{—} \cdot \text{—} \square \text{—} \} \pm \text{Tr} \{ \text{—} \square \text{—} \cdot \text{—} \square \text{—} \}. \quad (4.14)$$

4. Third set of $k = 2$ operators expected to project onto $w = 2$ unbound states:

As mentioned in Section 1.3.3, an attempt to test whether the $k = 2$ closed flux tube

spectrum includes unbound $w = 2$ states has also been conducted. These states are expected to appear in the spectrum if and only if the appropriate operators are used. They are also expected to be described by frequencies lower than those describing the $k = 2$ bound states. Although some $k = 2$ operators look as if they wind twice around the torus (operators of type $\text{Tr}l_{\mathcal{C}}^2$), the way they had been constructed, prohibits the projection onto states with lower frequencies since each Polyakov loop starts and ends at the same lattice point within one lattice size. To overcome this we construct Polyakov lines that wind twice around the torus with transverse deformations at the joint of the two lattices or equivalently operators with periodicity $2L_{\parallel}$ rather than L_{\parallel} . These operators can be expressed as:

$$\Phi_{i,\pm}^b(\vec{x}) = \text{Tr}\{\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_i, 2 \cdot L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +)\} \pm \text{Tr}\{\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_i, 2 \cdot L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -)\}. \quad (4.15)$$

An example of this operator is demonstrated in Equation (4.16).

$$\Phi_{w=2}^{P=\pm} = \text{Tr} \{ \text{---} \square \text{---} \} \pm \text{Tr} \{ \text{---} \square \text{---} \}. \quad (4.16)$$

It is important to be noted that the new operators in Equation (4.15) transform the same under the centre of the group Z_N as the other $k = 2$ operators i.e $\Phi_{w=2} = \text{Tr}(l_{\mathcal{C}}l'_{\mathcal{C}})$. So these new “unbound” operators have N -ality $k = 2$ and will, therefore, contribute to an extended $k = 2$ spectrum.

5. Projection onto the symmetric and antisymmetric $k = 2$ representations:

To single-out the irreducible representations which describe the theory, we perform antisymmetrisation and symmetrisation according to the relevant Young-tableau decomposition⁵ of $k = 2$ fundamental colour sources:

$$\square \otimes \square = \square \oplus \square. \quad (4.19)$$

The resulting operators will be of the type: $1/2[\text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}\}^2 \pm \text{Tr}\{l_{\mathcal{C}}^2\}]$, where $+(-)$ for symmetric (antisymmetric) representation. Once more we need to introduce transverse deformations, in order to project onto the non-trivial irreducible representations that characterise the closed flux tube in $D = 2 + 1$. Examples of such operators are demonstrated in Equations (4.20) and (4.22) below.

⁵If U is an $SU(N)$ matrix implementing the transformation $q \xrightarrow{SU(N)} U_j^i q^j$, where q^i ($i = 1, \dots, N$) is a colour source transforming in the fundamental representation of $SU(N)$, then the tensor product of the two quarks gives the following antisymmetric (A_{lm}^{ij}) and symmetric (B_{lm}^{ij}) tensors:

$$A_{lm}^{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(U_l^i U_m^j - U_l^j U_m^i), \quad B_{lm}^{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(U_l^i U_m^j + U_l^j U_m^i). \quad (4.17)$$

By tracing them one obtains,

$$\text{Tr}A = \frac{1}{2}(\{\text{Tr}U\}^2 - \text{Tr}U^2), \quad \text{Tr}B = \frac{1}{2}(\{\text{Tr}U\}^2 + \text{Tr}U^2). \quad (4.18)$$

(a) *Operators projecting onto the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation:*

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_{i,\pm}^b(\vec{x}) &= \frac{1}{2}[\text{Tr}\{\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +)\}^2 - \text{Tr}\{\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +)\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +)\}] \\ &\pm \frac{1}{2}[\text{Tr}\{\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -)\}^2 - \text{Tr}\{\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -)\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -)\}],\end{aligned}\quad (4.20)$$

with an example:

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_{k=2A}^{P=\pm} &= \frac{1}{2}[\text{Tr}\{ \text{---} \}^2 - \text{Tr}\{ \text{---} \cdot \text{---} \}] \\ &\pm \frac{1}{2}[\text{Tr}\{ \text{---} \}^2 - \text{Tr}\{ \text{---} \cdot \text{---} \}].\end{aligned}\quad (4.21)$$

(b) *Operators projecting onto the $k = 2$ symmetric representation:*

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_{i,\pm}^b(\vec{x}) &= \frac{1}{2}[\text{Tr}\{\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +)\}^2 + \text{Tr}\{\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +)\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +)\}] \\ &\pm \frac{1}{2}[\text{Tr}\{\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -)\}^2 + \text{Tr}\{\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -)\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_i, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -)\}],\end{aligned}\quad (4.22)$$

with an example:

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_{k=2S}^{P=\pm} &= \frac{1}{2}[\text{Tr}\{ \text{---} \}^2 + \text{Tr}\{ \text{---} \cdot \text{---} \}] \\ &\pm \frac{1}{2}[\text{Tr}\{ \text{---} \}^2 + \text{Tr}\{ \text{---} \cdot \text{---} \}].\end{aligned}\quad (4.23)$$

4.5 Giving Tolelons Momentum

In order to project onto zero-momentum⁶ transverse to the flux tube, let us say $p_\perp = 0$, we need to add all x_\perp translations of our basic operator $\Phi_{i,\pm}^b(\vec{x})$. Nevertheless, one can impose transverse momentum $p_\perp \neq 0$ by translating the loop by x_\perp , multiplying by a factor $\exp\{ip_\perp x_\perp\}$ and summing over all such translations. Equivalently, if we translate the loop by x_\parallel , multiply it by $\exp\{ip_\parallel x_\parallel\}$, and sum all over the longitudinal lattice sites, we can create an operator with longitudinal momentum p_\parallel .

Therefore the final form of our flux tube operator will be given by:

$$\Phi_{i,\pm}^b(p_\parallel, p_\perp) = \frac{1}{L_\parallel L_\perp} \sum_{\vec{x}} \Phi_{i,\pm}^b(\vec{x}) e^{ip_\parallel x_\parallel + ip_\perp x_\perp}, \quad (4.24)$$

where $p_\parallel = 2\pi q/L_\parallel$ with $q = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$ and $p_\perp = 0$.

4.6 Fattening

So far it has been assumed that the path order product of link matrices at blocking level b along the path \mathcal{C}_i leads to an operator with associated length equal to the longitudinal size

⁶We do not consider $p_\perp \neq 0$ due to the facts that previous calculations have shown that for the range of lattice spacings we consider, the continuum energy-momentum dispersion relation is accurately satisfied and moreover it is not involved in any way in the effective string theory model, suggesting that one could not learn anything new by probing the sector of non-zero transverse momentum.

of the lattice L_{\parallel} . In other words the longitudinal lattice size could be fitted exactly by a sequence of segments of associated length $a \cdot 2^{b-1}$. In practice this is not always the case, and can be satisfied only if:

$$L_{\parallel} - 2^{b-1} \times \text{Int} \left[\frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}} \right] = 0, \quad (L_{\parallel} \in \mathbb{N}_1). \quad (4.25)$$

However, this should not be a problem since in a lattice which cannot be entirely fitted with link variables of a certain blocking level b the remaining segment can be completed by links of smaller blocking levels. The need of preserving the “spreading” of the operators outwards requires the “fattening” of the matrices that will fill the rest of the lattice. In order to achieve this, each one of the link matrices composing the path order product which fits this segment receives such “staples”, as those introduced in Section 4.2 with amplitude formed by link matrices at blocking level b (as the rest of the operator).

Expressing this algorithmically, the remaining part of an operator that initiates from \vec{x} and “lives” at blocking level b , can be “filled” in by $U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_i, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b)$ which is obtained by iterating the following routine from $i = b - 1$ to $i = 1$.

$$\begin{aligned} L_x^{i=b} &= L_{\parallel}, \\ L_x^i &= L_x^{i+1} - 2^i \times \text{Int} \left[\frac{L_x^{i+1}}{2^i} \right] \quad \text{only if } L_x^{i+1} > 0, \\ \vec{x}_{i=b} &= \vec{x}, \\ \vec{x}_i &= \vec{x}_{i+1} + a \cdot 2^i \text{Int} \left[\frac{L_x^{i+1}}{2^i} \right] \hat{\mu}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.26)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} U_{F\mu}^i(\vec{x}_i) &= \prod_{j=1}^{\text{Int} \left[\frac{L_x^i}{2^{i-1}} \right]} \left[U_{\mu}^i(\vec{x}_i + a \cdot 2^{i-1}(j-1)\hat{\mu}) \right. \\ &+ U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x}_i + a2^{i-1}(j-1)\hat{\mu}) U_{\mu}^i(\vec{x}_i + a(2^{b-1}\hat{\nu} + 2^{i-1}(j-1)\hat{\mu})) U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x}_i + a2^{i-1}j\hat{\mu}) \\ &+ U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x}_i + a(2^{i-1}(j-1)\hat{\mu} - 2^{b-1}\hat{\nu})) U_{\mu}^i(\vec{x}_i + a(2^{i-1}(j-1)\hat{\mu} - 2^{b-1}\hat{\nu})) \\ &\left. \times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x}_i + a2^{i-1}(j-1)\hat{\mu}) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.27)$$

After performing the iteration, the final fattened operator can be obtained as:

$$U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_i, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b) = \mathcal{U} \left[\prod_{i=b-1}^1 U_{F\mu}^i(\vec{x}_i) \right], \quad (4.28)$$

since unitarity is lost when link matrices are summed up.

4.7 Lattice Paths

In this subsection we present the different operators that have been used to perform the $D = 2 + 1$ calculations. Here we pictorialise the lattice paths. Complementarily and for

Chapter 5

The spectrum of closed fundamental flux tubes

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter we present a study on the closed-flux tube spectrum of $SU(N)$ gauge theory in the fundamental representation of colour in $D = 2 + 1$. We do so for $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$ and $\beta = 40$, $SU(4)$ at $\beta = 50$, $SU(5)$ at $\beta = 80$ and $SU(6)$ at $\beta = 90$. For each one of the commented gauge groups, we calculated the energy levels for a number $\sim \mathcal{O}(10)$ of the low-lying states with non-trivial quantum numbers $P = \pm$ and $q = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. As the project progressed calculation needs led us to project onto different values of the longitudinal momentum $2\pi q/l$, for each gauge group. More precisely, for $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$ we projected onto $P = \pm$ and $q = 0, 1, 2$, for $\beta = 40$ onto $P = \pm$ and $q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 8$, for $SU(6)$ at $\beta = 90$ onto $P = \pm$ at $q = 0, 1, 2$ and finally, for $SU(4)$ and $SU(5)$, onto $P = \pm$ and $q = 0$. A fit to the ground state for $P = +$ and $q = 0$ determines the value of the string tension in lattice units i.e. $a^2\sigma_f$. We compare these results to the theoretical predictions, by applying the estimate value for the string tension.

Briefly, some of the most important results obtained in the calculation of the $k = 1$ spectrum are the following. We find that our results for the ground $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ state are very well approximated by the $D = 2 + 1$ Nambu-Goto predictions even for a short string whose length is close to the deconfining transition l_c below which the flux tube dissolves. For the excited states, we obtain that at moderate string lengths, they exhibit a degeneracy pattern according to an effective bosonic string theory such as Nambu-Goto. Additionally, for the excitation spectrum we observe significant deviations from the Nambu-Goto predictions only for very short strings, that decrease rapidly as the length of the string increases. Remarkably, Nambu-Goto provides a much better description of our results than any other effective string theoretical prediction [15, 21, 16, 18, 20].

The structure of this chapter is the following: In the next section we explain the motivations that led to the work presented in this chapter. Consequently, we explain the lattice calculation commenting on the systematics and the variational calculation, with which we achieved the extraction of the excitation spectrum of the closed fundamental flux tube. Finally, we present the results and we conclude.

5.2 Motivation

Recent results on the lattice [2, 39, 40] showed that the ground state of a fundamental closed flux tube can be accurately described by the free Nambu-Goto string on a flat space-time with almost negligible corrections down to the shortest flux tube lengths. In fact, one would expect that a fundamental flux tube has an effective string theoretical description at large distances. As it turns out, not only this expectation occurs, but, if this effective string theory is the Nambu-Goto, the agreement stretches down to flux tube lengths $l \simeq 1.5/\sqrt{\sigma_f}$ that are comparable to the deconfining length $l_c = 1/T_c$ and the width of the flux! This provides important information about the dynamics of the ground state of a closed flux tube which apparently can be denoted as $|0\rangle$.

This astonishing agreement was obtained in lattice calculations of correlators of operators, that involve sums of path ordered products of link matrices that live along the simple line curve at several blocking levels. The simple line operator (Equation (A.1) and picture \mathcal{C}_1 in Table 4.1) transforms trivially under the action of the parity P . In addition, it is translationally invariant along the longitudinal direction, thus forbidding the projection onto the non-zero longitudinal momentum $q \neq 0$ sector of states. Hence, the ground state of the spectrum appears as the ground state of the configuration of quantum numbers $\{P = +, q = 0\}$. Therefore, the phonon structure of this state is trivial and cannot deliver important information towards the excitation spectrum of the closed fundamental flux tube.

In sum, we could safely say that the ground state provides only a small portion of information about the nature of the fundamental flux tube and consequently about its effective string theoretical description. So, it is important to perform accurate calculations on the energy levels for at least a few excited states. Such a task is not easy in a lattice calculation, where one can obtain accurate energies only for states with very high overlaps onto the wave-functionals of the basis being used.

Using the simple line operator at several blocking levels as a basis we can additionally project, at most, onto the first excited state of the sector $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ with moderate overlaps compared to those obtained for the ground state. However, the first excited state $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ cannot provide significant information on the questions we want to address. This is because it falls onto the special sector of states described by the same number of left- and right-moving phonon contributions $N_L = N_R$ driven by the zero projection onto the longitudinal momentum. According to Nambu-Goto model and more specifically to the level matching constrain $N_L - N_R = qw$, the quantised longitudinal momentum has a direct impact on the phonon structure of the states. This obstacle can be overcome by constructing operators with longitudinal momentum encoded within. In general, there is a need of a basis able to project onto $P = \pm$ and non-zero values of the longitudinal momentum $2\pi q/l; q = 1, 2, \dots$ states with large enough overlaps.

We face this challenge using a large $\sim \mathcal{O}(100)$ number of operators Φ_i , which form the basis and were constructed in such a way so as to project onto states with $P = \pm$ and $q = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. This is applicable only if the chosen lattice paths that define the shape of the constituents of the operators have transverse deformations. Using a Monte-Carlo simulation, we calculate the correlator $C_{ij}(t) = \langle \Phi_i^\dagger(t) \Phi_j(0) \rangle$ for each diverse configuration of quantum numbers $\{P, q\}$ and by applying the variational calculation on this we extract the associated low-lying spectrum.

5.3 Lattice Calculation

Although the lattice calculation was described in detail at Section 3.4.5, here the adopted methodology is briefly explained. The Yang-Mills $SU(N)$ gauge theory is formulated on a cubic Euclidean space time lattice with volume $L_{\parallel} \times L_{\perp} \times L_T$ and lattice spacing a . Periodic boundary conditions are imposed along all directions. The 2+1 dimensional theory does not have a physical analog and, therefore, there is not much point in giving physical units to the lattice spacing a . Thus, it would be much more sensible to work in dimensionless units, such as $E/\sqrt{\sigma_f}$ for the energy and $l\sqrt{\sigma_f}$ for the flux tube length. However, if we wish to impose “physical” units, we can extract the fundamental string tension in lattice units $a^2\sigma_f$. For example we could fit the large distance linearly rising expression $aE(L_{\parallel}) \stackrel{L_{\parallel} \rightarrow \infty}{=} a^2\sigma_f L_{\parallel}$, and then use the estimated value for the string tension $\sqrt{\sigma_f} = 440(30)$ MeV [101] to calculate the lattice spacing.

The basic degrees of freedom are $SU(N)$ matrices U_l aligned with the straight line joints connecting two nearest neighboring sites. The quantisation of the theory is achieved by inserting the Wilson action presented in Equation (3.42) in the probability distribution of the Feynman path integral, in the way explained in Chapter 3. Our goal was accomplished by calculating correlation functions of operators Φ_i constructed in such a way so as to project onto particular configurations of the quantum numbers $\{P, q\}$, such as:

$$\langle \Phi_i^\dagger(t)\Phi_j(0) \rangle = \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}(\beta)} \int \prod_l dU_l \Phi_i^\dagger(U(t))\Phi_j(U(0)) e^{-\beta \sum_p \{1 - \frac{1}{N} \text{ReTr} U_p\}}, \quad (5.1)$$

with partition function:

$$\mathcal{Z}(\beta) = \int \prod_l dU_l e^{-\beta \sum_p \{1 - \frac{1}{N} \text{ReTr} U_p\}}, \quad (5.2)$$

where U_p is the plaquette defined in Equation (3.36) and labelled by p that stands for “ p =plaquette” as in Equation (3.42).

A lattice calculation provides results obtained at a certain ultraviolet cutoff a and, therefore, one should be able to tend to the continuum limit $a \rightarrow 0$, in order to obtain the “real” physics of a problem. In Chapter 3 we mentioned that, in order to get the correct continuum limit, β in $D = 2 + 1$ has to be equal to $\beta = 2N/ag^2$ according to which the coupling g^2 has dimensions of [mass]. So, the continuum limit can be approached by sending $\beta \rightarrow \infty$. Since this calculation involves a large number of operators and relatively high accuracy, it demanded too much computational time. Given that our computational resources were limited, the possibility of extrapolating to the continuum by performing calculations for a significantly large number of different lattice spacings a was aborted. Hence, we attempted to check whether our results alter significantly by decreasing the lattice spacing, let us say, by performing the same calculation at half the lattice spacing for the smallest value of N . It would be helpful to mention that by decreasing the lattice spacing by a factor of 1/2 we need to increase all the lattice sizes by a factor of ~ 2 in order to keep the finite volume effects at the same level of suppression. This means that at least the update process slows down by a factor of ~ 8 , while the time increase in the measuring process cannot be quantitatively defined¹ exactly. The value of β that corresponds to a finer

¹For a taster of how the increase of the lattice sizes influences the time consumption, a brief description is provided below. It is obvious that the number of the components of each operator at each time slice, which

lattice spacing can be taken from previous work or it can be obtained by applying the results of the recent work [39], according to which we can work out the empirical extrapolation in the continuum provided by the authors in order to obtain an estimate for the value of β .

Simultaneously, we would like to perform calculations at large values of N , where effects such as glueball-string coupling and string/anti-string coupling are suppressed. It would be ideal to extrapolate in the large- N limit, a procedure which was unrealistic since the computing time increases due to the rise of the number of matrix elements. If we perform a calculation at, let us say $N = N_1$, and then by keeping the lattice spacing fixed we move to a larger number of colour, let us say $N = N_2$, then all the processes that involve matrix multiplications slow down by a factor of $\sim N_2^3/N_1^3$. This indicates that by moving from $N = 3$ to $N = 6$ the computational time increases by a factor of ~ 8 . To see roughly how β alters as we increase N , we must use the 't Hooft coupling $\lambda = g^2 N$, which is kept fixed in the definition of β ; $\beta = 2N^2/a\lambda$ up to $\mathcal{O}(1/N^2)$ corrections. Once more, the value of β for the calculation at $N = 6$ was obtained from previous projects, but it could have also been estimated by using the extrapolation in the large- N limit provided in [39].

We calculated the spectra of a fundamental flux tube winding around the compactified longitudinal directions and range in dimensionless length $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \in [1.37, 5.56]$. Therefore the length of the flux tube is not much larger than its width. This suggests that the glueelectric flux forms a “tube” rather than a thin string. For comparison, the minimum length below which the flux tube dissolves is according to [102, 103]:

$$l_c = \frac{1}{T_c} \simeq \begin{cases} 5.9a & : SU(3), \beta = 21 \\ 11.5a & : SU(3), \beta = 40 \\ 6.3a & : SU(6), \beta = 90 \end{cases} \quad (5.4)$$

In the three Tables 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3, we present the lattices and the total number of Monte-Carlo sweeps that were used. The analogous information on $SU(4)$ and $SU(5)$ shall be found in Chapter 6.

5.4 Systematics

The control of the systematic errors in a lattice calculation is a task of high importance, since such errors would lead to incorrect results and consequently to wrong conclusions. An effort was, therefore, made to minimise such effects. Let us see what the main sources of the systematics are:

1. Finite transverse size effect, a finite volume effect caused by short transverse sizes L_\perp .

contribute to the transverse translation invariance, and the impose of longitudinal momentum increases by a factor of 4. It is also obvious that by increasing the length of the flux tube we also increase the maximum allowed blocking level by one ($b \rightarrow b+1$); this will also contribute, albeit minimally, to the time consumption. Concerning the measuring process that involves wave operators, apart from the latter contributions, there is an additional contribution, reflecting the dependence of the number of operators upon the longitudinal and transverse sizes of the lattice given by the formula:

$$\# \text{ of wave operators} = \# \left\{ \sum_i^b \text{Int}\{L_\parallel/2^i\} \times \text{Int}\{L_\perp/2^i\} \right\}. \quad (5.3)$$

The above formula shows that by doubling the sizes of the lattice the number of wave operators increases by a factor of ~ 4 . Additionally, the number of matrix multiplications also alters.

2. Finite temporal extent effect, a finite volume effect caused by short temporal sizes L_T .
3. Contributions coming from the back of the torus, a periodicity effect, which is caused by imposing periodic boundary conditions, as explained in Section 3.5.2 and visualised in Figure 3.2.
4. Calculation of massive states the correlators of which disappear in noise after a very few lattice temporal intervals.
5. A systematic error arising from the fact that a trial wave-functional may have a non-zero overlap onto lighter eigenstates.
6. Variational technique repulsion, in the sense that two or more nearly-degenerate states, that in an ideal calculation would be equal within their errors, may experience an artificial level of repulsion driven by finite statistical fluctuations.
7. Finiteness of the variational basis.

Having described the problems, let us now see how we attempted to attack them. The transverse size effect can be easily controlled by choosing a transverse size large enough so such effects become negligible. This was obtained numerically in the sense that we kept performing calculations on the ground state for the same longitudinal L_{\parallel} and different increasing transverse L_{\perp} sizes, until we obtained an unchangable ground state energy. In practice this has not been performed in this calculation, but it had been performed by Barak and Teper in a previous calculation [39], in which one of the goals was the suppression of the systematics. The transverse sizes that were used in our calculation can be found in Tables 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3.

In a similar way, we can resolve the problem of the finite temporal extent effect by selecting large enough temporal sizes. This could also be achieved using the same investigation process as that for the transverse size effect. The temporal sizes used in the calculation can be found in Tables 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3.

In fact, there is no need to worry about the temporal lattice size effect, since this has to be adjusted at large values for a much more significant effect, namely the contribution coming from the “back” of the torus. As mentioned before, we can get rid of these artifacts by choosing a large enough temporal extent and by using the fitting ansatz:

$$C(t) = A \left(e^{-E_0 t} + e^{-E_0(T-t)} \right), \quad (5.5)$$

rather than just the simple exponential:

$$C(t) = A e^{-E_0 t}, \quad (5.6)$$

to fit the asymptotic behaviour for the best estimate correlator of the ground state. Equation (5.5) can be alternatively used to give a rough estimate for the minimum temporal size such that the single exponential could still be used as a good fitting ansatz; this can be achieved by choosing T such as $e^{-E_0(T-t)} \ll e^{-E_0 t}$.

The next source of systematics is an obstacle we can barely deal with and hence shall live with, bearing in mind that this could appear at some point. As a matter of fact it does! Imagine that we want to calculate the ground state E_0 by performing a fit with either a

single exponential (5.6) or a hyperbolic cosine (5.5) to $C(t)$ for $t \geq t_1$ with t_1 being the lowest value of t for which we obtain an acceptable fit (good χ^2). The error of the $C(t)$ is more or less independent of t , while the signal decreases at least exponentially with t . This indicates that the error/signal ratio also increases almost exponentially with t . Therefore, we can only hope to obtain E_0 with good accuracy if the corresponding ground state dominates $C(t)$ at small values of t . Thus, if aE_0 is small enough such as the ratio error/signal is small for a range of $t \geq t_1$, then the correlator on the ground state could be successfully fitted by a single exponential/hyperbolic cosine. However, if the aE_0 is too large that this range is small, then this evidence does not anymore occur. We will, therefore, use a single exponential/hyperbolic cosine fit over a range of time intervals t , where the contributions coming from higher excited states may still be significant. This might push the estimation of aE_0 up a bit. This is an important systematic error that will be visible when considering very long and highly excited flux tubes. This cannot be exactly resolved, but we can at least try to improve the results by minimising such effects. We, therefore, attempted to build operators that dominate the asymptotic decaying behaviour of $C(t)$ at small values of t , let us say for $t_1 = a, 2a, 3a$. This can be achieved using the smearing/blocking techniques described in Section 4.2. To this purpose we could also try to increase the number of statistics; in other words to perform more Monte-Carlo sweeps, in order to decrease the error/signal ratio. This is a task that is usually forbidden by time limitations since in order to decrease the error by a factor of ~ 10 , we need to increase the computing time by a factor of ~ 100 . The number of Monte-Carlo sweeps used in the calculation is presented in Tables 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3. Another possibility, is to use more than one exponential/hyperbolic cosine for the fits, a procedure that presupposes a large statistical sample of measurements so that it could lead to accurately extracted fitting parameters; this tasks also faces the same time limitations as the previous one.

According to the fifth source of error, there may exist states the best trial wavefunctionals Φ_i of which have non-zero overlaps onto lighter eigenstates $\Psi_j; j < i$, such as $|\langle \Psi_j^\dagger(0)\Phi_i(0) \rangle|^2 \neq 0$. If this overlap is small then it is only at large time intervals t that the correlator $\langle \Phi_i^\dagger(t)\Phi_i(0) \rangle$ will behave like $\sim e^{-E_j t}$, while there exists an intermediate range of t , where the correlator will behave as $\sim e^{-E_i t}$. Therefore the best estimate value of E_i can be extracted by fitting the correlator and performing an effective energy investigation only at this intermediate range of time. However, as this overlap becomes more significant, the ambiguity in extracting E_i increases.

The sixth source of error can hardly be controlled, because it takes place in a sector of the data analysis which goes far beyond our control. The variational technique may create this artificial energy level repulsion for nearly degenerate states within their errors, this can be attacked only by providing the variational calculation with enough statistics, so that the two nearly degenerate states within the errors have their errors decreased to a level where they are not degenerate anymore.

Finally the seventh source of error can not completely disappear, but it can be improved by providing more information on the variational basis. This can be achieved only by considering more smeared/blocked operators Φ_i in the variational basis. The variational calculation is the topic of discussion in the next section, thus we shall not bother with explaining the details here.

String Length	Lattice Volume	Monte-Carlo Sweeps
8	$8 \times 32 \times 62$	500000
10	$10 \times 32 \times 60$	500000
12	$12 \times 28 \times 24$	500000
14	$14 \times 18 \times 24$	500000
16	$16 \times 20 \times 24$	500000
18	$18 \times 20 \times 24$	500000
20	$20 \times 22 \times 24$	500000
22	$22 \times 22 \times 22$	500000
24	$24 \times 24 \times 24$	500000
26	$26 \times 26 \times 26$	500000
32	$32 \times 40 \times 48$	450000

Table 5.1: The lattice volumes and the number of Monte-Carlo sweeps that have been used for the calculation of the $k = 1$ spectrum for $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$.

String Length	Lattice Volume	Monte-Carlo Sweeps
16	$16 \times 64 \times 124$	500000
20	$20 \times 64 \times 120$	500000
24	$24 \times 56 \times 48$	500000
28	$28 \times 40 \times 48$	500000
32	$32 \times 40 \times 48$	500000
36	$36 \times 40 \times 48$	500000

Table 5.2: The lattice Volumes and the number of Monte-Carlo sweeps that have been used for the calculation of the $k = 1$ spectrum for $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 40$.

5.5 Variational Calculation

Rather than re-discussing the concept of the variational calculation, which can be found in Section 3.5.3, here we deal with the implementation of this in the calculation of the closed fundamental flux tube spectrum.

In order to calculate the excitation spectrum as well as the ground states, we carried out a variational calculation. The operators which form the bases should reflect the physics of the flux tube. Therefore, let us see what one may expect to observe within the spectrum of the fundamental closed flux tube:

1. Firstly we expect to observe string-like states, driven by the massless “phonon” fluctuations along the string and having an asymptotic large- l behaviour of $\lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} E_n / \sigma_f l = 1, \forall n : 0, 1, 2, \dots$. These states are to be compared to the effective string theoretical models.
2. Secondly, we might also observe massive states that can be thought of as bindings between a string-like state and a glueball. If these “artificial” states really exist they should only appear for the lowest values of N and only if their resonance amplitudes are high enough since they should vanish as we tend to the $N \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, we should be aware of such states in calculations of low N gauge groups.
3. Thirdly, although they have not showed up yet, there might be stringy massive states

String Length	Lattice Volume	Monte-Carlo Sweeps
8	$8 \times 32 \times 62$	500000
10	$10 \times 32 \times 60$	500000
12	$12 \times 28 \times 24$	500000
14	$14 \times 32 \times 32$	500000
16	$16 \times 20 \times 24$	500000
18	$18 \times 20 \times 24$	500000
20	$20 \times 22 \times 24$	500000
22	$22 \times 22 \times 22$	500000
24	$24 \times 24 \times 24$	500000

Table 5.3: The lattice volumes and the number of Monte-Carlo sweeps that have been used for the calculation of the $k = 1$ spectrum for $SU(6)$ at $\beta = 90$.

such as brether modes, which reflect the non-trivial structure of the effective string theory. Nevertheless, due to the absence of a concrete prediction of such states, their identification is not a straightforward task.

Our expectations should determine how our operators are built. It is clear that these three cases involve at least string-like degrees of freedom and consequently they are expected to appear in our spectrum. The latter should incorporate the quantum numbers corresponding to the irreducible representations of the orthogonal group of rotations $SO(D - 2)$, which at $D = 2 + 1$ can be re-expressed as the transverse parity with eigenvalues $P = \pm$. This suggests that our operators and consequently the best approximate wave-functionals should transform irreducibly under parity transformations with eigenvalues $P = \pm$. In addition, since the structure of some of our expectations depends on the quantised longitudinal momentum $p_{\parallel} = 2\pi q/aL_{\parallel}$, we construct the operators in such a way so as to project onto eigenstates of longitudinal momentum. For example, see Equation (4.24). This can be possible only by introducing transverse deformations on the straight line operator, as explained several times in this thesis.

But what should the shape of these deformations be? There is no reason to believe that a particular shape of an operator would alter dramatically the projection onto a state, since all operators pass through a smearing/blocking procedure; this step produces thousands of link paths. However, it is more an intuitively desire that drives us to use particular shapes for our operators. It should also be mentioned that we have chosen operators whose construction can be implemented easily on the lattice, minimising thus the computing time.

Let us first consider the string-like states. Classically, one may think of these states as wave modes propagating along the string like standing waves such as the one presented in the left panel of Figure 5.1. These can be modelled by square waves that satisfy the

Figure 5.1: Left Panel: A standing wave on a periodic string. Right Panel: A “standing” square wave on a periodic lattice.

continuity of the derivative at the boundary, such as the one presented in the right panel of Figure 5.1. The amplitude and the number of modes of the wave operators is just a matter of construction. To understand how these operators have been constructed, please see Equation (A.18). We have included all possible configurations of amplitudes and modes in order to obtain the maximum projection onto the corresponding states. Unfortunately, as it turned out, these operators contribute minimally in the low-lying spectrum. Here, it should be mentioned that we exclude the wave operators of Equation (A.18) with paths that also appear as pulse-like transverse deformations in Table 4.1.

One may also think of phonons as “lumps” propagating along the string. These can be visualised by pulse-like transverse deformations interposing the propagation of the gluonic operator along a straight line, such as the square operator presented in Figure 5.2. All the

Figure 5.2: The square-pulse path.

pulse-like transverse deformations are presented in Table 4.1.

Concerning the string-glueball couplings, we intuitively believe that a right operator, which could possibly trigger them, can be visualised as a straight-line operator with an arbitrary Wilson loop attached to it. This operator can be obtained by breaking the straight line Polyakov loop at some spatial lattice site $x_{\parallel,\perp}$ and using this as an initial and final point we construct a spatial-like path ordered Wilson loop. This is also a pulse-like operator, expected to contribute to the string-like states as well. An example of such an operator is the clip-like pulse presented in Figure 5.3. Finally, the appearance of the additional massive

Figure 5.3: The clip-like pulse path.

states, if they do exist, is expected to be triggered using pulse-like operators. In addition, for each individual type of path we construct its associated reflection, in order to produce operators that transform irreducibly under parity transformations.

The next step, then, would be the construction of the operators. This topic is presented in detail in Chapter 4 and we will not discuss it here. So, given that we have applied the techniques of Chapter 4, we built a basis of N_O different smeared/blocked² operators $\Phi_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, N_O$ described by configurations of quantum numbers $\{P, q\}$. Then, this set of operators is encoded on the lattice in the form of a Fortran code. This code, the implementation of which is described in Section 3.4.5, is then compiled and submitted as an executable file on a CPU. Everything now has been left on the “hands” of the computer and we just wait until the simulation completes all the Monte-Carlo sweeps, a number of times pre-adjusted by us. The selected numbers of Monte-Carlo sweeps can be found in Tables 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3.

Firstly, after all simulations were completed and all bins of measurements for each different configuration of quantum numbers were gathered in a single correlation data file

²The relative weight p_a , which appears in Equation (4.1) and Figure 4.1, and determines how fast the link field spreads outwards as the smearing/blocking procedure is being iterated, is chosen to be $p_a = 0.75$.

Figure 5.4: Effective ground state energies against the time interval n_t for seven different flux tube lengths in $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 40$ and $\{P = +, q = 0\}$.

$\simeq A_0 e^{-aE_0}$ to the ground state, the eigenvector for the next highest eigenvalue $\simeq A_1 e^{-aE_1}$ to the first excited state, and so on. These eigenvectors are then applied to each jackknife average correlation matrix $C_{ij}^{J(s_{bin})}(t)$ according to Section 3.5.3 and Equation (3.91). The correlation function for a state with excitation index $n = 0, 1, \dots, N_O$ for a jackknife bin s_{bin} reads as:

$$\langle \Phi_n^\dagger(t) \Phi_n(0) \rangle_{J(s_{bin})} \equiv \sum_{k,l=1}^{N_O} a_{nk}^* a_{nl} C_{kl}^{J(s_{bin})}(t). \quad (5.10)$$

Now for each different jackknife bin s_{bin} we perform an effective energy calculation and fits according to Sections 3.5.1 and 3.5.2 respectively, with all the resulting parameters treated as secondary quantities. For each such parameter, we extract the average and the associated variance by applying the general Formulae (3.94) and (3.95) respectively. An example of an effective energy estimation is presented in Figure 5.5. There we consider the ground state effective energies on several time intervals, for seven different flux tube lengths in $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 40$ and $\{P = +, q = 0\}$. The horizontal lines correspond to the best estimates for the ground state. In Figure 5.5 we present the correlators of the first three states extracted using the variational technique for $L_{\parallel} = 26$, $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$ and $\{P = +, q = 0\}$. The parameters of the curves in the plot were extracted by fitting the correlators. As can be seen from Figure 5.5, the single exponential fits, reproducing exactly the correlators with high overlaps of $\sim 99.5\%$ for the ground, $\sim 98.7\%$ for the first and $\sim 97.2\%$ for the second excited states, suggesting that the large basis of operators that has been used gives successful results.

Figure 5.5: Correlators for the ground, first excited, and second excited states in red, green and blue, respectively, and their best fits for $SU(3)$, $\beta = 21$, $L_{\parallel} = 26$ and quantum numbers $\{P = +, q = 0\}$. The corresponding effective energies are also presented in the plot on the left bottom of the graph.

5.6 Results

5.6.1 General

In this section we present the results of the fundamental closed flux tube spectrum calculation. The presentation is divided into two parts. In the first part we discuss the zero momentum sector, where we mainly present the results obtained by applying the variational technique on the two decoupled correlation matrices with quantum numbers $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ and $\{P = -, q = 0\}$. The results obtained in this calculation fall into three sub-categories: the ground state referring to the lowest effective string theory energy level with $N_L = N_R = 0$, the first excited state corresponding to the first excited state according to an effective string theory model with $N_L = N_R = 1$ and finally the second excited state with $N_L = N_R = 2$. One of course may say that our convention of categorising these states is biased by a single expectation, namely that all states are string-like. To this purpose we note that indeed, as it turned out, the spectrum of the closed fundamental flux tube, at least at the level of our probing, does not include any other states rather than string-like.

The second part of this chapter discusses the non-zero longitudinal momentum sector. As for $q = 0$, we categorise the presentation onto four different subsections, according to the excitation level in the effective string theoretical framework of Nambu-Goto. More precisely, the four different components are the ground state energy level for $q = 1$ with $N_L = 1, N_R = 0$, the first excited state level for $q = 1$ with $N_L = 2, N_R = 1$, the ground state energy level for $q = 2$ with $N_L = 2, N_R = 0$ and the first excited state for $q = 2$ with $N_L = 3, N_R = 1$; we close this part by making some general remarks on higher excited states.

5.6.2 Zero longitudinal momentum; $q = 0$

Let us now investigate the $q = 0$ sector.

5.6.2.1 Ground State; $N_L = N_R = 0$

The ground state was obtained by performing an effective energy calculation and a fit on the correlator of the best approximate wave-functional associated with the ground state in a variational calculation for the sector $\{P = +, q = 0\}$. Three facts are of interest here: firstly this is the lightest state of the spectrum, secondly it appears as the ground state in the sector $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ and finally the mass gap with the first excited state within the same sector for relatively short flux tubes is large enough minimising possible contaminations from excited states. These are the basic reasons that lead to an approximation which is very well-defined numerically with high overlaps ($A_0 \sim 99 - 100\%$) and nice effective energy plateaus that dominate the effective energy behaviour already from the first time interval ($n_t = 1$). Two examples of effective energy calculations for the ground state are presented in Figures 5.5 and 5.6. In the former we present an effective energies plot for seven different string lengths at $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 40$. As can be seen, the plateaus can already be obtained from the first time intervals for all string lengths except for the longest one, which is massive and the contamination from the first excited state contributes significantly within the first time interval. The associated mass can, therefore, be obtained successfully by fitting the correlation from $n_t = 2$ onwards. It is also obvious that some states suffer with positivity. This is considered as a statistical fluctuation and thus it has been ignored. The more massive a state is, the more rapidly the correlator decays, and by the time it disappears in the noise, we cannot apply the effective energy criterion anymore. So, as the mass of a state increases we get less and less time intervals, which may constrain the energy of the state under investigation; this can be seen in the plot of Figure 5.6. In Figure 5.6, we present the effective energies for eleven excitations for a fixed string length ($L_{\parallel} = 14$) at $SU(6)$ and $\beta = 90$. The lowest energy level corresponds to the ground $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ state.

Since the ground state is the most accurately derived state, we use it to obtain an estimate for the fundamental string tension in lattice units $a^2\sigma_f$. This can be done in several ways. We choose to fit the ground state using the ansatz presented in Equation (2.93), which also provides us with an approximation of the level of the empirical corrections materialised by the value of the coefficient C_p . Although, the statistics are not enough to constrain what value of p the fit prefers and consequently to indicate the effective string theoretical description whose prediction for the minimal value of this correction term is the most favorable, we obtain that this dimensionless correction is rather small. Here, it should be mentioned that up until the time the article by Aharony and Karzbrun had been released, we assumed that the minimal value of p was $p = 3$. So in our publications [1, 2] we obtained and used string tensions $a^2\sigma_f$ that were extracted using the same ansatz and $p = 3$. By looking at the results of the fits one realises that the string tension remains the same within the errors for the range $p = 1 - 6$, and, therefore, the convention of using fits with $p = 3$ was consistent. The results of the fits with $p = 6$ are presented in Table 5.4 while the results of the fits with $p = 3$ are presented in Table 5.5.

Although the basis $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ consisted of a large number of operators, nothing new on the ground state came out of this calculation. Repeating what can be found in previous works [39, 40], the ground state can be very well-approximated by the Nambu-Goto (red line in Figure 5.7), even for short strings with lengths close to the deconfining length

Figure 5.6: Effective energies aE_{eff} as a function of the time n_t for eleven different excited states for a flux tube with $L_{\parallel} = 14$ at $SU(6)$. From lower to higher, the quantum number of these states are as follows: 1. ground state $\{P = +, Q = 0\}$, 2. ground state $\{P = -, Q = 1\}$, 3. first excited state $\{P = +, Q = 0\}$, 4. ground state $\{P = +, Q = 1\}$, 5. first excited state $\{P = -, Q = 1\}$, 6. second excited state $\{P = +, Q = 0\}$, 7. ground state $\{P = -, Q = 2\}$, 8. ground state $\{P = -, Q = 0\}$, 9. third excited state $\{P = +, Q = 0\}$, 10. ground state $\{P = +, Q = 2\}$, 11. first excited state $\{P = -, Q = 0\}$.

$l_c = 1/T_c$ and comparable to the width of the flux tube. For, $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \gtrsim 1.5$ the discrepancies of the ground state with Nambu-Goto become negligible. The L.O Nambu-Goto prediction provided by Polchinski and Strominger (green line in Figure 5.7) is insufficient to describe the ground state data for short flux tube lengths; according to our results, this is the case until the flux tube length reaches $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \gtrsim 2.5$ at which point L.O Nambu-Goto starts providing an adequate description for the ground state. For the N.L.O Nambu-Goto prediction of Lüscher and Weisz (blue line in Figure 5.7) and the N.N.L.O Nambu-Goto prediction of Aharony and Karzburn (magenta line in Figure 5.7), there is not much to say since their differences with the full Nambu-Goto are negligible at the level of ground state and our statistics are not that accurate to distinguish between these three predictions. The only thing that can be said is that the prediction which is closer to the ground state data for the shortest string is full Nambu-Goto. Nevertheless, a much clearer description between these three predictions is presented for the first excited state in the next section, where it is shown that the best approximation on the data is provided by full Nambu-Goto. Closing this section, we emphasise that the ground state can be thought of as a free Nambu-Goto bosonic string state with no phonons, namely $|0\rangle$. This state has no phonons, hence it was

Configuration	C_6	$a^2\sigma_f$	$\chi^2/\text{d.o.f}$
$SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$	0.149(74)	0.030210(35)	1.69
$SU(3)$ at $\beta = 40$	0.104(107)	0.007589(16)	1.10
$SU(6)$ at $\beta = 90$	0.257(62)	0.029527(40)	0.84

Table 5.4: The parameters $a^2\sigma_f$, C_6 and $\chi^2/\text{d.o.f}$ in the fit of Equation (2.93) with $p = 6$ extracted using Bayesian fits (Section 3.6.2).

Configuration	C_3	$a^2\sigma_f$	$\chi^2/\text{d.o.f}$
$SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$	0.067(27)	0.030221(36)	1.48
$SU(3)$ at $\beta = 40$	0.007(40)	0.007588(16)	1.10
$SU(6)$ at $\beta = 90$	0.096(24)	0.029538(42)	1.06

Table 5.5: The parameters $a^2\sigma_f$, C_3 and $\chi^2/\text{d.o.f}$ in the fit of Equation (2.93) with $p = 3$ extracted using Bayesian fits (Section 3.6.2).

expected to appear as a ground state in the $P = +$ sector and so it happened.

5.6.2.2 First Excited State; $N_L = N_R = 1$

The first excited state was obtained by performing an effective energy calculation and a fit on the correlator of the best approximate wave-functional associated with the first excited state in the variational calculation for the sector $\{P = +, q = 0\}$. An example of an effective energy calculation of the first excited state is presented in Figure 5.6 as the third line from the bottom in green. In addition, in Figure 5.5 we present an example of a first excited state correlator. According to Nambu-Goto, the first excited state for $q = 0$ can be described by $N_L = N_R = 1$ with phonon structure $\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$. This state has an even number of phonons, a left-handed and a right-handed both of absolute momentum $2\pi/l$, and, therefore, it is characterised by positive parity $P = +$. Since the $q = 0$ ground state appeared as the ground state in the $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ sector, the first excited state is expected to appear as the first excited state in the same sector. Indeed, that is what we have observed! By performing the variational technique we obtain that the first excited state of the sector $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ has a large gap with the next excited state, indicating that this state is not degenerate and it, therefore, agrees with Nambu-Goto. Having showed that the degeneracy pattern for the first excited state matches that of Nambu-Goto, let us now see how its associated energy level is related to Nambu-Goto and the other effective string theoretical predictions.

The accurate energy estimation of the first excited state would not be possible if we had not used the large basis of operators. As an example, let us take the case of $L_{\parallel} = 14$ at $SU(6)$ and $\beta = 90$, the effective energy plateaus of which are presented in Figure 5.6. Using the large basis of operators, more precisely a basis consisting of 107 operators, we obtained an estimate for the first excited state of $aE_1 = 0.9165(29)$ with an overlap of $A_1 \simeq 99.1\%$, by fitting from $n_t = 1$ onwards. However, if we now isolate the 16 (4×4) correlation matrix elements that correspond to the single line operator at four blocking levels, in other words if we re-perform the calculation using only the straight line path, and apply the variational technique, we obtain an estimate of 0.9443(101) with a poorer overlap of $A_1 \simeq 93.4\%$,

Figure 5.7: The ground state energy per unit length, in dimensionless units, vs. the string length for $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 21$, $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 40$, $SU(4)$ and $\beta = 50$, $SU(5)$ and $\beta = 80$ and finally $SU(6)$ and $\beta = 90$. Using the values we obtain for the string tensions we plot the full Nambu-Goto, the Polchinski and Strominger (L.O), the Lüscher and Weisz (N.L.O) and the Aharony and Karzbrun (N.N.L.O) predictions.

by fitting from $n_t = 2$ onwards. The former estimate for the first excited state is nearly six standard deviations lower than the latter, a difference which cannot be ignored in an accurate calculation. Moreover the overlap A of the latter, which serves as a measure of the accuracy and the “quality” of an energy extraction, is 6% off the former. This argument reflects the importance of using a large basis of operators!

In Figure 5.8 we present results for the first excited state from five different simulations. The Nambu-Goto energy level for $N_L = N_R = 1$ is presented in black, the Polchinski-Strominger prediction in green, the Lüscher-Weisz prediction in blue and Aharony-Karzbrun prediction in magenta. As can be seen in the plot, the prediction that approximates better the results is full Nambu-Goto. At short strings there are discrepancies with full Nambu-Goto, which become negligible by the level of $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 3.5$. The first calculation on the first excited state had been performed for $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 21$ corresponding to a lattice spacing of $a' \simeq 0.174/\sqrt{\sigma_f}$. By keeping the lattice spacing fixed we moved to $SU(6)$ at $\beta = 90$, in order to check how the picture alters in the large- N limit. As it has turned out, these discrepancies remain the same and can therefore be considered as a large- N effect. Having checked the N -dependence of these deviations, we attempted to check whether there is a modification by moving to the continuum. This has been checked by extracting the first excited state for $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 40$, which corresponds to decreasing the lattice spacing by a factor of 2. Once more we have not obtained significant differences, suggesting that the discrepancies with Nambu-Goto is also a continuum effect. The configurations of $SU(4)$ at $\beta = 50$ and $SU(5)$ at $\beta = 80$ which correspond to a lattice spacing of $3a'/4$, are providing exactly the same information.

Remarkably, full Nambu-Goto has proven to be the best known approximation for the first excited state of the closed flux tube spectrum, even at string lengths lower than the critical length $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 4.9$, at which the Nambu-Goto expansion parameter $8\pi(1-1/24)/(l\sqrt{\sigma_f})^2$ deviates. It is also clear that none of the three other effective string theoretical predictions provides a good description for our results, within the range of the probing string lengths. It is expected that at some point as the string length increases, these theoretical predictions will start providing an adequate description for the first excited state as soon as their differences with the full Nambu-Goto become negligible.

Figure 5.8: The energy of the first excited state for $\{P = +, q = 0\}$, $N = 3, 4, 5, 6$ and several values of β as a function of the flux tube length, plotted in dimensionless units. The black line represents the first excited Nambu-Goto state (Equation (2.98) with $N_L = N_R = 1$), the green line presents the first excited state prediction of Polchinski-Strominger (Equation (2.68) with $n = 1$ and $D = 3$), the blue line denotes the first excited state prediction of Drummond, Dass-Matlock and Lüscher-Weisz prediction (Equation (2.71) with $n = 1$ and $D = 3$) and the magenta line shows the first excited state prediction of Aharony-Karzbrun (Equation (2.92) with $n = 1$ and $D = 3$). Obviously, full Nambu-Goto provides a much better description of our results than any other known effective string theoretical prediction.

5.6.2.3 Second Excited State; $N_L = N_R = 2$

According to Nambu-Goto, the second excited state for $q = 0$ can be characterised by $N_L = N_R = 2$. We can, therefore, build four different states satisfying this condition, namely, $\alpha_{-2}\bar{\alpha}_{-2}|0\rangle$, $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$, $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-2}|0\rangle$ and $\alpha_{-2}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$. The first two states have an even number of phonons and are thus described by $P = +$, while the two latter have an odd number of phonons and hence they are described by $P = -$. This suggests that the two $P = +$ states are expected to appear as the second and third excited states in the sector $\{P = +, q = 0\}$, since the ground and first excited states have already been occupied; the other two $P = -$ states are expected to appear as the ground and first excited states in the sector $\{P = -, q = 0\}$; this is the first time we encounter $P = -$

states. Ideally, one would expect to obtain two-fold degeneracy patterns for both $P = +$ and $P = -$, giving in total a four-fold degenerate energy level.

Adopting the same procedure as before, the second excited state spectrum has been obtained by performing effective energy calculations and fits on the correlators of the best approximate wave-functionals extracted from two separate variational calculations, one for $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ and one for $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ correlation matrices. Examples of effective energy calculations for these four states can be found in Figure 5.6. Additionally, in Figure 5.5 a correlator with its associated effective energy plot for the second excited state of the sector $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ is presented with an overlap of $A_2 \simeq 97.3\%$. Once more we emphasise the importance of using a large basis of operators with transverse deformations. We do so by arguing that if we used only the single line operator, which is trivially transforming under parity, we would not have been able to project onto the sector $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ and obtain an energy plateau for the second and third excited states in the sector $\{P = +, q = 0\}$. Nevertheless, by making use of this large basis of operators, we managed to project onto these four states with good enough overlaps.

The second excited state of the sector $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ which is presented in Figure 5.9 appears to deviate a lot from full Nambu-Goto at the very shortest lengths. As the length increases this state approaches the Nambu-Goto prediction rapidly until it reaches the level of $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 5.5$, where these deviations become negligible. By decreasing the lattice spacing and keeping the gauge group fixed, we obtain that no significant changes occur for the deviations. On the other hand, by increasing the value of N , we realise that these deviations decrease for the shortest flux tube lengths.

The third excited state of the sector $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ which is also presented in Figure 5.9 appears to be close to the Nambu-Goto prediction, with a remarkable agreement for the sum of the shortest flux tube lengths. As the length increases it seems to fluctuate slightly around $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 3$, deviating negatively from Nambu-Goto and then rising again, exhibiting a behaviour with almost negligible discrepancies with Nambu-Goto. Its behaviour seems to be relatively unaffected by moving towards the continuum ($SU(3)$, $\beta = 21 \rightarrow \beta = 40$) and the large- N limit ($SU(3) \rightarrow SU(6)$).

Let us now move to the $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ configuration of quantum numbers and see what was obtained there. The ground state of this sector is presented in blue in Figure 5.9. We obtain that for the three lowest string lengths it exhibits a behaviour that appears with different patterns in the three different plots. From $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 2.5$ onwards, this state moves close to the Nambu-Goto prediction with almost negligible corrections to it; this particular behaviour seems to remain unaltered as we tend to the continuum and the large- N limit.

The first excited state of the sector $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ has large deviations from Nambu-Goto for the very shortest flux tube lengths. As the length increases these deviations decrease, then rise again and then decrease until they become negligible; this pictorialises a “wavy” decaying behaviour. Nothing important can be said on what happens by tending to the continuum and the large- N limit, since the picture remains relatively the same without the appearance of striking and constraining observations in the comparison from moving from one case to the other.

Having described the behaviour of these four states individually, we can obtain a more general picture by considering these as a cluster of states. According to this description, as we increase the length of the flux tube they converge onto Nambu-Goto and by the time they reach $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 5.5$ they become degenerate and consistent with it. This agrees perfectly with the predicted degeneracy pattern of four states obtained in the Nambu-Goto framework. Safely, it can be said that above this lower length limit, these four excitations

of the flux tube behave as bosonic Nambu-Goto strings.

A detailed comparison of our best estimate states to the other three effective string theoretical predictions will not be provided here, since none of them approaches our results as fast as full Nambu-Goto does; especially at a flux tube length region where the expansion parameter of Nambu-Goto diverges. This should, therefore, lead us to conclude that one should take full Nambu-Goto expression as the starting point and consider corrections to that for all excitation levels. If the accuracy of the extracted states is enough, somebody could obtain empirical corrections by fitting these corrections. In this case the quest would be to choose the right fitting ansätze.

5.6.2.4 Higher Excited States; $N_L = N_R = 3$

The application of the variational technique onto the correlator matrices with quantum numbers $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ and $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ leads to a vast number of best approximate wave-functionals each one mapping onto an associated excitation level. Theoretically, for each configuration of quantum numbers one should obtain as many excited states as the number of the operators forming the basis. However, only a few of those project successfully onto the states under investigation, by means of leading to correlators with high overlaps onto the physical states. Usually, these best approximate wave-functionals are associated with the low-energy spectrum. At the second excited Nambu-Goto energy level, investigated in the previous subsection, the overlaps are good, although they decrease as we move to higher excitations. Nevertheless, by going beyond this level, we face wave-functionals with poor overlaps and consequently we cannot rely on them. On the other hand, they can at least provide us with an upper bound of the associated energy levels.

Thus, we attempted to extract higher excited states. Although results are not presented here, we mention that for the very largest flux tube there is strong evidence that nine such states, four of negative parity and five of positive parity, are nearly degenerate and close to the $N_L = N_R = 3$ Nambu-Goto energy level. The degeneracy pattern is in agreement with Nambu-Goto, since according to this framework, there are nine possible states satisfying the level matching constrain $N_L = N_R = 3$, five with an even and four with an odd number of phonons; namely $\alpha_{-3}\bar{\alpha}_{-3}|0\rangle$, $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-3}|0\rangle$, $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-2}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-2}|0\rangle$, $\alpha_{-3}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$, $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$ characterised by positive parity $P = +$ and $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-2}\bar{\alpha}_{-3}|0\rangle$, $\alpha_{-3}\bar{\alpha}_{-2}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$, $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-2}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$, $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-2}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$ characterised negative parity $P = -$.

5.6.3 Non-Zero longitudinal momentum; $q \neq 0$

Having investigated the zero longitudinal momentum excitations of the closed flux tube, it is time to discuss the $q = 1$ and $q = 2$ sectors of states. Once more, all the obtained states at large flux tube lengths could be accommodated within the Nambu-Goto framework, suggesting that the only kind of states appearing in the $k = 1$ flux tube spectrum are string-like. Hence the taxonomy of the states is driven according to their connection to Nambu-Goto.

5.6.3.1 Ground state for $q = 1$; $N_L = 1, N_R = 0$

Using the term ground state for $q = 1$, we refer to the closed flux tube state the energy level of which at large flux tube lengths can be described by the Nambu-Goto $q = 1$ ground state with $N_L = 1, N_R = 0$. Within the Nambu-Goto framework there is only one way to

Figure 5.9: Second excited state as a function of the flux tube length for $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$ presented in the first plot, $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 40$ presented in the second plot and $SU(6)$ at $\beta = 90$ presented in the third plot. Full Nambu-Goto prediction is denoted by the black line, L.O Nambu-Goto prediction by the green line, N.L.O Nambu-Goto prediction by the magenta line and N.N.L.O Nambu-Goto prediction by the blue line. Data in “-” represents the second excited state of $\{P = +, q = 0\}$, in “x” the third excited state of $\{P = +, q = 0\}$, in “*” the ground state of $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ and in “o” the first excited state of $\{P = -, q = 0\}$.

construct a state satisfying this condition, namely the $\alpha_{-1}|0\rangle$. This has only one phonon, so it is expected to appear in the $P = -$ sector of states. Indeed, the state which has been obtained by an effective energy calculation and a fit on the correlator of the best approximate wave-functional associated with the ground state in the variational technique for the sector $\{P = -, q = 1\}$ is consistent with Nambu-Goto from $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 2.5$ onwards (Figure 5.10). An example of an effective energy calculation of this state is shown in Figure 5.6; the second from the bottom.

Since full Nambu-Goto predictions appear to work so well, it is worth investigating the phonon contributions more closely and trying to isolate the level of agreement of the phonon excitations to our numerical results. To this purpose it is noted that according to Equation (2.98), the piece of the energy that is due to the phonons can be expressed as:

$$\Delta(q, l) = E_0^2(q; l) - E_0^2(q = 0; l) - \left(\frac{2\pi q}{l}\right)^2. \quad (5.11)$$

Following this expression, in order to perform such an investigation, we use the numerically calculated values for $E_0^2(q; l)$ and $E_0^2(q = 0; l)$. We could have also used the Nambu-Goto predictions instead of $E_0^2(q = 0; l)$, but we decided not to since the numerical result already “contains” information on the deviations of the zeroth phonon energy regarded to belong to the Casimir energy rather than to the excitation energy. Rather than plotting $\Delta(q, l)$, it has been decided to plot $\Delta(q, l)/\pi\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$ with $\mathcal{R} \equiv f$ that provides an effective value for the total phonon contribution $4(N_L + N_R)$.

In the plot presented in Figure 5.10 we perform a comparison of the $\{P = -, q = 1\}$ ground state obtained for $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$ and $SU(6)$ at $\beta = 90$. In other words we attempted to check how the phonon contribution alters when moving to the large- N limit. According to this plot, our results remain relatively the same; for the very shortest flux tube lengths they exhibit deviations that decrease as the length increases.

However, it is also interesting to investigate whether this deviating behaviour for the short flux tube lengths changes as we move to the continuum. To this purpose we present in Figure 5.10 a comparison of the $\{P = -, q = 1\}$ ground state obtained for $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$ and $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 40$. In other words we attempted to check whether the behaviour of this state changes by decreasing the lattice spacing by a factor of 2. Remarkably, we obtained that all the discrepancies vanish and our results become statistically fully consistent with the Nambu-Goto prediction even for the very shortest flux tube length! This enables us to state that the obtained low length discrepancies for the ground state of sector $\{P = -, q = 1\}$ are just a finite lattice spacing effect and, therefore, this state can be described perfectly by Nambu-Goto.

5.6.3.2 First excited state for $q = 1$; $N_L = 2, N_R = 1$

Having presented the ground state for $q = 1$, let us now move one excitation level higher. On the first excited state we include all the states the energy levels of which approach the prediction of Nambu-Goto for $q = 1$ and $N_L = 2, N_R = 1$. According to Table 2.1, there are two possible ways of constructing states satisfying this condition. More specifically we can construct two states: one with three phonons of absolute momentum $2\pi/l$, two left- and one right-handed, acting on the vacuum, such as $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$. And one state with two phonons, a left-moving with momentum $4\pi/l$ and a right-moving with momentum $-2\pi/l$, acting on the vacuum, such as $\alpha_{-2}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$. The latter, therefore, has positive parity and the

Figure 5.10: Plots representing the comparison between states obtained for a. $SU(3)$, $\beta = 21$ and $SU(3)$, $\beta = 40$ and b. $SU(3)$, $\beta = 21$ and $SU(6)$, $\beta = 90$, for the ground state (g.s) $\{P = -, Q = 1\}$. Each plot presents the phonon energy of a state according to Equation (5.11) as a function of the flux tube length in dimensionless units.

former has negative parity.

Since we have not encountered any other state with $P = +$ and $q = 1$ before, this indicates that the positive parity state is expected to appear as a ground state in the sector $\{P = +, q = 1\}$. In the previous subsection it was demonstrated that the ground state within the sector $\{P = -, q = 1\}$ is already occupied making us believe that the new negative parity state would appear as the first excited state.

Hence, we apply the variational technique to $\{P = +, q = 1\}$ and $\{P = -, q = 1\}$ correlation matrices and subsequently we perform effective energy calculations and fits on the correlators for the best approximate wave-functionals associated with the ground $P = +$ state and the first excited $P = -$ state. Examples of such effective energy calculations are presented in Figure 5.6; the fourth and fifth lines from the bottom represent the best estimate values for the energies of the ground $P = +$ and first excited $P = -$ states respectively. Here it should be mentioned that by the time we reach the first excited state of the sector $\{P = -, q = 1\}$, states are getting so massive that only the first three time intervals could constrain an estimate on the energy of a state.

The ground state of $\{P = +, q = 1\}$ presented in Figure 5.11 appears to be extremely close to the Nambu-Goto for $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 21$ for the shortest flux tube lengths, and becomes fully consistent with it at larger lengths. By decreasing the lattice spacing by a factor of 2, by going from $\beta = 21$ to $\beta = 40$ while keeping $N = 3$ fixed, the data becomes fully consistent with Nambu-Goto for all the probed flux tube lengths. This is presented in the first plot of Figure 5.11. Surprisingly, according to the second plot of Figure 5.11, by increasing the value of colour N and keeping the value of the lattice spacing a fixed,

our states unexpectedly deviate more (although they are still small) compared to those obtained for $N = 3$. This is odd and cannot receive a reasonable interpretation, since we would expect that our extracted energy levels would at least exhibit the same, if not smaller, deviations from Nambu-Goto.

The first excited state of $\{P = +, q = 1\}$ also appears to be extremely close to the Nambu-Goto prediction. In the case of $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 21$ the state exhibits an agreement with the theoretical prediction by the level of $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} = 1.7$, with the data point (within the error bars) for the shortest flux tube length deviating positively only one standard deviation. Exactly the same behaviour was obtained for the case of $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 40$, suggesting that the behaviour of this state does not alter as we move to the continuum limit. The comparison of the data for $SU(3)$, $\beta = 21$ and $\beta = 40$ is presented in the third plot of Figure 5.11. There is not a clear indication how the large- N limit affects the behaviour of this state. The only thing which can be said in this direction is that by moving to $SU(6)$ the state keeps behaving similarly. The comparison of the data $SU(3)$, $\beta = 21$ and $SU(6)$, $\beta = 90$ is presented in the fourth plot of Figure 5.11.

5.6.3.3 Ground state for $q = 2$; $N_L = 2, N_R = 0$

By using the phrase ground state for $q = 2$, we refer to the set of closed flux tube states the energy levels of which at large flux tube lengths can be described by the Nambu-Goto $q = 2$ ground state, characterised by $N_L = 2, N_R = 0$. According to the Nambu-Goto framework there are two possible ways of constructing states satisfying this level-matching constrain. We can either construct a state with two left-handed phonons of momentum $2\pi/l$ each, acting on the vacuum, such as $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}|0\rangle$, or a state with only one left-handed phonon of momentum $4\pi/l$, with structure $\alpha_{-2}|0\rangle$. The former state consists of two phonons and, therefore, has $P = +$ while the latter with one phonon, has $P = -$.

The above parity structure of these two states indicates that one state is expected to appear as a ground state in the sector $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ and the other as a ground state in the sector $\{P = -, q = 2\}$. We, therefore, apply the variational technique to $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ and $\{P = -, q = 2\}$ correlation matrices and using the resulting eigenvectors of the diagonalisation process we perform effective energy calculations and fits on the correlators for the best approximate wave-functionals associated with the ground $P = +$ and ground $P = -$ states. Examples of such effective energy calculations are presented in Figure 5.6; the seventh and tenth lines from the bottom present the best estimate values for the ground $\{P = -, q = 2\}$ and $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ states respectively.

The ground state of $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ presented in Figure 5.12 appears to be extremely close to the Nambu-Goto prediction even at the shortest flux tube lengths, at which it appears to deviate slightly, but it becomes consistent with the theoretical prediction by the time it reaches $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 2.5$. The comparison between $SU(3)$, $\beta = 21$ and $SU(6)$, $\beta = 90$, presented in the second plot of Figure 5.12, does not show any significant differences, suggesting that the picture does not change as we increase the value of N . However, the comparison between $SU(3)$, $\beta = 21$ and $SU(3)$, $\beta = 40$, presented in the first plot of Figure 5.12, does not deliver important information on how the state's behaviour alters as we move to the continuum. The only thing that can be said for the case of $SU(3)$, $\beta = 40$, is that the state becomes consistent (within the error) with Nambu-Goto at the level of $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 1.7$.

The ground state of $\{P = -, q = 2\}$, the behaviour of which was completely unexpected, seems to exhibit a finite lattice spacing effect resulting in significant deviations from the

Figure 5.11: Plots representing the comparison between states obtained for a. $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$ and $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 40$ and b. $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$ and $SU(6)$ at $\beta = 90$, for the ground state (g.s) $\{P = +, q = 1\}$ and first excited state (f.e.s) $\{P = -, q = 1\}$. Each plot presents the phonon energy squared of a state extracted according to Equation (5.11) as a function of the flux tube length in dimensionless units.

Nambu-Goto predictions. More specifically, for both, $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$ and $SU(6)$ at $\beta = 90$, which correspond relatively to the same lattice spacing, the phonon energy contribution is almost null for the shortest flux tube length and increases rapidly until it reaches $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 3.1$ where it becomes almost consistent with the prediction. This can be viewed in the fourth plot of Figure 5.12. Amazingly, this striking deviating behaviour minimises as we move towards the continuum limit. This can be seen in the third plot of Figure 5.12, where we present a comparison between $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$ and $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 40$; for the shortest flux tube length at $\beta = 40$ the state exhibits a negative discrepancy of only four standard deviations. This particular behaviour of the ground state of $\{P = -, q \neq 0\}$ seems to be enhanced by longitudinal momentum, since for the case of $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 40$ we have obtained that these deviations increase with the longitudinal momentum q . This can be seen in Figures 5.13 and 5.14. At $q = 4$ the phonon contribution appears to be negative and it keeps decreasing as we increase the value of q . In any case, this is an artificial effect and in no way does this reflect a physical property of the closed flux tube; it is, therefore, not of high significance.

5.6.3.4 First excited state for $q = 2$; $N_L = 3, N_R = 1$

Having discussed the ground state for $q = 2$, it is time to go one excitation level further and investigate the first excited state for $q = 2$. At this level we include all the states with energy levels approaching the prediction of Nambu-Goto for $q = 2$, which obeys the condition $N_L = 3, N_R = 1$. According to the Nambu-Goto framework there are three possible ways to construct states satisfying this level matching constrain (Table 2.1). Two of these states are of $P = +$ and only one of $P = -$. More specifically, the positive parity sector consists of one state with four phonons, three left- and one right-handed, all of absolute momentum $2\pi/l$ with structure $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$, and one state with two phonons, one left-handed with momentum $6\pi/l$ and one right-handed with momentum $-2\pi/l$, with structure $\alpha_{-3}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$. In the negative parity sector only one such state appears with two left-handed phonons, one of momentum $4\pi/l$ and one of $2\pi/l$, and a right-handed phonon with momentum $-2\pi/l$. The latter can be written as $\alpha_{-2}\alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$.

Taking into account that the ground state levels in both $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ and $\{P = -, q = 2\}$ sectors had already been occupied by the ground $q = 2$ string-like state, we expected that the two parity states characterised by $N_L = 3, N_R = 1$ would appear as the first and second excited states in the sector $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ and the one negative parity state as the first excited state in the sector $\{P = -, q = 2\}$. So it happened! By using once again the helpful tool of variational technique in both $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ and $\{P = -, q = 2\}$ sectors we obtained the best estimated energy values for these three states (see Figure 5.15). At these energy levels the contamination caused by uncontrolled systematics forbids a detailed description of the behaviour of the states. Therefore, only a qualitative description on these three states is presented, avoiding a comparison between the three gauge group configurations. However, according to our results as shown in the comparison between the three plots of Figure 5.15, it seems that the “best” monotonic behaviour is possessed by the gauge group configuration $SU(6)$ and $\beta = 90$.

The three states seem to experience important deviations from Nambu-Goto at the very shortest flux tube lengths without a well-justified degeneracy pattern. Nevertheless, as the flux tube length increases, these become exactly degenerate within their errors, indicating thus the agreement with the Nambu-Goto predicted degeneracy pattern. In addition, the energy levels of these three states, appear to be extremely close to the Nambu-

Figure 5.12: Plots representing the comparison between states obtained for a. $SU(3)$, $\beta = 21$ and $SU(3)$, $\beta = 40$ and b. $SU(3)$, $\beta = 21$ and $SU(6)$, $\beta = 90,000$, for the ground state (g.s) $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ and $\{P = -, q = 2\}$. Each plot presents the phonon energy of a state according to Equation (5.11) as a function of the flux tube length in dimensionless units.

Figure 5.13: Fundamental closed flux tube excitation energies for the $q = 3$ string-like ground state for $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 40$, extracted using Equation (5.11). The line corresponds to the Nambu-Goto prediction for $N_L = 3, N_R = 0$.

Figure 5.14: The ground state of a fundamental closed flux tube for the sector $\{P = -, Q = 4\}$ from the $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 40$, extracted using Equation (5.11). The line corresponds to the Nambu-Goto prediction for $N_L = 4, N_R = 0$.

Goto prediction for large ($l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \gtrsim 3$) flux tube lengths.

5.6.3.5 Higher excited states for $q \neq 0$.

Closing the presentation of our results, we briefly discuss what has been obtained for the higher excited states of the $q \neq 0$ sector. In the previous section, we demonstrated that by the level of the string-like first excited $q = 2$ state the systematics are significant and, therefore, there is not much point to present a detailed picture of what happens beyond this level. In addition the deviations of the higher excited states from the theoretical prediction $4(N_L + N_R)$ of Equation (5.11) are getting larger and the overlaps are getting smaller, prohibiting the identification of these as Nambu-Goto string-like states within the range of the probed flux tube lengths.

The question rises again of whether there exist massive excitations which reveal the internal degrees of freedom of the flux tube. Although such states have not been observed in the low-lying fundamental flux tube spectrum, they may be hidden in higher excitation levels that are either beyond our limit of probing or have been extracted with low accuracy that does not allow us to give a concluding identification. In an attempt to convince you that some higher excitations are indeed Nambu-Goto like, we have chosen to present collectively several cases in which the string-like interpretation can still be identified.

In Figure 5.13 we present the phonon contribution to the $q = 3$ string-like ground state for $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 40$ as a function of the flux tube length; this corresponds to the level

matching constrain $N_L = 3, N_R = 0$. In the string theoretical framework, this condition can be satisfied in three different ways. We can, therefore, construct three states, one of positive parity $\alpha_{-2}\alpha_{-1}|0\rangle$ and two of negative parity $\alpha_{-3}|0\rangle$ and $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}|0\rangle$. As it was expected, the ground and first excited states of the sector $\{P = -, q = 3\}$ appear to be exactly degenerate with the ground state of the sector $\{P = +, q = 3\}$ at the very largest flux tube length $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 3.1$, confirming the free Nambu-Goto string description of the flux tube at large string lengths. For shorter strings, the states appear to deviate from the Nambu-Goto prediction for $N_L = 3, N_R = 0$. These deviations are large for the very shortest string-length, but as this increases, they rapidly converge onto the theoretical prediction.

In Figure 5.14 we present the phonon energy squared for the ground state of the sector $\{P = -, q = 4\}$ with $SU(3)$ and $\beta = 40$. As has already been explained, this state suffers from important finite lattice spacing effects that impart tachyonic character to the very shortest flux tube length contributions. As the flux tube length increases, the state rapidly approaches the Nambu-Goto prediction for $N_L = 4, N_R = 0$, until it becomes fully consistent with it. According to the string theoretical framework the ground $q = 4$ state, with level matching constrain $N_L = 4, N_R = 0$ can be satisfied in five different ways. These consist of three positive parity states, namely $\alpha_{-3}\alpha_{-1}|0\rangle$, $\alpha_{-2}\alpha_{-2}|0\rangle$ and $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}|0\rangle$, and two states of negative parity: $\alpha_{-4}|0\rangle$ and $\alpha_{-2}\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}|0\rangle$. Hence, the observed state is associated either with one of the two negative parity states or with a mixing among them.

5.7 Conclusions

In this chapter we examined to what extent the excitation spectrum of the closed fundamental flux tube can be described by an effective string theory. Amazingly, we found that a simple Nambu-Goto free string description reproduces the spectrum very well, even when the length of the flux tube is of the order of its width. A question then arises: Can a flux tube that looks more like a blob rather than a tube possess phonon-like spectrum associated with a prediction deriving from a theory which is quantum mechanically consistent in $D = 26$ and effectively usable at $D < 26$ only for long enough strings? This is of great interest and should teach us something about the nature of the effective string theory description for the confining flux tube. Apparently, neither of the other effective string theoretical approaches that have manifestly been constructed in such a way so as to predict the spectrum of the flux tube manage to provide a description as good as the critical bosonic string of Nambu-Goto.

This suggests that theorists should change their way of viewing the confining string dynamics. This is also enhanced by the fact that all the effective approaches proposed so far in $D = 2 + 1$ can be reproduced perfectly by expanding the Nambu-Goto prediction square root in powers of $1/l$. Perhaps instead of using the Gaussian action that derives from Nambu-Goto at low energies under the right gauge, as a starting point, one can use the full Nambu-Goto action and consider correcting additive terms to it. This is of course not a straightforward task, but it might lead to an inspiration that will hopefully show the way to the “right” effective theory.

It appears that our spectrum of the confining closed flux tube includes only string-like states. However, although no any other “extra” massive mode states show up, they may still be included in the spectrum. It is likely that the lack of knowledge on these objects prohibits us from constructing operators with the physics of these states encoded within them. Hence, the only statement that can be made is that using a particular basis

of operators we did not observe any other states rather than string-like. Nevertheless, by exploring the spectrum of $D = 2+1$ flux tubes that are quite different than the fundamental such as $k = 2$, we might obtain states associated with such “extra” modes; this is discussed in the next chapter. It is also possible that such states will show up in $D = 3 + 1$ where a torelon operator can be transversely deformed along two directions and subsequently can have a much more complicated structure that might somehow encode the “physical” properties of these “extra” states.

Considering the technical part, this calculation simply reveals the importance of using a large basis of operators in order to extract the first few states of the fundamental closed flux tube spectrum. In fact, the variational calculation with a large sample of operators is the only way to extract the spectrum with high accuracy. As has already been discussed, although we can extract some approximate value for the first excited state of the trivial configuration with quantum numbers $\{P = +, Q = 0\}$ using just the straight line operator, we realise that the overlap is enhanced with the insertion of extra operators. We can, therefore, use the simple Polyakov operator to project onto the ground state $\{P = +, Q = 0\}$ with an apparent success, but by the time we need the extraction of the excitation spectrum, the creation of extra operators by means of inserting transverse deformations, is more than necessary. It should be kept in mind that by using operators with transverse deformations is the only way to project onto states described by non-trivial configurations of the quantum numbers $\{P, Q\}$.

Figure 5.15: First excited state for $q = 2$ as a function of the flux tube length for $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 21$ presented in the first plot, $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 40$ presented in the second plot and $SU(6)$ at $\beta = 90$ presented in the third plot. The Nambu-Goto prediction is denoted by the red line. Data in green represents the first excited state of the sector $\{P = +, q = 2\}$, in blue the second excited state of the sector $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ and in magenta the first excited state of the sector $\{P = -, q = 2\}$.

Chapter 6

The spectrum of closed $k = 2$ flux tubes

6.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to explore what happens to the spectrum of a 2+1 dimensional $SU(N)$ closed flux tube when the flux is in a representation of colour higher than the fundamental with \mathcal{N} -ality of $k = 2$. We do so for $SU(4)$ at $\beta = 50$ and $SU(5)$ at $\beta = 80$. In Chapter 5 and in previous work [39, 41, 43] the lattice spacing corrections were found to be small, except in some particular cases such as the ground state for $\{P = -, q = 2\}$; we, therefore, decided not to perform a continuum extrapolation, but instead to perform calculations at fixed small values of the lattice spacing a . The adopted gauge group couplings correspond to a common value of the lattice spacing a .

For each value of N and β , we attempted to calculate the energy levels for the low-lying spectrum of correlation matrices constructed from four different bases of operators, each one described by the non-trivial quantum numbers of parity $P = \pm$ and longitudinal momentum $q = 0, 1, 2$. The first set of operators has been constructed in such a way so that it projects onto the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation ($k = 2A$) and it consists of components described by Equation (4.20). The second set of operators is formed by Polyakov loops built in such a way so as to project onto the $k = 2$ symmetric representation ($k = 2S$); these can be expressed according to Equation (4.22). The third set of $k = 2$ operators has been created without encoding within the projection onto a particular $k = 2$ irreducible representation. This consists of general $k = 2$ operators such as the ones presented in Equations (4.12) and (4.14); this set of operators is denoted as $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\}$. Finally the fourth set of operators consists of the third set plus the set of $k = 2$ operators that have been constructed in such a way so as to give rise to doubly wound ($w = 2$) states of fundamental flux such as Equation (4.15); this set of operators is denoted as $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\} \oplus \{w = 2\}$. As mentioned in Sections 4.7.1 and 5.5, the wave operators used in the $k = 1$ spectrum extraction contribute minimally and have, therefore, been discarded from the set of lattice paths contributing to the $k = 2$ spectrum. Hence all the operators constructed here use as basic components Polyakov loops with transverse deformations given by Table 4.1.

Some of our most important results that derived from this calculation are briefly presented below. We find that to a very good approximation the low-lying spectrum of the $k = 2$ string falls into sectors that belong to nearly pure antisymmetric and symmetric

representations, showing that k -strings know not only about the centre of the group Z_N , but also about the full $SU(N)$ gauge group. In addition, we obtain that each irreducible representation possesses a low-lying spectrum very close to the full Nambu-Goto spectrum. For the stable $k = 2A$ irreducible representation this agreement is astonishing for flux tube lengths l not too small. Since in the previous chapter we showed that the three other effective string theoretical predictions fail to provide an adequate description for our results, we do not bother comparing the $k = 2$ results to these. Instead we perform comparisons to the full Nambu-Goto spectrum only. We confirm [41] that the corrections compared to the free string theory are of order $\mathcal{O}(1 - 10)$, in striking contrast to the very small corrections observed for the fundamental string. Moreover we obtain that the deviations from Nambu-Goto are particularly small when the phonons propagating along the string have the same momentum, and large when their momentum is opposite. This reveals information about the detailed nature of the interactions in the effective bosonic string theory. Finally, we have not found states associated with excitations of massive modes, although we have searched for them; however, we obtain strong evidence that the $k = 2$ spectrum also includes unbound states of doubly wound fundamental fluxes ($w = 2$).

The structure of this chapter is as follows. In the next section we briefly describe the motivation that led to the investigation of the $k = 2$ flux tube spectrum. Then we briefly explain the lattice calculation, commenting on the systematics and the variational calculation; although these matters have already been discussed in Chapter 5, in addition there exist some peculiarities that appear only in the $k = 2$ spectrum extraction. We then present the results for the $k = 2$ spectrum. This is divided in four distinct parts. In the first part we present the results obtained by projecting onto the $k = 2$ fully antisymmetric ($k = 2A$) and symmetric ($k = 2S$) irreducible representations. In the second part we show that such a separation is appropriate, by demonstrating in detail that the $k = 2$ flux tube knows about the full $SU(N)$ gauge group and not just about the centre Z_N . Subsequently, in the third part we demonstrate that among the $k = 2$ states there exist excitations of $w = 2$ tubes of fundamental flux. Next, in the fourth part we return to the interesting question of whether those excited states without an obvious string-like interpretation obtained in the first part, may be associated to massive states, revealing thus the internal degrees of freedom of the flux tube. In order to address this question we perform a heuristic method of comparing the shapes of the wave-functionals of $k = 2$ states with the $k = 1$ states. We end with the conclusions.

6.2 Motivation

The ground state energy of a closed $k = 2$ flux tube was calculated recently in [41], and it was shown to be adequately described by the free Nambu-Goto string, with string tension $\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} \equiv \sigma_{2A}$ and corrections that have coefficients that are $\mathcal{O}(1)$ in natural units. This is actually what one would expect if the $k = 2$ flux tube were to have an effective bosonic string description at large distances, and it also provides a striking contrast with the fundamental flux tube where the corrections to the free Nambu-Goto are much smaller. In practice, however, the ground state provides just a limited insight into the nature of the $k = 2$ flux tube spectrum and thus, just as for the fundamental flux tube (Section 5.2), it is important to perform accurate calculations of at least a few excited states. As has already been expressed, this is difficult in a lattice calculation where one can only hope to obtain accurate estimates for the excitations which have a very high overlap onto the basis of the

operators.

In Chapter 5, we have attacked this problem for the fundamental flux tube by using a very large basis of operators (Table 4.1 and Figure 4.7.1). Having already been equipped by such a powerful tool, we can convert this to $k = 2$ flux tube operators and use them for the extraction of the $k = 2$ spectrum. Apparently, the fact that the time-expensive wave operators contribute minimally to the $k = 1$ flux tube spectrum allows us to exclude such Polyakov loops from the $k = 2$ calculation.

The fundamental flux tube spectrum at large string lengths l has encoded within itself the quantum numbers that characterise the Nambu-Goto string. In the previous chapter it was shown that using the level-matching constrain $N_L - N_R = qw$ for a single wound flux tube, we can construct its large- l spectrum. Complementarily, it would be proper to check what happens for the doubly-wound fundamental flux-tube spectrum, and test whether this agreement still occurs for $w = 2$. The right framework to pursue such a study is the $k = 2$ string spectrum investigation because the centre symmetry keeps track of the net winding k ($l_C \rightarrow z^k l_C$). However, ordinary $k = 2$ operators, cannot project onto $w = 2$ states due to reasons we explain in Sections 1.3.3 and 4.4. To achieve such a task we have to construct operators with periodicity of two longitudinal lattice extents. The way we obtain such operators is by constructing Polyakov lines with one of the transverse deformations presented in Figure 4.1 located at the joint of the two lattices. Therefore, we expect that the spectrum will reveal extra states that are associated with phonon excitations with corresponding wave lengths $\lambda_n = wl/n$ and momenta $\omega = 2\pi n/wl$. The identification of such states will contribute towards the quest of revealing the nature of the confining flux tube, and its effective string theoretical description.

So far no “extra” massive states were identified. All the $k = 1$ flux tube states appeared to be Nambu-Goto-like. This may be because the basis of the operators used in the variational calculation has little overlap onto states of such nature. Exploring the spectrum of flux tubes which are quite different than the fundamentals we might obtain something that could be identified as an “extra” state. Finding these states would provide a useful clue about the nature of a hypothetical gauge/gravity dual theory which predicts such excitations. This is another reason, that makes us enthusiastic about this work.

6.3 Lattice Calculation

The standard lattice framework described in Chapter 5 was used for the lattice calculation. The framework will, therefore, not be presented here in detail. For more information on the lattice methodology, please see Sections 5.3 and 3.3. We work on a cubic periodic Euclidean space-time lattice with volume $L_{\parallel} \times L_{\perp} \times L_T$ and lattice spacing a . Again, we chose to present our results in terms of the dimensionless units $E/\sqrt{\sigma_f}$ for the energy and $l\sqrt{\sigma_f}$ for the flux tube length. So, again there was no need of giving lattice spacing a physical units.

The quantisation of the $SU(N)$ gauge theory was achieved by inserting the Wilson action of Equation (3.42) in the probability distribution of the Feynman path integral. The extraction of the $k = 2$ spectrum has been achieved by calculating correlation functions such as Equation (5.1) of operators Φ_i . These operators have been constructed in such a way so as to have the quantum numbers of $k = 2$ and $\{P, q\}$ encoded within them.

We performed calculations in $SU(4)$ and $SU(5)$ at $\beta = 50$ and $\beta = 80$, respectively. These values of β should correspond roughly to the same value of lattice spacing. Indeed, what we find by fitting the $k = 1$ ground state of the sector $\{P+, q = 0\}$ is that the lattice

spacing in terms of the fundamental string tension is given by:

$$a = \begin{cases} 0.1310(2)/\sqrt{\sigma_f} & : SU(4), \beta = 50 \\ 0.1298(1)/\sqrt{\sigma_f} & : SU(5), \beta = 80 \end{cases} \quad (6.1)$$

As mentioned in the introduction, our experience with the fundamental flux tube spectrum extraction as well as results for glueball masses [43] and the deconfining temperature [102, 103] indicate that lattice spacing corrections for such values of a are negligible, except in those cases where such effects are enhanced by the appearance of high longitudinal momenta.

We calculated the spectra of flux tubes with \mathcal{N} -ality $k = 2$ which wind around the compactified longitudinal direction and range in length from $L_{\parallel} = 12$ to $L_{\parallel} = 32$. Using the expressions of the lattice spacings presented in Equation (6.1) the flux tube length range corresponds to $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \in [1.56, 4.20]$. This indicates that our shortest flux tubes are presumably not much longer than they are wide; suggesting that our probing takes place in a region where the gluoelectric flux can still be thought of as a widthful tube rather than just an infinitesimally thin string. For reasons of comparison, the minimum length l_c below which the flux tube dissolves completely is:

$$l_c = \frac{1}{T_c} \simeq \begin{cases} 8.1a & : SU(4), \beta = 50 \\ 8.3a & : SU(5), \beta = 80 \end{cases} \quad (6.2)$$

In the next two tables we present the lattices and the total number of Monte-Carlo sweeps that were used in the calculation.

String Length	Lattice Volume in $SU(4)$	Lattice Volume in $SU(5)$	MC Sweeps
12	$12 \times 24 \times 40$	$12 \times 32 \times 80$	500000
16	$16 \times 24 \times 40$	$16 \times 32 \times 40$	500000
20	$20 \times 24 \times 32$	$20 \times 24 \times 32$	500000
24	$24 \times 24 \times 32$	$24 \times 24 \times 32$	500000
28	$28 \times 28 \times 32$	$28 \times 28 \times 32$	500000
32	$32 \times 32 \times 32$	$32 \times 32 \times 32$	500000

Table 6.1: The lattice volumes and the number of Monte-Carlo (MC) sweeps that have been used for the calculation of the $k = 2$ spectrum for $SU(4)$ and $SU(5)$.

6.4 Systematics

Since we were interested in accurately identifying the corrections to the asymptotic linear variation with l for the low-lying states, it was important to minimise the contribution of the systematic errors. Most of these were described in detail in the previous chapter in Section 5.4. In addition, due to the fact that the $k = 2$ calculation has a more complex implementation, a few more sources of systematics appear. Among these, the most important are:

1. Unstable excited states: theoretically this is what is expected for states emanating in representations higher than the stable (which appears to be the fully antisymmetric one) within the same \mathcal{N} -ality. More specifically this can be a problem if the energy gap between an excited state and the ground state i.e ($E_i - E_0$) is greater than the

lightest scalar glueball mass. As long as the decay width is small such a source of error will not lead to any visible effects. This is the case of large values of N , where such decay widths vanish.

2. Periodicity along the temporal direction: This is due to the fact that some $k = 2$ operators that consists of products of two $k = 1$ loops such as $\text{Tr}\{l_C\}^2$ can “decouple” during the numerical calculation of a correlator. Normally we would expect that a $k = 2$ wave-functional at time t_1 “sees” an anti-wave-functional at time t_2 separated by temporal distance $t_2 - t_1$, and at the same time it “feels” the same anti-wave-functional at temporal distance $T - t_2 + t_1$. This is pictorialised in the left panel of Figure 6.1. The former interaction would lead to a correlator behaving as $\sim e^{-E_0^{k=2}(t_2-t_1)}$ for $n_{t_2} - n_{t_1} \gg 1$ and the latter to a contribution of $\sim e^{-E_0^{k=2}(T-t_2+t_1)}$ for $L_T - n_{t_2} + n_{t_1} \gg 1$. These two contributions, for $t_2 - t_1 \ll T$ and $E_0^{k=2} \ll E_1^{k=2}$ lead to the two-fold correlator $C(t) = A\left(e^{-E_0^{k=2}(t_2-t_1)} + e^{-E_0^{k=2}(T-t_2+t_1)}\right)$. By either fitting this or fitting the single exponential after minimising the contribution coming from the back of the torus by choosing a large enough T , we can extract the ground $k = 2$ state. The operator $\text{Tr}\{l_C\}^2$ is expressed as a product of two fundamental flux tube operators. Hence, there is also the possibility that individually, each fundamental operator $\text{Tr}\{l_C\}$ receives a contribution from the face and the back of the torus of $\sim e^{-E_0^{k=1}(t_1-t_2)}$ and $\sim e^{-E_0^{k=1}(T-t_2+t_1)}$, respectively. A pictorialisation of this can be found in the right panel of Figure 6.1. By considering the correlator $\langle \Phi^\dagger(t)\Phi(0) \rangle = \langle e^{-\hat{H}(T-t)}\Phi^\dagger e^{-\hat{H}t}\Phi \rangle = \sum_{n,m} |\langle n|\Phi|m \rangle|^2 e^{-E_n^k(T-t)} e^{-E_m^k t}$ we realise that the leading contribution of such a “decoupling” is $\sim e^{-E_0^{k=1}(T-t_2+t_1)} e^{-E_0^{k=1}(t_2-t_1)} = e^{-E_0^{k=1}T}$. This contributes to the overall correlator and, consequently, it simulates, at fixed T , a non-zero vacuum expectation value for the $k = 2$ operator. We should, therefore, be aware of such effects. This can be attacked by making $L_T = T/a$ large enough so that the contribution of both $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ unnecessary loops to the partition function are negligible, and all our energies are normalised to the correct vacuum energy.

Figure 6.1: Pictorialisation of the source of the systematic error which results from the “decoupling” of a $k = 2$ loop ($\text{Tr}\{l_C\}^2$) to two $k = 1$ loops ($\text{Tr}\{l_C\}$). For simplicity, we exclude the presentation of the transverse direction.

Following a variety of checks in order to minimise the finite volume effects, the lattices we used for $SU(5)$ are presented in Table 6.1. For the $SU(4)$ calculations, which were performed earlier, we used slightly smaller lattices for the shorter flux tube lengths, where finite corrections might not be negligible; these are presented in Table 6.1.

6.5 Variational Calculation

The variational calculation applied in the case of $k = 2$ was described extensively in the previous chapter in Section 5.5. We shall, therefore, discuss it very briefly. Compared to the $k = 1$ calculation, the only difference, now, is that the constructed transverse deformation is used to form loops of \mathcal{N} -ality $k = 2$. This is explained in detail in Chapter 4. As mentioned in the introduction, the wave operators were excluded from this calculation.

For each flux tube length we perform in total 24 variational calculations for the corresponding correlation matrices, obtained by projecting onto the:

1. $k = 2A$ sectors: $\{P = \pm, q = 0\}$, $\{P = \pm, q = 1\}$ and $\{P = \pm, q = 2\}$.
2. $k = 2S$ sectors: $\{P = \pm, q = 0\}$, $\{P = \pm, q = 1\}$ and $\{P = \pm, q = 2\}$.
3. $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\}$ sectors: $\{P = \pm, q = 0\}$, $\{P = \pm, q = 1\}$ and $\{P = \pm, q = 2\}$.
4. $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\} \oplus \{w = 2\}$ sectors: $\{P = \pm, q = 0\}$, $\{P = \pm, q = 1\}$ and $\{P = \pm, q = 2\}$.

Subsequently for all the best estimate wave-functionals extracted from each correlation matrix, we perform an effective energy calculation and fits as these are described in Sections 3.5.1 and 3.5.2. In Figure 6.2 we present an example of an effective energy estimation for a few states extracted by projecting on the $k = 2A$ (left panel) and $k = 2S$ (right panel) irreducible representations for $SU(5)$ and $l = 24a$. The lines correspond to the best estimates evaluated by fitting the correlators within the ‘‘plateau’’ time intervals.

Figure 6.2: Effective energies with the corresponding overlaps (A) for $SU(5)$ at $\beta = 80$ and $L_{\parallel} = 24$.

6.6 Results

In this section we present the results from the calculation of the $k = 2$ closed flux tube.

6.6.1 $k = 2$ Antisymmetric Representation Flux Tubes

In this part of the results presentation, we discuss the spectrum which was obtained by projecting onto the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation. This was achieved by using operators such as the one presented in Equation (4.21) in order to project onto the six disjoint sectors characterised by the quantum number configurations $\{P = \pm, q = 0\}$, $\{P = \pm, q = 1\}$ and $\{P = \pm, q = 2\}$. For each one of these sectors we performed a variational calculation and subsequently an effective energy estimation and a correlator fit for each excitation level.

In Figures 6.3 and 6.4 we present the energies of the lightest states with longitudinal momentum $2\pi q/l$ with $q = 0, 1, 2$ along the flux tube, for $SU(4)$ and $SU(5)$ respectively. We obtain that for all values of the flux tube length l , the lightest $q = 0$ state has $P = +$, the lightest $q = 1$ state has $P = -$, and for $q = 2$ there are two states, one with $P = +$ and one with $P = -$; these two states appear to be nearly degenerate for short flux tubes and they become exactly degenerate (within errors) as the length l increases. It is noted that these quantum numbers and (near-)degeneracies are precisely those of the Nambu-Goto free single wound string. By performing a calculation on the general $k = 2$ spectrum, we find that the obtained ground states with the same quantum number as those presented in Figures 6.3 and 6.4, are within the errors the same as the ones obtained in $k = 2A$. Hence, all these states have a projection onto $k = 2A$ that is very much larger than onto $k = 2S$. We shall, therefore, regard them as constituting part of the $k = 2A$ spectrum.

The $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ ground state is fitted using the Nambu-Goto expression with the leading permitted correction term, according to Equation (2.93) with $\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} \equiv \sigma_{2A}$. Adopting the result of Aharony and Karzbrun, this leading permitting correction should be equal to $p = 6$. The fit leads to:

$$a^2\sigma_{2A} = 0.023160(43) = 1.350(3)a^2\sigma_f; \quad C_6 = 16.9(1.9) : SU(4) \quad (6.3)$$

$$a^2\sigma_{2A} = 0.025745(43) = 1.528(3)a^2\sigma_f; \quad C_6 = 14.07(76) : SU(5) \quad (6.4)$$

According to the results of Lüscher-Weisz and Drummond and Dass-Matlock the leading permitting correction should be equal to $p = 3$. Adopting this value of p , the fit leads to:

$$a^2\sigma_{2A} = 0.023232(51) = 1.355(4)a^2\sigma_f; \quad C_3 = 2.93(24) : SU(4) \quad (6.5)$$

$$a^2\sigma_{2A} = 0.025825(50) = 1.533(4)a^2\sigma_f; \quad C_3 = 2.28(22) : SU(5) \quad (6.6)$$

It is noted that the values of σ_{2A}/σ_f are close to the quadratic Casimir ratios:

$$\frac{k(N-k)}{N-1} = \begin{cases} 1.333\dots & : SU(4) \\ 1.5 & : SU(5) \end{cases} \quad (6.7)$$

We observe that when expressed in terms of natural units, as in Equation (2.93), the correction to Nambu-Goto has a coefficient $C_p \sim \mathcal{O}(1-10)$. In fact, this is a natural value if we regard the string theory as an effective theory within the Nambu-Goto universality class. This result is to be contrasted with the value $C_p \sim \mathcal{O}(1/10)$ that one finds for the $k = 1$ flux tube. We should, therefore, emphasise how remarkably well the fundamental flux

tube is described by the free bosonic Nambu-Goto string theory. Due to the fact that the fit for $p = 6$ gave an unacceptable χ^2 compared to the acceptable value of χ^2 for $p = 3$, we use the calculated values of σ_{2A} for $p = 3$ to calculate the lightest $q = 0, 1, 2$ energies of the Nambu-Goto model and plot the results in Figures 6.3 and 6.4. Once the $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ ground state has been fitted, the $q = 1, 2$ energies are parameter-free predictions. We observe that the agreement between our numerical results and the Nambu-Goto values is excellent.

The Nambu-Goto prediction appears to work very well. Therefore, as in the fundamental representation (Chapter 5), it is worth examining the results more closely to try and isolate the phonon excitation energy contribution which is reproduced by our results. This is done using once more the Equation (5.11) which expresses the piece of the energy that is due to the phonons appearance. For comparison we present the Nambu-Goto excitation energies as well; this can be found in Figures 6.5 and 6.6. We obtain that, remarkably, the simple free Nambu-Goto string excitation energies provide an excellent description of the flux tube excitation energies over almost our whole range of flux tube lengths, with significant deviations only beginning to appear at the shortest flux tubes with $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 1.5$. Considering, the qualitative (quantum number and degeneracy pattern) and quantitative agreement between Nambu-Goto and our results, we assume that these eigenstates are very close to those of the free string theory, with the following corresponding excitations. The $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ ground state behaves as $\sim |0\rangle$, the $\{P = -, q = 1\}$ ground state as $\sim \alpha_{-1}|0\rangle$, the $\{P = -, q = 2\}$ ground state as $\sim \alpha_{-2}|0\rangle$ and finally the $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ ground state as $\sim \alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}|0\rangle$.

Since ground state energies can be extracted more reliably than the excited states energies, we began this section by presenting the ground states for various q . We now turn to a few excited states that can be extracted from the $k = 2A$ $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ sector. The results for $SU(4)$ and $SU(5)$ with the Nambu-Goto predictions are presented in Figures 6.7 and 6.8 respectively. The first excited state $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ shows substantial deviation from the free Nambu-Goto energies, and the next two states even more so. However, at least the former seems to be approaching the free string energy as the flux tube length l increases. Our first thoughts, led us to assume that this excitation was a stringy one. By taking a closer look at this state, we realised that this would be dangerous, since the first excited state, to quite a good approximation, is greater than the ground state by a constant value, let us say:

$$E_1(q = 0, l) \simeq E_0(q = 0, l) + \epsilon; \quad \epsilon \simeq 2\sqrt{\sigma_f}. \quad (6.8)$$

This is reminiscent of the expectation for non-stringy states as this was quantitatively described in Equations 1.21 and 1.22. In this case, such a state would cross the level of the first string excitation at some larger length l , and perhaps this, and not a convergence, is what is seen in Figures 6.7 and 6.8. At this stage, we cannot decide the classification of this excited state. We will turn to this question in Section 6.6.5, where we perform a heuristic method for comparing the shapes of the $k = 2$ with the $k = 1$ wave-functionals in order to give an unambiguous answer to this question.

6.6.2 $k = 2$ Symmetric Representation Flux Tubes

In this part, we discuss the results on the spectrum which was obtained by projecting onto the $k = 2$ symmetric representation ($k = 2S$). This was achieved by using operators of the

type (4.23) in order to project onto the six disjoint sectors characterised by the quantum number configurations $\{P = \pm, q = 0\}$, $\{P = \pm, q = 1\}$ and $\{P = \pm, q = 2\}$. As in the previous section, for each one of these sectors we performed a variational calculation and then effective energy calculations and fits on correlations for each excitation level.

As we shall see in Section 6.6.3, all the $k = 2$ states we analyse appear to transform primarily as $k = 2A$ or as $k = 2S$; there is also strong evidence that there exist states which transform as $w = 2$ fundamental. However, the lowest $k = 2A$ states are much lighter than the corresponding $k = 2S$ states. Therefore, the latter will be much more susceptible to the systematic errors (Sections 5.4 and 6.4). In particular, we expect that their mass will be over-estimated.

Bearing this caveat in mind, in Figures 6.9 and 6.10 we present the energies of the lightest $k = 2S$ states with momentum $2\pi q/l$ and $q = 0, 1, 2$ along the flux tube, for $SU(4)$ and $SU(5)$ respectively. We obtain a qualitative picture that is very similar to that for the $k = 2A$ states. More specifically, we find that for all values of the flux tube length l , the lightest $q = 0$ state has $P = +$, the lightest $q = 1$ state has $P = -$, and $q = 2$ is two-fold degenerate with one state with $P = +$ and one with $P = -$. This fits in with the Nambu-Goto free string picture for a single wound string.

By turning to a quantitative comparison with the Nambu-Goto, we encounter an immediate obstacle: as can be clearly seen in Figure 6.10, our estimate of the $L_{\parallel} = 32$ ($l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 4.2$) ground $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ state energy is too high to fit in with an expression for $E(l)$ which tends to an asymptotically linear behaviour. Hence, we assume that what is obtained here is the result of a systematic error of the kind described as a fourth source of error in Section 5.4; this is perhaps twice the size of the statistical error. If we now exclude this value from our fit to the $k = 2S$, $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ ground state using Equation (2.93), we obtain the following string tensions:

$$a^2\sigma_{2S} = 0.03957(45) = 2.306(27)a^2\sigma_f : SU(4) \quad (6.9)$$

$$a^2\sigma_{2S} = 0.03793(33) = 2.251(20)a^2\sigma_f : SU(5) \quad (6.10)$$

It is noted that the values of σ_{2S}/σ_f are close to the quadratic Casimir ratios for the symmetric representation:

$$\frac{k(N+k)}{N+1} = \begin{cases} 2.4 & : SU(4) \\ 2.333\dots & : SU(5) \end{cases} \quad (6.11)$$

Using the values of σ_{2S} we present the corresponding $q = 0, 1, 2$ ground state Nambu-Goto spectra in Figures 6.9 and 6.10. Semi-quantitatively the agreement is good. However, the longer, more massive states tend to overshoot the predicted values. Our interpretation to this positive deviating behaviour is that it is due to the systematic errors of our calculation growing with the calculated mass.

In Figures 6.11 and 6.12, we extract the phonon excitation energies squared from $SU(5)$ and $SU(4)$ values respectively, using Equation (5.11). We observe that there is a good qualitative agreement with Nambu-Goto, but clearly we cannot say more than that.

In contrast to the $k = 2A$ case, we have severe difficulty in extracting excited states. We, therefore, did not attempt to produce plots which are analogous to Figures 6.9 and 6.10. We shall investigate the question of whether the $k = 2S$, $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ first excited state behaves as a bosonic string in Section 6.6.5. There, we expect that a heuristic comparison of the wave-functional shape of this state to that of the fundamental $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ first

excited state might reveal some helpful information towards this direction.

Closing this section, it is probably fair to state that the $q = 0, 1, 2$ ground states provide significant evidence that the $k = 2$ symmetric flux tube behaves like a bosonic string. However, any attempt for a stronger statement is limited by the current uncertainties of our numerical simulations.

6.6.3 Group or Centre?

In this section we investigate whether the “general” $k = 2$ flux tube extracted by projecting onto $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\}$ knows about the full group theoretical structure of $SU(N)$ or just about the centre Z_N of the group $SU(N)$. For each \mathcal{N} -ality k , and for each set of the quantum numbers $\{P, q\}$, there should only be just one absolutely stable flux tube. There is also the possibility that such a flux tube may decay into a flux tube within the same \mathcal{N} -ality k but with a different configuration of quantum numbers, and accompanied by glueballs which carry the compensating quantum numbers. This process becomes insignificant as we increase the value of N .

Flux tubes that carry flux in an $SU(N)$ representation with \mathcal{N} -ality k other than the “stable” one are in general not stable. They can, therefore, be screened by gluons down to the “stable” irreducible representation. If the amplitude for such a screening is large, such states will be difficult to identify. On the other hand, if this amplitude is small enough then it should be possible to identify such fluxes in the excitation spectrum of the $k = 2$ strings. In that case, it is likely that such flux tubes are stable enough to be readily identifiable in our simulations.

In the previous section we demonstrated that the low-lying spectrum of the disjoint $k = 2A$ and $k = 2S$ representations has a string-like behaviour. In this section we show that the portion of the accessible $k = 2$ extracted by projecting onto $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\}$ is, to a good approximation, the sum of the disjoint $k = 2A$ and $k = 2S$ spectra.

A basis of closed paths is, therefore, constructed consisting of Polyakov loops of the type presented in Equations 4.11 and 4.13. Using this basis and applying the techniques described in Chapter 4, we construct operators which can project onto the six different irreducible representations $\{P = \pm, q = 0\}$, $\{P = \pm, q = 1\}$ and $\{P = \pm, q = 2\}$. Subsequently, this set of operators is inserted into a Monte-Carlo simulation. After the simulation has completed, we perform a variational calculation to each correlation matrix associated with a particular configuration of the quantum numbers $\{P, q\}$. The resulting best estimate wave-functionals are put through an effective energy estimation and correlation fittings in order to reveal the $k = 2$ spectrum.

6.6.3.1 Operator Overlaps

The investigation of whether the $k = 2$ flux tube spectrum knows about the full group theoretical structure of $SU(N)$ begins by studying the overlaps of the $k = 2A$ basis operators, $\{\Phi_{2A}^i; i = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$, onto their $k = 2S$ counterparts $\{\Phi_{2S}^i; i = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. To this purpose the normalised overlaps were defined as:

$$O_{AS}(i, j; t) = \frac{\langle \Phi_{2A}^{i\dagger}(t) \Phi_{2S}^j(0) \rangle}{\langle \Phi_{2A}^{i\dagger}(t) \Phi_{2A}^i(0) \rangle^{1/2} \langle \Phi_{2S}^{j\dagger}(t) \Phi_{2S}^j(0) \rangle^{1/2}}. \quad (6.12)$$

In previous work [41], Bringoltz and Teper calculated such overlaps at $t = 0$ for a small basis of blocked/smeared Polyakov loops of length $L_{\parallel} = 24$ ($l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 3$) on a $24 \times 24 \times 32$ lattice in $SU(5)$ at $\beta = 80$. This work showed that most of these overlaps were null within the errors, except for those where one of the operators was at the largest blocking level; nevertheless the largest overlap was still small < 0.03 . The only significant overlaps were for the largest blocking level $b = 5$, where the blocked link has width which is as large as its length; the operator more or less covers the whole spatial torus. As it turned out [1], these non-zero overlaps are nothing else but finite volume effects that decrease by increasing the transverse lattice size L_{\perp} and vanish by increasing both the longitudinal L_{\parallel} and transverse sizes L_{\perp} . However, higher blocking levels will become possible at larger values of the longitudinal size. We expect that the largest of these blocking levels will generate significant overlaps. Moreover, while this small basis has a reasonably good overlap onto $k = 2A$ and $k = 2S$ ground states, the overlap onto excited states is in general poor. This provided some evidence that the theory breaks up into approximately disjoint $k = 2A$ and $k = 2S$ sectors.

It would, therefore, be interesting to see what happens when we consider our much larger operator basis which has a good overlap onto most of the low-lying excited states. The overlaps for the extended basis were calculated on a 32^3 lattice for $\{P = +, q = 0\}$, $SU(4)$ and $SU(5)$ at $\beta = 50$ and $\beta = 80$, respectively. In Figure 6.13 we provide a three-dimensional plot of the values of $|O_{AS}(i, j; t = 0)|$ as i and j run over the basis of some 80 operators. As we might have expected from the more limited study discussed in the previous paragraph, the overlaps are mostly small, and in most cases zero within the errors. Only in the cases of operators at the very largest blocking levels these overlaps are significant, although these are numerically small. Since the 5th blocking level is the largest and considering the construction of the basis, these overlaps correspond mostly to operators labeling at multiples of 5. It is also mentioned that the largest overlaps are rising from operators the shape of which constructionally spread all over the spatial tori, such as paths \mathcal{C}_{12-16} . We can, therefore, assume that most of these large overlaps are much enhanced by finite volume corrections. As it turned out, this study confirms that even when we extend the basis so that it is quasi-complete for the low-lying spectrum of the $k = 2$ flux tube, the near-orthogonality of the $k = 2A$ and $k = 2S$ sectors is maintained. In physical terms, this suggests that the effects of screening the $k = 2S$ representation down to the $k = 2A$ one are very weak. This is also supported by the comparison of the left to the right panel of Figure 6.13, where it is shown that the largest overlaps in $SU(5)$ are much smaller than in $SU(4)$, suggesting that such screening effects become less important as we increase N . We also mention that similar results are also obtained for $t > 0$

6.6.3.2 State Overlaps

In this subsection we estimate the overlaps of the actual flux tube states onto the $k = 2A$ and $k = 2S$ sectors. Let us now see how this estimation was carried out.

Let $\{\tilde{\Psi}^i\}$ with $i = 1, 2, \dots, N_O$ be the true energy eigenfunctionals ordered by their energy $\{E_i\}$. By projecting only onto our $k = 2A$ basis, let the variationally extracted best estimate eigenfunctionals be $\{\tilde{\Phi}_{2A}^i\}$. Let us now suppose that the eigenfunctional $\tilde{\Phi}_{2A}^j$, corresponds to $\tilde{\Psi}^i$ with $j \leq i$. Here we count the possibility of $j < i$ arising from the fact that there may be a real eigenstate $\tilde{\Psi}$ with a small enough overlap onto the $k = 2A$ basis which does not lead to the right corresponding $\tilde{\Phi}_{2A}$, so that the set of the best estimate eigenfunctions is not complete.

The normalised correlation function of $\tilde{\Phi}_{2A}^j$ will be:

$$\langle \tilde{\Phi}_{2A}^{j\dagger}(t) \tilde{\Phi}_{2A}^j(0) \rangle \simeq \gamma_{2A}^2 e^{-E_j t}, \quad (6.13)$$

within some range of t at which the effective energy plateau occurs. The prefactor of the exponential γ_{2A} gives the overlap of the real eigenstate $\tilde{\Psi}^i$ on $\tilde{\Phi}_{2A}^j$, and therefore, onto the $k = 2A$ basis. The same procedure was done with the $k = 2S$ basis. This leads to the corresponding overlap γ_{2S} which appears in

$$\langle \tilde{\Phi}_{2S}^{j\dagger}(t) \tilde{\Phi}_{2S}^j(0) \rangle \simeq \gamma_{2S}^2 e^{-E_j t}. \quad (6.14)$$

In reality, we know that such a state will not appear at all in a sector where its overlap is small. For example, we do not expect that a $\tilde{\Phi}_{2S(2A),k}$ can be obtained in a calculation performed using the $k = 2A(2S)$ basis. So in practice, we calculate either γ_{2A} or γ_{2S} this way but not both. If, for example, γ_{2A} is large enough so that it can be clearly calculable, instead of looking within the $k = 2S$ basis, in order to estimate γ_{2S} , we look at the joint basis $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\}$. There the overlap is denoted as γ_{2AS} and it must be larger than or equal to γ_{2A} so as the state is visible in the variational calculation.

As shown in the previous subsection, we can take the $k = 2A$ and $k = 2S$ bases to be approximately orthogonal to each other. Then we can estimate γ_{2S} using:

$$\gamma_{2S}^2 \simeq \gamma_{2AS}^2 - \gamma_{2A}^2. \quad (6.15)$$

Respectively, if the state with overlap γ_{2AS} is more $k = 2S$ than $k = 2A$ then we do the same procedure with $k = 2A$ and $k = 2S$ interchanged. In this way we derive an estimate of γ_{2A}^2 and γ_{2S}^2 for each energy eigenstate. Because the $k = 2A$ and $k = 2S$ bases are not complete we expect $\gamma_{2A}^2 + \gamma_{2S}^2 < 1$ and that these estimates are approximate.

A selection of such analyses is presented in Figures 6.14 and 6.15. The examples are all from the $SU(4)$ calculation at $\beta = 50$. We note that the $SU(5)$ results would be very similar. In Figure 6.14 we demonstrate results for the $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ spectrum for the three flux tube lengths shown, as well as results for the $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ spectrum for the same flux tube lengths. In Figure 6.15 we present results for the $\{P = +, q = 1\}$ spectrum for the same three flux tube lengths, as well as results for the $\{P = -, q = 1\}$ spectrum for the same lengths. For each state we show our estimate for the overlaps squared of the $k = 2A$ and $k = 2S$ in red circles and blue squares respectively. The guide lines demonstrate how the energy levels alternate from being antisymmetric to being symmetric. We obtain that all the states are predominantly in one sector or the other. It is also observed that in some cases the sum of overlaps squared is significantly less than unity which reflects the overlap of that state on our whole basis; this effect becomes stronger for higher excited states.

6.6.4 Unbound fundamental flux loops of $w = 2$

So far we have focused on the spectrum investigation of $k = 2$ bound states. However the $k = 2$ spectrum should also include states which consist of fundamental flux that winds twice around the compactified spatial direction. Their spectrum is expected to be given, to some first approximation, by the Nambu-Goto Equation (2.98) with $w = 2$. In $D = 2 + 1$ such a double winding loop will necessarily cross itself. We also know that there are interactions between loops that are strong enough to bind them into the $k = 2A$ strings. We, therefore, expect that such states would suffer large corrections. In addition, the $w = 2$

flux tubes should typically be more massive than the corresponding $k = 2A$ states and so they are expected to appear in the part of the $k = 2$ spectrum that forms the excitation spectrum. Hence, they might be confused with other excited states. The above suggest that the observation of such states is non-trivial. We shall make it clear that this presentation is a very preliminary search for unbound fundamental $w = 2$ flux tubes.

In order to enhance the projection onto these states, additional operators of the form presented in Equations (4.15) and (4.16) were included. Subsequently, we perform the same calculation as in the Section 6.6.3, with the only difference that now we use the extended basis $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\} \oplus \{w = 2\}$. This basis consisted of approximately ~ 240 operators. By applying the variational technique, effective energy investigations and their associated fits, we extract the spectrum of the six disjoint sectors of quantum number configurations $\{P = \pm, q = 0\}$, $\{P = \pm, q = 1\}$ and $\{P = \pm, q = 2\}$. By comparing the resulting spectra to those obtained in Section 6.6.3, we attempted to identify such new states.

In Figures 6.16 and 6.17 we perform a comparison of the $SU(4)$ and $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ spectrum which was obtained with and without the extra $w = 2$ operators respectively. Indeed, we observe that the latter appears to contain two extra states, which are presented with black symbols. The blue line corresponds to the Nambu-Goto prediction of Equation (2.98) with $\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} = \sigma_f$, $w = 2$ and $N_L = N_R = 2$. The red line represents the Nambu-Goto prediction of Equation (2.98) with $\sigma_{\mathcal{R}} = \sigma_{2A}$, $w = 1$ and $N_L = N_R = 2$. As presented in Chapter 5, the ground and first excited states of a single wound flux tube with $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ should be two-fold degenerate for large enough tube lengths. However, for short flux tubes, we obtained that there is one state that is close to the theoretical Nambu-Goto prediction and another one that approaches the theoretical prediction from above as the length increases. A similar behaviour such as the latter is observed in Figure 6.17, with the lighter state, represented by an asterisk, being close to the $w = 2$ prediction and the heavier state, represented by a circle, approaching the blue line from above.

In addition, in order to confirm that these two states are primarily associated with the extra $w = 2$ operators in our extended basis $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\} \oplus \{w = 2\}$, in Figure 6.18 we present the projection of the variational eigenstates corresponding to the ground and first excited states onto all the operators in the basis. We looked at $l = 16a$ which corresponds to $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 2.1$ in the sector $\{P = -, q = 0\}$. At this flux tube length, the ground state corresponds to $w = 1$, $k = 2A$ and the first excited to $w = 2$, $k = 1$. For this size of lattice we can construct 160 operators in total. From these, the first 100 are ordinary $k = 2$ operators projecting onto $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\}$ and the other 60 are $w = 2$ operators projecting onto $\{w = 2\}$. As can be seen from Figure 6.18, the ground state (in red) projects mainly onto ordinary $k = 2$ operators, while the first excited state (in blue) projects almost entirely onto $w = 2$ operators. This is a piece of evidence that strengthens our interpretation of these states.

Furthermore, it is interesting to check which operator contributes the most to the first excited state. According to Figure 6.18, there is a peak contributing $|a_i|^2 \sim 63\%$ to this state. This operator is the rectangular pulse, the shape of which appears as \mathcal{C}_3 in Table 4.1, with link constituents at blocking level $b = 4$. Therefore, the transverse deformation has a physical length of $2 \times 2^{b-1} = 16$ lattice spacings. The complete shape of this operator is presented in the panel of Figure 6.18. The shape of this looks like an oscillating string with two nodes, doubly wound around the spatial torus. This can also be used as a heuristic support of our conclusion that a more general picture of the $k = 2$ spectrum includes unbound wave-like fundamental $w = 2$ states.

6.6.5 Are there extra massive states?

6.6.5.1 The Idea

As mentioned in Section 6.6.1, the first excited state in the $k = 2A$, $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ spectrum presented in Figures 6.7 and 6.8 has an ambiguous interpretation. It could be corresponding to the first excited string state with large deviations from the Nambu-Goto free string energy, which is also presented in Figures 6.7 and 6.8 and appears to be approaching as the length of the flux tube increases. Alternatively, this state could be a new excitation that arises from one of the massive modes of the ground state being excited. This scenario rises from the fact that the energy of this state has the same monotonic behaviour as that of the ground state; in other words it differs from the energy of the ground state by a nearly constant amount as the length of the flux tube varies. In this picture, the energy of this state would approach the energy level of the first excited Nambu-Goto state prediction, just to cross it at some larger length, and, therefore, the true stringy excitation would be presumably the next state up in energy (which indeed in Figure 6.8 is much closer to the Nambu-Goto prediction for most of the values of the flux tube length).

The identification of such extra states would provide a completely new source of important information about the string theoretical description of the gauge theory. Therefore, the investigation of this ambiguity is of high importance.

6.6.5.2 The Method

If the first excited state is indeed behaving as an approximate Nambu-Goto string excitation of the $k = 2A$ flux tube, then we would expect the associated wave-functional to have the appropriate “shape”. There is no need to know about the shape of the operators in terms of the highly blocked/smeared link matrices, but it is enough to know that the relevant part of the fundamental ($k = 1$) flux-tube spectrum is Nambu-Goto like. Indeed, the $k = 1$, $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ low-lying spectrum shows only small corrections to the free Nambu-Goto string. Hence, all we need to do is to perform a comparison between the wave-functionals of the first excited $k = 1$ and $k = 2A$ states extracted from the same lattice calculation and obtain the degree of agreement. In addition, we can also perform a similar comparison between the wave-functionals of the first excited $k = 1$ and $k = 2S$ states.

In the next few paragraphs we explain the adopted way in order to perform the comparison. Firstly let us define the set of winding operators as $\{\phi_i; i = 1, \dots, N_o\}$ the number of which is typically of $N_o \sim 100$. For this particular comparison they were chosen as to have quantum numbers of $P = +$ and $q = 0$. Before we trace these operators, they are group elements of $SU(N)$ and so they may be at any representation of $SU(N)$. If the flux is in a representation \mathcal{R} , by performing the variational calculation over the appropriate basis, we obtain a set of wave-functionals $\Phi_{\mathcal{R}}^n$. These wave functionals are linear combinations of the basis operators that have been used:

$$\Phi_{\mathcal{R}}^n = \sum_i^{N_o} b_{\mathcal{R},i}^n c_{\mathcal{R},i} \text{Tr}_{\mathcal{R}}\{\phi_i\} \equiv \sum_i^{N_o} b_{\mathcal{R},i}^n \text{Tr}'_{\mathcal{R}}\{\phi_i\}, \quad (6.16)$$

with the coefficients $c_{\mathcal{R},i}$ chosen in such a way to satisfy the normalisation condition:

$$\langle \text{Tr}'_{\mathcal{R}}\{\phi_i(0)\} \text{Tr}'_{\mathcal{R}}\{\phi_i(0)\} \rangle = 1. \quad (6.17)$$

The purpose of choosing this common normalisation is to make the comparison of the coefficients $b_{\mathcal{R},i}^n$, for different irreducible representations¹ \mathcal{R} meaningful. The basic idea now is that the coefficients $b_{\mathcal{R},i}^n$ include information about the “shape” of the state associated with the wave-functional, because they multiply the same operators, albeit in different representations, and with common normalisation. In order to compare the excited $k = 1$ and $k = 2A$ wave functionals we could just compare their coefficients $b_{f,i}^n$ and $b_{2A,i}^n$. This comparison would be straightforward if the operators ϕ_i that form the basis are orthogonal. However, they are not orthogonal, and in fact some have very large overlaps with each other. Apparently, diverse sets of b_i 's can correspond to very similar wave-functionals. Ideally, the most straightforward way to calculate the overlap of the two wave-functionals would be a direct numerical determination. Unfortunately this is something that cannot be applied in this case since the two operators have different \mathcal{N} -alities ($k = 1$ vs. $k = 2$) and consequently the overlap would be zero. So, in order to proceed to the calculation of the overlaps we need to transform the \mathcal{N} -ality of the $k = 2$ irreducible representation operator wave-functional to $k = 1$ and at the same we have to preserve its essential spatial characteristics that are encoded within the coefficients $b_{\mathcal{R},i}^n$. This is done by the simple substitution (with $t = 0$ throughout):

$$\Phi_{\mathcal{R}}^n = \sum_i^{N_o} b_{\mathcal{R},i}^n \text{Tr}'_{\mathcal{R}}\{\phi_i\} \longrightarrow \tilde{\Phi}_{\mathcal{R}}^n = \sum_i^{N_o} b_{\mathcal{R},i}^n \text{Tr}'_f\{\phi_i\}, \quad (6.21)$$

where we replace $\text{Tr}'_{\mathcal{R}}$ by Tr'_f in the expression for $\Phi_{\mathcal{R}}^n$. Although the main objective is to perform an investigation over the wave-functionals of the $\mathcal{R} = 2A$ the case of $\mathcal{R} = 2S$ has also been consider. Intuitively it is plausible to think of $\tilde{\Phi}_{2A(2S)}^n$ as having approximately the same “shape” as $\Phi_{2A(2S)}^n$. If we now compare $\tilde{\Phi}_{\mathcal{R}}^n$ with $\Phi_f^{n'}$ by calculating the normalised overlap defined as:

$$O_{n',n} = \frac{\langle \Phi_f^{n'\dagger} \tilde{\Phi}_{\mathcal{R}}^n \rangle}{\langle \Phi_f^{n'\dagger} \Phi_f^{n'} \rangle^{\frac{1}{2}} \langle \tilde{\Phi}_{\mathcal{R}}^{n\dagger} \tilde{\Phi}_{\mathcal{R}}^n \rangle^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad (6.22)$$

we are in fact comparing the shape of $\Phi_f^{n'}$ to that of the original $\Phi_{\mathcal{R}}^n$ wave-functional. It is clear that this method of performing the comparison, has a strong heuristic character and, therefore, the confidence on the result will depend on how clear-cut it proves to be.

Hence, we take the four lightest $k = 2A$ and $k = 2S$ best estimate variational eigenstates and form the sets $\{\tilde{\Phi}_{2A}^n; n = 0, 1, 2, 3\}$ and $\{\tilde{\Phi}_{2S}^n; n = 0, 1, 2, 3\}$ respectively. Then we take the overlap, by means of applying Equation 6.22, of each one of these with the corresponding

¹The operation $\text{Tr}_f\{\phi_i\}$ is defined as:

$$\text{Tr}_f\{\phi_i\} = \text{Tr}\{\phi_i\} \pm \text{Tr}\{\hat{P}\phi_i\}, \quad (6.18)$$

with $\hat{P}\phi_i$ denoting the reflection of ϕ_i over the longitudinal plane. Operation $\text{Tr}_{\mathcal{R}}\{\phi_i\}$ is defined as:

$$\text{Tr}_{2S}\{\phi_i\} = \frac{1}{2}\{\text{Tr}\{\phi_i\}^2 + \text{Tr}\{\phi_i \cdot \phi_i\}\} \pm \frac{1}{2}\{\text{Tr}\{\hat{P}\phi_i\}^2 + \text{Tr}\{\hat{P}\phi_i \cdot \hat{P}\phi_i\}\}, \quad (6.19)$$

for $\mathcal{R} = 2S$ and as:

$$\text{Tr}_{2A}\{\phi_i\} = \frac{1}{2}\{\text{Tr}\{\phi_i\}^2 - \text{Tr}\{\phi_i \cdot \phi_i\}\} \pm \frac{1}{2}\{\text{Tr}\{\hat{P}\phi_i\}^2 - \text{Tr}\{\hat{P}\phi_i \cdot \hat{P}\phi_i\}\}, \quad (6.20)$$

for $\mathcal{R} \equiv 2A$. For more information on the operator construction see Chapter 4.

best estimate variational eigenstates $\{\Phi_f^{n_f}; n_f = 0, 1, 2, 3\}$.

6.6.5.3 Results

The presentation of the results begins by showing the absolute overlaps squared $|O_{n_f, n_{2A}}|^2$ ($n_f \equiv n', n_{2A} \equiv n$) in the four left panels of Figures 6.19 and 6.20 for $l = 16a$ and $l = 32a$ respectively. We see that the $k = 2A$ ground state has an overlap which is virtually 100% on the $k = 1$ ground state. Having already established that both ground states can be very well-described by the free Nambu-Goto string, this result gives confidence that this method of comparison will lead to reliable results. The first excited $k = 2A$ states, the state the identity of which we are mostly interested in, appears to have an overlap that is almost entirely on the first excited states with $k = 1$. Since we found that the latter is a free Nambu-Goto string excitation, we infer that so is the first excited state of $k = 2A$. It is, therefore, clear that the first excited $k = 2A$ state with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ approach Nambu-Goto and is not an “extra” state reflecting to massive excitations of the flux tube.

Additionally, it is observed from Figure 6.20 that the next two $k = 2A$ states with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$, corresponding to the second and third excited states, are also very similar to the associated $k = 1$ states, and they, therefore, receive the interpretation of being Nambu-Goto string like. By performing a comparison between the left panels of Figures 6.20 and 6.19, we observe that in the latter, albeit leading to the same conclusion, the results for these two states are now less clear-cut. This might be due to the fact that the states become more Nambu-Goto-like as we move to longer flux tubes.

In the four right panels of Figures 6.19 and 6.20 we present the absolute overlaps squared $|O_{n_f, n_{2S}}|^2$ ($n_f \equiv n', n_{2S} \equiv n$) for $l = 16a$ and $l = 32a$ respectively. Once again, we obtain that the ground $k = 2S$ state with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ has an almost 100% overlap onto the $k = 1$ ground state. Although the first $k = 2S$ excited state is less clear-cut than for $k = 2A$, it still provides a high level of similarity between this and the corresponding $k = 1$, so we refer to this as being Nambu-Goto-like. However, the comparison for the second and third $k = 2S$ excited states with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ does not produce any useful information at all.

The above comparison teaches that the first excited $k = 2A$ state of the $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ sector is Nambu-Goto-like $\sim \alpha_{-1}\bar{\alpha}_{-1}|0\rangle$, and therefore has two phonons of opposite momenta of $p = \pm 2\pi/aL_{\parallel}$. The large correction of this state to the free string for short flux tubes suggests that these two phonons have a large interaction contribution to the energy. However, the ground $k = 2A$ state in the $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ sector has its energy level very close to the free string energy at all flux tube lengths l . This state which can approximately be denoted as $\alpha_{-1}\alpha_{-1}|0\rangle$ has two phonons of the same momentum $+2\pi/aL_{\parallel}$. All these facts led us to assume that the interaction energy of two phonons with the same momentum is very small.

6.6.6 Conclusions

In this chapter we examined whether the closed $k = 2$ flux tube can be described by an effective string theory. This study complements the study of fundamental ($k = 1$) flux tubes presented in the previous chapter, where it was concluded that the simple Nambu-Goto string provides a very good description for the spectrum, even when the length of the flux tube is comparable to its width.

We have also checked and confirmed that there is very little overlap between the totally symmetric ($k = 2S$) and totally antisymmetric ($k = 2A$) representations of the closed flux

tube. We subsequently demonstrated that our variationally extracted eigenfunctionals fall into these irreducible representations of colour to a good approximation. This enables us to categorise the spectra according to their behaviour under the full $SU(N)$ gauge group rather than just its centre Z_N .

In the $k = 2A$ sector of states we find that the ground states for $q = 0$, $q = 1$ and $q = 2$ possess energies which are very close to those of the Nambu-Goto with string tension $a^2\sigma_{2A}$. The leading permitted correction to $(E(q = 0; l)/(\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}l))^2$ is $\mathcal{O}(1/(\sqrt{\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}l})^7)$, and its fitted coefficient has a value of $\mathcal{O}(1 - 10)$. This is in striking contrast to the fundamental flux tube, where the corresponding coefficient is unnaturally small of order $\mathcal{O}(1/10)$. However, more surprising is the fact that the $q = 1$ and $q = 2$ ground states are well-described by Nambu-Goto all the way down to $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 1.5$. There the flux forms a thick tube rather than an infinitesimally thin string and it is, therefore, remarkable that the string oscillation spectrum should accurately describe its lowest modes. For the low-lying excited state within the $q = 0$ sector, we obtain that the deviations are much larger. This is the size of deviations that one would expect to observe within an effective string theory description that was only valid asymptotically.

In the $k = 2S$ sector, our ability to derive any useful conclusions is strongly limited by the much larger systematic errors. However, as in the $k = 2A$ sector the ground states of $q = 0, 1, 2$ are recognisably string-like; this is the only statement that can be made for this much heavier sector of states.

By including operators that wound twice around the toroidally compactified direction by means of possessing a periodicity of two longitudinal lattice extents, we were able to identify some “extra” eigenstates that correspond to doubly-wound flux tubes of fundamental flux, in addition to the bound $k = 2$ singly-wound flux tubes.

Although once more non-stringy states have not been identified, we have been able to reach a qualitative understanding on features of the interactions amongst the phonons along the flux tube. It was shown that the first excited state $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ is in fact a string excited state, with two phonons of opposite momentum $p = \pm 2\pi/l$ and large interaction energy; according to Figures 6.7 and 6.8 the energy of this state has very large corrections to the corresponding free string energy level. On the other hand the ground $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ state, has exactly the same two phonons, with the only difference that now they have the same momentum. According to Figures 6.3 and 6.4 the ground $\{P = +, q = 2\}$ state has energy which is virtually identical to that of the corresponding free string state, over the whole range of the flux tube lengths. We can, therefore, come to a conclusion about the non-trivial interactions between two phonons: these interactions are negligible when the phonons have exactly the same momenta and large when the momenta are exactly opposite.

Figure 6.3: Energies of the lightest four states with $q = 0, 1, 2$, for winding flux tubes in the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation of $SU(4)$ at $\beta = 50$. Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions of Equation (2.98), with string tension σ_{2A} obtained by fitting the ground state.

Figure 6.4: Energies of the lightest four states with $q = 0, 1, 2$, for winding flux tubes in the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation of $SU(5)$ at $\beta = 80$. Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions of Equation (2.98), with string tension σ_{2A} obtained by fitting the ground state.

Figure 6.5: Flux tube excitation energies from the $SU(4)$, $q = 1, 2$ calculations in Figure 6.3, extracted using Equation (5.11). Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions from Equation (2.98).

Figure 6.6: Flux tube excitation energies from the $SU(5)$, $q = 1, 2$ calculations in Figure 6.4, extracted using Equation (5.11). Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions from Equation (2.98).

Figure 6.7: Energies of the lightest four states with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$, for winding flux tubes in the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation of $SU(4)$ at $\beta = 50$. Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions of Equation (2.98), with the string tension obtained by fitting the ground state.

Figure 6.8: Energies of the lightest four states with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$, for winding flux tubes in the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation of $SU(5)$ at $\beta = 80$. Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions of Equation (2.98), with the string tension obtained by fitting the ground state.

Figure 6.9: Energies of the lightest four states with $q = 0, 1, 2$, for winding flux tubes in the $k = 2$ symmetric representation of $SU(4)$ at $\beta = 50$. Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions of Equation (2.98), with the string tension obtained by fitting the ground state.

Figure 6.10: Energies of the lightest four states with $q = 0, 1, 2$, for winding flux tubes in the $k = 2$ symmetric representation of $SU(5)$ at $\beta = 80$. Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions of Equation (2.98), with the string tension obtained by fitting the ground state.

Figure 6.11: Flux tube excitation energies from the SU(4) $q = 1, 2$ calculations in Figure 6.9, extracted using Equation (5.11). Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions from Equation (2.98).

Figure 6.12: Flux tube excitation energies from the SU(5) $q = 1, 2$ calculations in Figure 6.10, extracted using Equation (5.11). Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions from Equation (2.98).

Figure 6.13: The overlap $|O_{AS}(i, j; t = 0)|$ as defined by Equation (6.12) for $SU(4)$ and $SU(5)$ in left and right panels respectively, $L = 32a$ and $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ with $i, j = 1 - 80$.

Figure 6.14: Overlaps squared onto $k = 2A$ (red circles) and $k = 2S$ (blue squares) of the low-lying $k = 2$ flux-tube states with the lengths shown. In sectors from left to right, $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 2.1$, $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 3.1$, $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 4.2$, $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 2.1$, $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 3.1$, $\{P = -, q = 0\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 4.2$. The guide lines demonstrate how the energy levels alternate from being antisymmetric to being symmetric.

Figure 6.15: Overlaps squared onto $k = 2A$ (red circles) and $k = 2S$ (blue squares) of the low-lying $k = 2$ flux-tube states with the lengths shown. In sectors from left to right, $\{P = +, q = 1\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 2.1$, $\{P = +, q = 1\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 3.1$, $\{P = +, q = 1\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 4.2$, $\{P = -, q = 1\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 2.1$, $\{P = -, q = 1\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 3.1$, $\{P = -, q = 1\}$ at $l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \sim 4.2$. The guide lines demonstrate how the energy levels alternate from being antisymmetric to being symmetric.

Figure 6.16: Spectrum of $k = 2$ flux loops with $P = -$ and $q = 0$, as extracted using only our usual normal $k = 2$ basis of $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\}$ operators, as in Equations (4.11) and (4.11), and excluding the w states.

Figure 6.17: Spectrum of $k = 2$ flux loops with $P = -$ and $q = 0$, as extracted using the extended basis of operators $\{k = 2A\} \oplus \{k = 2S\} \oplus \{w = 2\}$, that includes $w = 2$ $k = 1$ operators as in Equation (4.15).

Figure 6.18: The contribution of each of our extended basis of operators to the ground and first excited states shown in Figure 6.17 for $L_{\parallel} = 16$. For $i \leq 100$ the operators are the ordinary $k = 2$ ones and for $i > 100$ the operators are the additional $w = 2$ ones.

Figure 6.19: Four left panels: The Overlaps $|O_{n_f, n_{2A}}|^2$ defined in Equation (6.22) for the lightest four states in the $SU(5)$ $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ and flux tube length $l = 16a$. Four right panels: The Overlaps $|O_{n_f, n_{2S}}|^2$ defined in Equation (6.22) for the lightest four states in the $SU(5)$ $k = 2$ symmetric representation with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ and flux tube length $l = 16a$.

Figure 6.20: Four left panels: The Overlaps $|O_{n_f, n_{2A}}|^2$ defined in Equation (6.22) for the lightest four states in the $SU(5)$ $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ and flux tube length $l = 32a$. Four right panels: The Overlaps $|O_{n_f, n_{2S}}|^2$ defined in Equation (6.22) for the lightest four states in the $SU(5)$ $k = 2$ symmetric representation with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ and flux tube length $l = 32a$.

Chapter 7

Discussion and Future Work

7.1 Conclusions

In this thesis we studied and presented the low-lying spectra of the closed $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ flux tubes in $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories. We did so using the formulation of lattice gauge theories. To perform this calculation we constructed a basis of operators with transverse deformations for each configuration of quantum numbers. The use of this large basis of operators appears to be convenient for two reasons. Firstly, it is the only way to extract the low-lying excitation spectrum of the closed flux tube with high confidence since this enhances the overlaps onto the physical states. Secondly, it enables us to study states which fall into the non-trivial sectors of the spectrum described by the quantum numbers of the transverse parity P and non-zero longitudinal momentum q .

The resulting spectra were compared to energy expressions derived by known effective string theoretical models. These approaches are the Nambu-Goto free string action, the Polchinski and Strominger effective action [15] which has also been used by Drummond [16] and Dass and Matlock [18], so as to improve older results, and finally the Lüscher and Weisz approach [21], which was also used by Aharony and Karzbrun [20] so as to improve older results.

The main astonishing observation can simply be expressed by the following question: why should a short flux tube, that looks more like a fat blob rather than a tube, have the phonon-like spectrum of a short and infinitesimally thin non-interacting bosonic string? This needs to be investigated deeply and receive attention from researchers working on effective string theoretical descriptions of the QCD string and gauge/gravity duality. Does this actually suggest that the flux tube is a thin string with its width being just a manifestation of the zero-point fluctuations? Does this suggest that in some kind of gauge/string duality the starting point for describing even a short fat flux tube is a thin string? Does this mean that in a field theoretical point of view, instead of using the Gaussian action [11] as a starting point, one should use the full Nambu-Goto action and add correction terms to it? Resuming our results let us point out our main observations.

Firstly, Nambu-Goto free string model appears to provide a very good description for the closed fundamental flux tube even at short lengths ($l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 1.5$) which are comparable to its width. It is remarkable that the correction term for the ground state with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ has an unnaturally tiny value of $\mathcal{O}(\lesssim 1/10)$. This is stunning since one would expect that if a flux tube is to be described by an effective string theory model, then these corrections would be at least of $\mathcal{O}(1)$. In addition, it appears that, none of the other effective string

theoretical models approaches our results as fast as Nambu-Goto does.

To a very good approximation the low-lying spectrum of the $k = 2$ flux tube falls into sectors that belong to nearly pure antisymmetric and symmetric representations, showing that $k = 2$ strings know not only about the centre of the group Z_N , but also about the full $SU(N)$ gauge group. We observed that the lightest states for various momenta q in the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation of colour are, for length not too small, very close to those of Nambu-Goto. The higher excited states, although stringy, appear to exhibit large deviations from Nambu-Goto. We found that in the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation of colour, if a state has two phonons of the same absolute momentum, then its deviations from Nambu-Goto are negligible when the phonons have exactly the same momenta, and large when the momenta are exactly opposite. The correction term for the ground state of the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation with $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ has a natural value of $\mathcal{O}(1 - 10)$. Although afflicted from important statistical uncertainties, the lightest states for various momenta q in the $k = 2$ symmetric representation of colour are recognisably stringy. Additionally, our results provide evidence that the $k = 2$ spectrum includes unbound fundamental doubly-wound ($w = 2$) states.

Finally, we do not observe any “extra” states associated with additional massive modes, neither in the fundamental nor in the $k = 2$ closed flux tube spectra. However, this does not mean that such kind of states do not exist in the torelon spectrum in $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories. It is likely that these states indeed exist, but do not couple at all to our incomplete basis of operators. The basic problem results from the fact that due to the lack of a concrete description of these states we are unable to encode the right physical properties within our operators. We have to rely, therefore, on guesses and intuitive beliefs on how an operator incorporates the right properties. One perhaps could create Polyakov operators using links in different blocking levels so as to “simulate” blobs with width larger than the rest of the flux tube hoping that this will couple to such additional states; a calculation involving these operators is relatively easy and fast and will probably be included in our future projects. Nevertheless, one can accidentally construct operators able to project onto additional non-string-like states in $D = 3 + 1$, where in principle one could possibly create transverse deformations with much more complicated structure than in $D = 2 + 1$. In fact it appears that the $D = 3 + 1$ spectrum, which is briefly discussed in the Appendix B, exhibits behaviour that cannot be recognised as being string-like.

7.2 Future Work

It is in fact impossible to describe all the further projects one could pursue towards the investigation of the closed flux tube spectrum. However, what we learned in this thesis is that the variational calculation - in combination with a large basis of operators - is a powerful tool that can reveal the excitation spectrum of the closed flux tube. The latter hides the non-trivial information contributing to the quest for the right effective string theory description. Having already been equipped by this powerful tool, we can either expand it or use it as it is in order to perform a number of complementary calculations.

It would be interesting to improve our results for the excited states, so that we accurately quantify their corrections to Nambu-Goto in an attempt to derive specific conclusions about the non-trivial interactions between phonons for both $k = 1$ and $k = 2$. Although for $k = 2$ we came to some conclusion about the interaction between two phonons, in the lighter and, therefore, more sensitive to momentum and lattice corrections $k = 1$ spectrum this was not

possible. It could be that an improved calculation may well show that the closed $k = 1$ flux tube displays the same kind of behaviour. The improvement can be done by increasing the statistics and the overlaps. The former can be achieved by simply performing a simulation for a longer period of time and the latter by increasing the number of operators.

Another interesting task would be the further investigation of whether the $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ $D = 2 + 1$ spectra include non-stringy states. Although this was extensively discussed in previous sections, we note that this can only be achieved by testing bases which consist of operators with different shapes. Although conceptually easy, constructing and testing different bases of operators in addition to limitations in computational resources make this task hard but not inaccessible.

As it was shown, the first excited state of the $k = 2$ antisymmetric representation $\{P = +, q = 0\}$ although stringy, exhibits a significant deviating behaviour from Nambu-Goto which appears to be independent of N . This has been interpreted as being caused by the interaction energy of the two phonons with opposite momenta. Hence, it would also be interesting to check how this depends upon k . To this purpose we shall perform similar calculations for several values of k , let us say, $k = 3, 4, 5$ and compare the resulting spectra. This will reveal more information about the non-trivial interactions of phonons namely how these depend upon k . In such a calculation we could also investigate if the closed k -flux tube spectrum includes unbound fundamental k -wound ($w = k$) states. This may lead to a generalisation of our current results for any k . However, as k and, thus N , increases, the spectrum of the fully antisymmetric representation becomes heavier making the calculations increasingly susceptible to systematic errors. Additionally, by increasing k the number of operators is also rising, making the simulation slower and the memory consumption exploding beyond the CPU limits. The latter could be a natural obstacle that we might never overcome while the former suggests that this would be a long time scale calculation that could take a couple of years to complete. Complementarily, it would be interesting to investigate how the spectra of higher representations (see Section 1.3.1) of \mathcal{N} -ality k behave, and if this can be described by an effective string theory model.

It should be mentioned that calculations for $k = 1, 2, 3$ and $q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 8$ in $D = 2 + 1$ $SU(6)$ gauge theory at $\beta = 171$ ($a\sqrt{\sigma_f} \simeq 0.09$) and for a large range of flux tube lengths ($l\sqrt{\sigma_f} \in [1.4, 5.6]$) are under way. This will partially contribute to some of the proposed ideas, and will complete the $k = 1$ calculation, since the missing link between the results is the spectrum for $SU(6)$ at the finer lattice spacing.

Finally, we would like to investigate the fundamental and $k \geq 2$ $SU(N)$ closed flux tube spectra in $D = 3 + 1$. In fact the spectrum of the closed fundamental flux tube in $D = 3 + 1$ $SU(N)$ gauge theories has already been analysed and awaits publication [5]. However, due to lack of space its presentation in this thesis is impossible and we, therefore, provide only a very brief overview of this in the Appendix B.

Appendix A

Explicit Expressions of the Operators

If the longitudinal direction is denoted by $\hat{\mu}$, then the explicit forms of the operators before being summed over the spatial lattice sites are the following:

1. \mathcal{C}_1 : Straight line path:

$$\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_1, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}) = \left[\prod_{j=1}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_1, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b). \quad (\text{A.1})$$

(for the straight line path $\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_1, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) = \Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_1, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) = \Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_1, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}).$)

2. \mathcal{C}_2 : Square pulse path:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_2, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x}) U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\ &\times \left[\prod_{j=2}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_2, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\ \Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_2, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\ &\times \left[\prod_{j=2}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_2, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

3. \mathcal{C}_3 : Rectangular pulse path:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_3, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x}) U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\nu} + \hat{\mu})) U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\ &\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_3, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\ \Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_3, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2 \cdot \hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\ &\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_3, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

4. \mathcal{C}_4 : Wave-like pulse i:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_4, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int}\frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_4, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_4, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int}\frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_4, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.4}$$

5. \mathcal{C}_5 : Wave-like pulse ii (for $b > 1$):

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_5, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= U_{\nu}^{b-1}(\vec{x})U_{\mu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\mu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(2\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=2}^{\text{Int}\frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_5, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_5, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= U_{\nu}^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu})U_{\mu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U_{\mu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=2}^{\text{Int}\frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_5, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.5}$$

6. \mathcal{C}_6 : Double wave-like pulse i (for $b > 1$):

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_6, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= \prod_{k=0}^1 \{ U_{\nu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-2}ka\hat{\mu})U_{\mu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\nu} + 2k\hat{\mu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(2k+1)\hat{\mu})U_{\nu}^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a((2k+1)\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a((2k+1)\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a((2k+2)\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \} \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int}\frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_6, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_6, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= \prod_{k=0}^1 \{ U_{\nu}^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(2k\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\mu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(2k\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a((2k+1)\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(2k+1)\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a((2k+1)\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(2k+2)\hat{\mu}) \} \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int}\frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_6, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.6}$$

7. \mathcal{C}_7 : Double wave-like pulse ii (for $b > 1$):

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_7, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +) &= U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U^{b-1\dagger}_\nu(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U^{b-1\dagger}_\nu(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(2\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 3 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu}))U^{b-1\dagger}_\nu(\vec{x} + 4 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_\parallel}{2^{b-1}}} U_\mu^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_7, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_7, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -) &= U^{b-1\dagger}_\nu(\vec{x} - 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U^{b-1}_\nu(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu}))U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(2\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U^{b-1\dagger}_\nu(\vec{x} + 3 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U^{b-1\dagger}_\nu(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U^{b-1}_\nu(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(4\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_\parallel}{2^{b-1}}} U_\mu^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_7, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.7}$$

8. \mathcal{C}_8 : Double lump operator i (for $b > 1$):

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_8, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +) &= U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U^{b-1\dagger}_\nu(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 3 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu}))U^{b-1\dagger}_\nu(\vec{x} + 4 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_\parallel}{2^{b-1}}} U_\mu^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_8, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_8, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -) &= U^{b-1\dagger}_\nu(\vec{x} - 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U^{b-1\dagger}_\nu(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U^{b-1}_\nu(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(4\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_\parallel}{2^{b-1}}} U_\mu^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_8, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.8}$$

9. \mathcal{C}_9 : Double lump operator ii (for $b > 1$):

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_9, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +) &= U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu})U_\nu^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3 \cdot \hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3 \cdot \hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(4 \cdot \hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_\parallel}{2^{b-1}}} U_\mu^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F_\mu}(\mathcal{C}_9, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_9, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -) &= U_\nu^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu})U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 3 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3 \cdot \hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 4 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_\parallel}{2^{b-1}}} U_\mu^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F_\mu}(\mathcal{C}_9, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.9}$$

10. \mathcal{C}_{10} : Double lump operator iii (for $b > 1$):

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_{10}, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, +) &= U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu})U_\nu^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(2 \cdot \hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 3 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3 \cdot \hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 4 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_\parallel}{2^{b-1}}} U_\mu^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F_\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{10}, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_\mu^b(\mathcal{C}_{10}, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, -) &= U_\nu^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-2}a\hat{\nu})U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu})U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-2}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3 \cdot \hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_\mu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(3 \cdot \hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_\nu^{b-1}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-2}a(4 \cdot \hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_\parallel}{2^{b-1}}} U_\mu^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F_\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{10}, L_\parallel, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.10}$$

11. \mathcal{C}_{11} : Clip-like pulse:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{11}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) \left[\prod_{j=1}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{11}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{11}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu})U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x}) \left[\prod_{j=1}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{11}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.11}$$

12. \mathcal{C}_{12} : Expanded Clip-like pulse:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{12}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x})U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2 \cdot \hat{\nu} + \hat{\mu}))U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2 \cdot \hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2 \cdot \hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - 2 \cdot \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} - 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=1}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{12}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{12}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} - 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - 2 \cdot \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2 \cdot \hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu})U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2 \cdot \hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2 \cdot \hat{\nu} + \hat{\mu}))U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x}) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=1}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{12}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.12}$$

13. \mathcal{C}_{13} : Double Clip-like pulse i:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{13}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= \prod_{j=1}^2 \{U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(j-1)\hat{\mu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a((j-1)\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}aj\hat{\mu})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(j\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a((j-1)\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a((j-1)\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(j-1)\hat{\mu})\} \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{13}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{13}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= \prod_{j=1}^2 \{U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a((j-1)\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a((j-1)\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(j\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}aj\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a((j-1)\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(j-1)\hat{\mu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(j-1)\hat{\mu})\} \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{13}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.13}$$

14. \mathcal{C}_{14} : Double Clip-like pulse ii:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{14}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu})U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \left[\prod_{j=2}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{14}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{14}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu})U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x})U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=2}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{14}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.14}$$

15. \mathcal{C}_{15} : Double Clip-like pulse iii:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{15}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{15}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{15}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu})U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x})U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=3}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{15}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.15}$$

16. \mathcal{C}_{16} : Double Clip-like pulse iv:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{16}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu})U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=2}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{16}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_{16}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} - 2^{b-1}a\hat{\nu})U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu}))U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2 \cdot 2^{b-1}a\hat{\mu}) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(2\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}))U_{\mu}^{b\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}a(\hat{\mu} + \hat{\nu})) \\
&\times \left[\prod_{j=2}^{\text{Int} \frac{L_{\parallel}}{2^{b-1}}} U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + 2^{b-1}(j-1)a\hat{\mu}) \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_{16}, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.16}$$

17. Wave Operator: For $m = \text{Int}[L_{\parallel}/2n]$, $n = 1, \dots, \text{Int}[L_{\parallel}/2^{b-1}]$ and $l = 1, \dots, \text{Int}[L_{\perp}/2^{b-1}]$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_W, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) &= \left[\prod_{i_m=1}^m \left\{ \left[\prod_{i_l=1}^l U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + a2^{b-1}(2n(i_m-1)\hat{\mu} + (i_l-1)\hat{\nu})) \right] \right. \right. \\
&\times \left. \left\{ \prod_{i_n=1}^n U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + a2^{b-1}(l\hat{\nu} + (2n(i_m-1) + (i_n-1))\hat{\mu})) \right\} \right. \\
&\times \left. \left[\prod_{i_l=1}^l U_{\nu}^{\dagger}(\vec{x} + a2^{b-1}(n(2i_m-1)\hat{\mu} + (l-i_l)\hat{\nu})) \right] \right. \\
&\times \left. \left[\prod_{i_l=1}^l U_{\nu}^{\dagger}(\vec{x} + a2^{b-1}(n2^{b-1}(2i_m-1)\hat{\mu} - i_l\hat{\nu})) \right] \right. \\
&\times \left. \left\{ \prod_{i_n=1}^n U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + a2^{b-1}((n(2i_m-1) + (i_n-1))\hat{\mu} - l\hat{\nu})) \right\} \right. \\
&\times \left. \left. \left[\prod_{i_l=1}^l U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + a2^{b-1}(2ni_m\hat{\mu} - (l+1-i_l)\hat{\nu})) \right] \right\} \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_W, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b), \\
\Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_W, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) &= \left[\prod_{i_m=1}^m \left\{ \left[\prod_{i_l=1}^l U_{\nu}^{\dagger}(\vec{x} + 2an2^{b-1}(i_m-1)\hat{\mu} - i_l\hat{\nu}) \right] \right. \right. \\
&\times \left. \left\{ \prod_{i_n=1}^n U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + a2^{b-1}((2n(i_m-1) + (i_n-1))\hat{\mu} - l\hat{\nu})) \right\} \right. \\
&\times \left. \left[\prod_{i_l=1}^l U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + a2^{b-1}(n2^{b-1}(2i_m-1)\hat{\mu} - (l+1-i_l)\hat{\nu})) \right] \right. \\
&\times \left. \left[\prod_{i_l=1}^l U_{\nu}^b(\vec{x} + a2^{b-1}(n(2i_m-1)\hat{\mu} + (i_l-1)\hat{\nu})) \right] \right. \\
&\times \left. \left\{ \prod_{i_n=1}^n U_{\mu}^b(\vec{x} + a2^{b-1}((n(2i_m-1) + (i_n-1))\hat{\mu} + l\hat{\nu})) \right\} \right. \\
&\times \left. \left. \left[\prod_{i_l=1}^l U_{\nu}^{\dagger}(\vec{x} + a2^{b-1}(2ni_m\hat{\mu} - (l-i_l)\hat{\nu})) \right] \right\} \right] \times U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_W, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b).
\end{aligned} \tag{A.17}$$

It is noted that in the wave operator $U_{F\mu}(\mathcal{C}_W, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, b) = \mathbf{1}$ only if $2n \times \text{Int}[L_{\parallel}/2n] = L_{\parallel}$. In this case:

$$\sum_{x_{\parallel}} \Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_W, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, +) e^{ip_{\parallel}x_{\parallel}} = \sum_{x_{\parallel}} \Phi_{\mu}^b(\mathcal{C}_W, L_{\parallel}, \vec{x}, -) e^{ip_{\parallel}x_{\parallel}} \begin{cases} \neq 0 & : p_{\parallel} = 0 \\ = 0 & : p_{\parallel} \neq 0 \end{cases} \tag{A.18}$$

indicating that for this special case the wave operator is translationally invariant and, therefore, forbids the projection onto the $P = -$ and $q \neq 0$ sectors.

Furthermore, these operators have been used only in the calculation of the fundamental flux tube spectrum. By taking a look at the eigenvectors extracted during the variational procedure, we realise that these wave-functionals contribute a little or even not at all in the light excited states. For example, see Figure A.1. This suggests that their usage might not be justified since their contribution is minimal.

The fact that the contribution of these operators is insignificant may be due to a number of reasons. One possibility is that all these wave-functionals are somehow included in other pulse-like operators, whose contribution is much stronger in the

variational calculation. Indeed all the paths scetched out by the wave operators at a certain blocking level, are already included in pulse-like operators of higher blocking levels. Another possibility is that these operators may correspond to multi-mode states associated with extremely high energy excitations and they therefore, fail to project onto the light excited states we are aiming for. In any case, we know that the wave operators \mathcal{C}_W cannot give significant information and, thus, we exclude them from those of our calculations that are the slowest.

Figure A.1: The contribution of each operator $|a_i|^2$ obtained in the variational analysis with $k = 1$, $P = +$, $q = 0$, $SU(3)$, $\beta = 21.000$ and $L = 16a$ for the first and second excited states. The vector a_i corresponds to the eigenvectors of the normalised correlation matrix $C^{-1}(0)C(t = a)$ according to Equation (3.90).

Appendix B

$D = 3 + 1$ closed fundamental flux tubes in a nutshell

The “physically more relevant” case of 3+1 dimensions is much more complicated compared to the $D = 2 + 1$ analog, since the flux tube has now one extra dimensional degree of freedom. This results in the states of the closed flux tube spectrum to be categorised according to the lattice symmetry group of rotations about the principal flux tube axis. The lattice symmetry of rotations about the flux tube axis is denoted as $C_{4\nu} \otimes Z(\mathcal{R})$ for zero longitudinal momentum and $C_{4\nu}$ for non-zero longitudinal momentum. The group $C_{4\nu}$ includes the rotations of $\pi/2$ around the tube axis, which generate the quantum number of angular momentum $J = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2$ and the reflections on the plane orthogonal to the tube which gives rise to the quantum number of $P_{\mathcal{P}}$ parity. This symmetry distinguishes the states in five different irreducible representations: $A_{1(2)}$ which corresponds to $J = 0, \pm 4, \dots$ and $P_{\mathcal{P}} = +(-)$, E which corresponds to $J = \pm 1, \pm 3, \dots$ and $B_{1(2)}$ corresponding to $J = \pm 2, \pm 6, \dots$ and $P_{\mathcal{P}} = +(-)$. $Z(\mathcal{R})$ is the two-element group that consists of the identity operation and the reflection across the same orthogonal plane giving rise to the quantum number of $P_{\mathcal{R}}$ parity. Hence, for zero longitudinal momentum the states are characterised by 10 different irreducible representations and for non-zero longitudinal momentum by 5.

Using transverse deformations that extend in the two transverse directions, we constructed a large basis of operators ~ 700 for all the irreducible representations of the lattice symmetry group of rotations. We first performed a calculation for $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 6.0625$ that corresponds to a lattice spacing of $a \simeq 0.1\text{fm}$. To check how the spectrum changes as we tend to the continuum, we performed a calculation for $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 6.3380$ that corresponds to a lattice spacing $a \simeq 0.065\text{fm}$. We also checked how the spectrum alters as it moves to larger values of N by performing a calculation at $SU(5)$ and $\beta = 17.630$ which is associated with the lattice spacing $a \simeq 0.1\text{fm}$. As in the case of $D = 2 + 1$, we apply the variational calculation on each correlator matrix and, subsequently, we extract the spectrum using effective energy estimations and single hyperbolic cosine fits. In Figure B.1 we present a comparison of the $q = 0, 1, 2$ Nambu-Goto ground states with our data for $\beta = 6.0625$. The ground state for $q = 0$, according to Nambu-Goto should have a degeneracy of one with quantum numbers $\{J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = +, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$. We fit our results from the projection onto the ground state of the closed flux tube with the same quantum numbers to Nambu-Goto plus a correction term; thus, we obtain the string tension. By definition the ground state of $\{A_1, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$ will, therefore, become consistent with Nambu-Goto by some very small value of the flux tube length. Let us now move to the ground state of $q = 1$. Ac-

Figure B.1: Energies of the lightest six states with $q = 0, 1, 2$, for a single-wound flux tube in the fundamental representation of colour in $D = 3 + 1$, $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 6.0625$. Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions of Equation (2.56) with $D = 4$ and the string tension obtained by fitting the ground state $\{A_1, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$ (or $\{J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = +, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$).

According to Nambu-Goto this state should be one-fold degenerate with $J = 1$. By projecting onto all the irreducible representations of the fundamental flux tube with $q = 1$, we find that the E ground state is very well described by the Nambu-Goto prediction, while all the other states corresponding to other irreducible representations are far away. Nambu-Goto predicts that the ground state for $q = 2$ should be four-fold degenerate, consisting of a state with $\{J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = +\}$, a state with $\{J = 1\}$, a state with $\{J = 2, P_{\mathcal{P}} = +\}$ and finally a state with $\{J = 2, P_{\mathcal{P}} = -\}$. By projecting onto the five irreducible representations of $q = 2$ we find that the ground states of the four irreducible representations with group theoretical content A_1, E, B_1 and B_2 are adequately described by the theoretical prediction provided by Nambu-Goto. This spectrum appears to remain relatively unaltered as we move to the continuum and to the large- N limit.

It would be interesting to view what happens to the first excited state for $q = 0$ with $N_L = N_R = 1$. This is presented in Figure B.2. According to the construction of the string states within the Nambu-Goto framework, this energy level should be four-fold degenerate with a state of $\{J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = +, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$, a state of $\{J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = -, P_{\mathcal{R}} = -\}$, a state of $\{J = 2, P_{\mathcal{P}} = +, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$ and finally a state with $\{J = 2, P_{\mathcal{P}} = -, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$. By applying the variational technique followed by fits and effective energy determinations onto all the irreducible representations for $q = 0$, we find that the first excited state of $\{A_1, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$ is very close to the Nambu-Goto prediction. In fact it appears to deviate slightly from Nambu-Goto, but as the length of the tube increases it approaches until it becomes consistent. In addition it appears that the ground state of $\{B_1, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$ is almost onto Nambu-Goto and the ground state of $\{B_2, P_{\mathcal{R}} = -\}$ approaches Nambu-Goto from above until it falls onto it. However, this nice agreement with Nambu-Goto breaks while investigating the ground state

Figure B.2: Energies of the lightest five states with $q = 0$, for a single-wound flux tube in the fundamental representation of colour in $D = 3 + 1$, $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 6.0625$. Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions of Equation (2.56) with $D = 4$, with the string tension obtained by fitting the ground state $\{A_1, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$ (or $J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = +, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +$).

$\{A_1, P_{\mathcal{R}} = -\}$ ¹. This state shows substantial deviation from Nambu-Goto and appears to approach the theoretical prediction only very slowly. However, we should be careful and not overlook the fact that to quite a good approximation, it is greater than the ground state $\{A_1, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$ by a nearly constant value. Nothing guarantees that this converges to Nambu-Goto; it could possibly cross the theoretical prediction at some larger value of the flux tube length and keep rising with l . The striking contrast of this state with the other three makes it to appear to be anomalous. This behaviour does not change as we move to the continuum and its energy level drops even more as we move to the larger value of N .

An even more anomalous state appears in the spectrum of $q = 1$, which is presented in Figure B.3. According to Nambu-Goto, the first excited energy level ($N_L = 2, N_R = 1$) should have a degeneracy pattern of six. These states are supposed to appear as the ground states of $\{J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = +\}$, $\{J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = -\}$, $\{J = 3\}$, $\{J = 2, P_{\mathcal{P}} = +\}$, $\{J = 2, P_{\mathcal{P}} = -\}$ and the first excited state of $\{J = 1\}$. Assuming that all the states would be stringy, we expected that Nambu-Goto would provide a relatively good description for the ground states of A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2 and the first and second excited states of E ; since the ground state of E is already occupied by the ground state of $\{J = 1\}$ with $N_L = 1, N_R = 0$, these two states would correspond to the ground state of $\{J = 3\}$ and first excited state of $\{J = 1\}$. Although, we managed to probe through out all the irreducible representations of the lattice group of rotations, it was impossible to project onto all these six states. The reason is that,

¹It should be mentioned that at the level of the first excited state ($N_L = N_R = 1$) we do not expect any higher spin $J = 3, 4, \dots$ states to show up. This is an assumption based on the fact that these states would be extremely massive and the phononic construction prohibits their appearance. Nevertheless, it is expected that for the $q = 0$ sector such states will show up by the level of the second excited state ($N_L = N_R = 2$) which is not accessible given that the overlaps onto such states are too low. We, therefore, assume that $A_{1,2}$ correspond to $J = 0$, E to $J = 1$ and $B_{1,2}$ to $J = 2$.

Figure B.3: Energies of the lightest five states with $q = 1$, for a single-wound flux tube in the fundamental representation of colour in $D = 3 + 1$, $SU(3)$ at $\beta = 6.0625$. Lines are the Nambu-Goto predictions of Equation (2.56) with $D = 4$, with the string tension obtained by fitting the ground state $\{A_1, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +\}$ (or $J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = +, P_{\mathcal{R}} = +$).

driven by the fact that the projection onto some of these state is limited, the signal of their correlators is too low. We, therefore, extracted only four of these states. Three of them and more particularly the ground states of A_1 , B_1 and the first excited state of E appear to be very close to Nambu-Goto, while once more the A_2 ground state appears to possess an anomalous behaviour: it deviates a lot from the theoretical prediction and in addition it does not show a single sign of convergence and drops more as we move to the continuum and the large- N limit.

It appears that the spectrum of the closed fundamental flux tube in $D = 3 + 1$ is also mostly very close to Nambu-Goto down to very small flux tube lengths. However, there are a few states, such as the ground state of $\{J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = -, P_{\mathcal{R}} = -, q = 0\}$, that exhibit large deviations from Nambu-Goto. Some of these states such as the ground state of $\{J = 0, P_{\mathcal{P}} = -, q = 1\}$ do not show a single sign of converging to Nambu-Goto, not even at large values of l . The following question arises here: are these states Nambu-Goto-like with a very slow converging behaviour or are they either some mixture of stringy and massive mode excitations or pure massive modes? This is a question that needs to be to be further investigated. However, in the absence of a concrete theoretical prediction for the energy levels of these states, such an identification would be an extremely difficult task. Nevertheless, it is clear that in $D = 3 + 1$, apart from the string-like, in addition there is some kind of non-stringy dynamics.

Even though the calculation enables us to make some strong statements about the qualitative behaviour of the spectrum, the low overlaps ($\sim 80 - 90\%$), appearing by the level of the first excited level in each irreducible representation, prohibit us from providing a more quantitative description of the excitation spectrum. Several things can be done in order to increase these overlaps. Firstly we can use more operators in the variational

technique, and secondly we can tune the parameters² that control the spreading outwards to the spatial super links of the smearing/blocking procedure so as to maximise the overlap onto the excited states. Both procedures face important difficulties: the latter might be proven very time-consuming since the overlap onto these states might maximise by a different configuration of these parameters for each individual irreducible representation. And the former will face memory limitations due to the large size of the correlation matrix. In addition, by including more operators in the calculation, the time consumption increases. In any case both procedures must be investigated since this is in addition an important step before proceeding to a successful extraction of the $k \geq 2$ -closed flux tube spectrum in $D = 3 + 1$.

²The parameters we used have been tuned in such a way so as to maximise the overlaps onto the ground state.

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